

Deliverable 3.4

The monitoring, negotiation and decision support solutions toolkit – Final release

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Summary

WP3 aims at developing and deploying a series of water-smart applications, to be demonstrated at six Living Labs (LLs). The different solutions developed and demonstrated in T3.2-T3.7 are conceptually assembled into 2 coherent toolkits, a) the monitoring, negotiation and decision support solutions toolkit and b) the water cycle modelling and assessment solutions toolkit. The current report documents the final release of the monitoring, negotiation and decision support solutions toolkit which is comprised of the following ten tools: the water reuse strategic platform (#16), the environment for decision support and alternative course selection (#17), Re-Actor (#18), the sludge management platform (#19), the UWC observatory (#20), the stormwater reuse management system (#21), the Nessie System (#29), the Environmental Dashboard (#30), the Digital Enabler (#32) and the climate-readiness certification tool (#33) and complements the other toolkit. The final release of the toolkit aims at updating the readers about the latest developments of tools, focusing on tool description, attributes and information around pre-existing background, developments/advancements within the project, navigation and primary functionalities, interoperability, indicative applications and synergistic benefits and how to access each tool and test data. D3.4 dives deeper in the application of tools to the LLs by introducing initially the water-smartness challenges and ambition of the LLs, presents the selected technologies and products and explains the integrative use, conceptual links, data flows and pilot interactions. Further, it describes the pre-processing stage and setup process before documenting the final results and lessons learned from tools and technologies' application to the LLs. Building on results from the cases, the toolkit attempts to provide a more holistic and complementary picture of how water-smartness can be enhanced while highlighting complementarity and replicability aspects of tools.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AOP	Advanced Oxidation Processes
API	Application Programming Interface
ARPAV	Agenzia regionale per la protezione ambientale Veneto
ASR	Aquifer Storage and Recovery
BOD	Biological Oxygen Demand
BOHB	Bayesian optimization with Hyperband
BS	Baseline Scenario
BSD	Berkeley Source Distribution
BWS	B-WaterSmart
CAPEX	Capital Expenditures
CARD	Controlled Agricultural Recharge and Drainage
CCRO	Closed Circuit Reverse Osmosis
CDF	Cumulative Distribution Function
CE	Circular Economy
CLC	CORINE Land Cover
CML	Camara Municipal de Lisboa
CO	Confidential
CoP	Community of Practice
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CRC	Climate Ready Certificate
CSS	Cascading Style Sheets
CSV	Comma-separated values
DALY	Disability Adjusted Life Years
DAP	Data Application Products

DBMS	Database Management System
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary
DE	Digital Enabler
DPR	Direct Potable Reuse
DSS	Decision Support System
DW	Distilled Water
DWD	Deutscher Wetterdienst
DWTP	Drinking Water Treatment Plant
Dx.x	Deliverable
EC-JRC	European Commission - Joint Research Centre
EEA	European Environment Agency
EEC	European Economic Community
EEPA	European Enterprise Promotion Awards
EI	Expected Impact
EU	European Union
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
FAQ	Frequently Asked Questions
FIWARE GE	FIWARE Generic Enabler
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
GDPR	General data protection regulation
GHG	Greenhouse gases
GIS	Geographical Information System
GPU	Graphics processing unit
GUI	Graphical User Interface
GW	Greywater

GWR	Greywater Recycling
HD	Hard Drive
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IdM	Identity Management
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IoT	Internet of Things
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IT	Information Technology
IWA	International Water Association
JRC	Joint Research Centre.
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Cost
LL(s)	Living Lab(s)
LNEC	Laboratorio Nacional de Engenharia Civil
MAR	Managed Aquifer Recharge
MIT	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
MS	Milestone
MSL	Machine Learning
NA	Not Available / Not applicable
NGO	Non-governmental organization

NGSI-LD	Next Generation Service Interfaces – Linked Data
NTUA	National Technical University of Athens
O3/RO	Ozone/reverse osmosis
OOWV	Oldenburgisch-Ostfriesischer Wasserverband
OPC	Open Platform Communications
OPEX	Operating Expenses
OS	Operating System
PC	Personal Computer
PDF	Portable Document Format
PET	Potential Evapontraspiration
PIF	Progetto Integrato Fusina
PLC	Programmable logic controller
PO	Project Officer
PU	Public
QCRA	Quantitative Cost Risk Analysis
QMRA	Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment
R&D	Research and Development
RAM	Random-Access Memory
RDSMG	Regional demand-supply matching GIS tool
REST	Representational State Transfer
RO	Reverse osmosis
RR	Resource Recovery
RW	Rainwater
RWDS	Reclaimed water distribution system
RWH	Rainwater Harvesting
SDFT	Short-term demand forecasting tool

SDM	System Dynamic Modelling
SM	Sewer Mining
SO	Strategic Objective
SSD	Solid-State Drive
SuTRa	Subsurface Transport and Removal
SWDP	Sea Water Desalination Plant
tbd	To Be Decided
TP	Technology Product
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
Tx.x	Task
UI	User's Interface
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
URN	Uniform Resource Name
UWC	Urban Water Cycle
UWOT	Urban Water Optioneering Tool
WC	Water closet
WE	Water Europe
WEM	Water Europe Marketplace
WEP	Water-Energy-Phosphorus
WFD	Water Framework Directive
WHG	Wasserhaushaltsgesetz
WiCE	Water in the Circular Economy
WM	Waching Machine
WP	Work Package
WPC	Water Production Centre
WPx	Work Package
WQ	Water quality

WRRF	Water resource recovery facility
WS	Water Smart
WSGI	Web Server Gateway Interface
WW	Wastewater
WWTP	Wastewater Treatment Plant
XML	Extensible markup language

Executive summary

The BWS project aims to accelerate the transformation to water-smart economies and societies in coastal Europe and beyond. To achieve this, the project is delivering (among others) smart data applications for more efficient and safe allocation and use of resources (water, energy, nutrients) while building on FIWARE technology that will enable interoperability and cross-sectoral exchange. The latter is considered as a key element for systemic change. While working on this purpose, WP3 “Water-Smart applications and data” focused on the development and deployment of a series of water-smart applications, to be demonstrated at the six Living Labs (LLs) of the BWS project, namely Alicante (ES), Bodø (NO), Flanders (BE), Lisbon (PT), East Frisia (DE) and Venice (IT). Research partners and innovative solution providers worked with the LLs representatives, i.e., the problem owners participating in the project, having high ambitions to address water-related challenges and opportunities in order to deliver tools and Information and Communications Technology (ICT) solutions (combined with technologies). The tools target to enhance water-smartness in (waste)water reuse, recovery of energy and materials, management of water systems and infrastructure, monitoring, negotiation and decision support, water cycle modelling and assessment, risk assessment and management, water demand analysis and natural resources’ management. This deliverable (D3.4) reports the final release of the monitoring, negotiation and decision support solutions toolkit and presents the 10 solutions (Table 1) developed in the related tasks (T3.2 – T3.7) in close collaboration with the Living Labs.

With the goal to develop, customize and demonstrate data applications for transparent management and interoperability, WP3 developed and proposed an interoperability approach in T3.1 building on FIWARE technology and its open specifications to increase the transferability of the water-smart applications. Tasks T3.2 – T3.7 develop and demonstrate advanced analytics, models and tools for challenges identified through individual LLs and customize some of them to be compatible with FIWARE. While co-developing and implementing tools that demonstrate the advantages of the project’s interoperability approach and putting together BWS solutions from a number of tools that address similar problems at different scales, two sets of solutions emerged (organized as described in section 4) that form the two ICT solutions toolkits of the project (Table 1). The numbering of the tools (i.e. ‘#xx’) is the same as in the Grant Agreement of the project, Annex 1 part B section 1.3.5 Table 5 and is consistently used through all documents prepared by B-WaterSmart that make reference to the tools.

- ***The monitoring, negotiation and decision support solutions toolkit*** which aims at improving water smartness by supporting the steps of context awareness, decision making, management, monitoring, and certification. The toolkit is comprised of 10 tools:
 - The Water Reuse Strategic Platform (#16) which has been built upon the Digital Enabler (#32),

- The Sludge Management Platform (#19) which has been also built upon the Digital Enabler (#32),
 - The Environment for Decision Support and Alternative Course Selection (#17),
 - The Re-Actor (#18),
 - The Urban Water Cycle (UWC) Observatory (#20),
 - The Stormwater Reuse Management System (#21),
 - The Nessie System (#29),
 - The Environmental Dashboard (#30) and
 - The Climate-Readiness Certification tool (#33).
- **The water cycle modelling and assessment solutions toolkit**, comes to supplement the above-mentioned toolkit. It is focused on advanced analytics for providing detailed evidence in support of decision-making. This is achieved by providing the tools to conduct simulations, predictions, demand/supply match-making and other quantitative analyses. This second toolkit is comprised of 8 tools:
 - The Urban Water Optioneering Tool (UWOT) (#22),
 - The Regional Demand-Supply Matching GIS tool (#23),
 - The Reclaimed Water Distribution Network Water Quality Model (#24),
 - The Water-Energy-Phosphorous Balance Planning Module (#25),
 - The QMRA+ tool (#26),
 - The Risk Assessment for Urban Water Reuse Module (#27),
 - The Short-Term Demand Forecasting Tool (#28)
 - The SuTRa tool (#31) ¹.

The two toolkits conceptually assemble the different solutions, developed and eventually demonstrated in T3.2 to 3.7, into two coherent solutions that provide added value with respect to the water related challenges of the case studies, serving at the same time as an umbrella helping to clarify a potential combined use of the different tools.

Table 1: The two BWS ICT solutions toolkits and the tools that assemble them. The name of the city that follows corresponds to relevant Living Labs, where the tool is being applied.

The monitoring, negotiation, and decision support solutions toolkit	The water cycle modelling and assessment solutions toolkit
1. Water-reuse strategic platform (#16) – Venice	1. UWOT (#22) – Flanders & East Frisia
2. Sludge management platform (#19) – Venice	2. Regional demand-supply matching GIS tool (#23) – East Frisia

¹ SuTRa tool was originally called "ASR pro" tool. The name of the tool has been changed to 'SuTRa' to better reflect the broader application potential.

3. Digital Enabler (#32) – Venice	3. Short-term demand forecasting tool (#28) – East Frisia
4. Re-Actor (#18) – Alicante	4. QMRA+ for water reuse and agriculture (#26) – Flanders
5. Environment for decision support and alternative course selection - Baseform (#17) – Lisbon	5. SuTRa (#31) – Flanders
6. UWC observatory (#20) – Lisbon	6. Reclaimed water distribution network water quality model - Baseform (#24) – Lisbon
7. Climate-readiness certification tool (#33) – Lisbon	7. Water-energy-phosphorous balance planning module - Baseform (#25) – Lisbon
8. Stormwater reuse management system (#21) – Flanders	8. Risk Assessment for urban water reuse module - Baseform (#27) – Lisbon
9. Nessie System (#29) – Bodø	
10. Environmental Dashboard (#30) – Bodø	

As noted earlier, this deliverable (D3.4) reports the final release of the monitoring, negotiation and decision support solutions toolkit and the tools that comprise it. The current report has been prepared in parallel with D3.5 “The water cycle modelling and assessment solutions toolkit – Final release” in order to ensure that the work in the related tasks is aligned and the information/results are presented in a consistent way. Another reason for doing that is to highlight the complementarity of both toolkits and propose synergistic ways in which the tools could be used to provide a more holistic and complementary picture of water-smartness at the water cycle scale, while building on results from the cases (including findings from technologies’ implementations in WP2, when relevant). The general sections of D3.4/D3.5 (i.e., Chapter 1- Chapter 4) are common for the two toolkits in order to set the base for the readers while ensuring that each toolkit report is autonomous, complements the other and assists readers in their navigation through the available contents. Similarly, the concluding section of the document includes some parts that are repeated in both reports. These are related to final considerations that document the conceptual links among all tools and describe how the 18 solutions of both toolkits are related to the water related challenges and the steps of the urban water cycle.

The final release deliverable of the monitoring, negotiation and decision support solutions toolkit (as well as the one of the other toolkit) aims at introducing the readers to the tools per se and to the final developments as well as to the actual application of tools to the case studies.

The following features of tools are addressed in the first part of the report (Chapter 5) and follow a common pattern across different tools:

- Description of tools and their attributes (Section x.x.1),
- Pre-existing background (context) (Section x.x.2),
- Developments/advancements made within the project (Section x.x.3),
- Navigation and primary functionalities (Section x.x.4),

- Interoperability options covering also FIWARE compatibility when supported (Section x.x.5),
- Indicative applications and synergistic benefits (Section x.x.6, when applicable²),
- Accessibility and test data (Section x.x.6 or x.x.7),

With regard to the application of tools to the case studies, which is documented in the second part of this report (Chapters 6-9), the information is structured under each LL and includes the following sections:

- Key Water Smart³ (WS) challenges, ambition and case study description,
- Application of tools and methods by providing information on:
 - the selected tools and technologies of the pilot,
 - the integrative use of tools, pilot interaction and data flows,
 - the pre-processing stage and input data
 - setup process and application
 - results
- Lessons extracted at the LL level,
- Summary table which provides concise information on the tools and technologies applications in order to be used for the population of the Water Europe Marketplace (WEM) and the dissemination of the LL work to a wider audience. The WEM, which is a versatile platform for networking, business development, discovering and sharing knowledge, and exhibiting achievement in the areas of Water, Energy, and Materials, was originally created as part of the NextGen project and evolved through the BWS and ULTIMATE projects into the Water Europe Marketplace, currently curated by Water Europe. The platform is accessible via the URL following URL.

<https://mp.watereurope.eu/>

For the case of Lisbon, the above parts are duplicated in D3.4 and D3.5 since the 6 tools demonstrated in the LL are split in the two toolkit reports. With this approach, the application of tools is presented in a consistent way, as well as the overall picture of the LL work which involves integration and close interaction of the applied solutions.

D3.4 also attempts to extract findings with regards to the interoperability, transferability and the replicability of the tools and the toolkit overall, which are documented in the concluding section.

² This section is not applicable for those tools that have been developed from scratch and do not have previous applications

³ See Section 2 about the opportunity of using smart water solutions and tools for water challenges

The tools of the monitoring, negotiation and decision support solutions toolkit are applied in 5 out of 6 LLs and are noted in the proceeding table (Table 2).

Table 2: Ambitions and challenges of the 5 LLs where the tools of the monitoring, negotiation and decision support solutions toolkit are applied.

Living Lab	Ambition	Challenge ⁴	Tools
Flanders	To become more water-smart	High drinking water demand due to dense population; high irrigation water demand for agriculture; groundwater overexploitation; water quality deterioration; water scarcity due to droughts and climate change.	#21
Bodø		Includes growing resident population and economy, increased pollution, and untapped efficiency potential.	#29, #30
Lisbon		Distance from freshwater sources; need to increase urban green areas; climate change; growing population and economy.	#17, #20, #33
Venice		The need for reuse and recovery schemes for wastewater & sludge, substantial limitations to reuse and recovery due to low acceptance, increasing water scarcity, and untapped efficiency potential due to low water and resources valorisation.	#16, #19, #32
Alicante		Water scarcity, limitations to water reuse due to high salinity, and limitations to water reuse due the lack of storage infrastructure to cover the time decoupling between production and demand.	#18

Note: the challenges included in the table are the ones defined in GA and documented in the M18 scientific progress report, under the LL section (1.3.2 to 1.3.7).

Regarding the interoperability options of tools, and as noted in MS17 “Draft input received from T3.2-3.7 for D3.2 and D3.3; 1/3 of WP3 apps FIWARE compliant” a third of WP3 apps

⁴ as defined in GA and documented in the M18 scientific progress report, under the LL section (1.3.2 to 1.3.7)

is foreseen to be FIWARE compliant at the end of their BWS development phase. In more detail, WP3 will deliver 19 applications (18 from T3.2-T3.7 - reported in the toolkits' deliverables D3.4/D3.5 and 1 from T3.9 - based on information found in D3.1) out of which 7 are FIWARE compliant. The last-mentioned tool is the water-smartness dashboard (#34) currently under development under T3.9 "Develop and deploy the water-smartness dashboard" and to be applied in all BWS case studies. The related deliverables of the water-smartness dashboard are D3.6 (early release) / D3.7 (final release). The other six tools developed in T3.2-T3.7 and are FIWARE compatible are the following:

1. Water-reuse strategic platform (#16)
2. Sludge management platform (#19)
3. Short-term demand forecasting tool (#28)
4. Nessie System (#29)
5. Environmental Dashboard (#30)
6. Digital Enabler (#32)

The tools have been reported in the current deliverable (D3.4), with exception of the short-term demand forecasting tool, which is part of the report (D3.5).

Replicability of the digital solutions in other cities/regions is ensured by different actions and results that T3.8 pursued while interacting with the rest of the project. The developed BWS FIWARE approach with its interoperability guidelines (implementation guidelines, FIWARE and interoperability maturity levels) developed in T3.1 helped developers to conceive and realize tools that are easily integrated with third party systems using open and standard APIs, thus boosting replicability. As described above, WP3 will have delivered 7 FIWARE compatible solutions by the end of the project. Synergies with other WPs, i.e. WP2, WP1, WP7 also supports replicability of solutions. This was achieved by a) intensifying discussions and exchange of experience among technology/tool developers in joint WP/WP3 meetings, b) organising the training activities (at least 3 different training activities have taken place so far with the rest being planned during the last year of the project, c) distributing materials and recordings (foreseen under WP1) which were communicated inside and outside of the project through peer networks and WP7 dissemination channels and, finally, d) documenting the lessons learned that have been extracted so far from the application of the tools to the LLs in the final version of both toolkits. The finding from the LLs are communicated through the public toolkits' deliverables (D3.2 – D3.5) but also via the WEM under the case study sections and the related factsheets. This is achieved by extracting information from the current report and using it for populating the WEM. Moreover, a new Milestone (MS32) will be added in M45 which foresees that final key results and lessons learned from the LLs are available in the WEM.

As noted in the executive summary section, WEM is a versatile platform for networking, business development, discovering and sharing knowledge, and exhibiting achievement in the areas of Water, Energy, and Materials. It was originally created as part of the NextGen project and evolved through the BWS and ULTIMATE projects into the WEM, currently curated by Water Europe. Detailed information regarding this product can be found in D7.1

“B-WaterSmart Knowledge portal 'live' with initial upgrades”, where it is documented whereas the link to access the web application is the following:

<https://mp.watereurope.eu/>

1 Introduction

This report, along with D3.5, constitutes the final release of deliverables which document the work done within the tasks T3.2 – T3.7 under which the developments, deployment and demonstration of a series of water-smart applications are foreseen in the six Living Labs (LLs), according to the project Grant Agreement (GA). Task 3.8, building on the aforementioned work attempts to conceptually assemble the different solutions developed and eventually demonstrated in T3.2 to T3.7 into two coherent toolkits that provide added value with respect to the water related challenges of the case studies, serving at the same time as an umbrella to orchestrate and align the LLs around the deployment of tools. Under the lead of T3.8, tool owners in collaboration with the problem owners initially contributed to MS20 “Final input received from T3.2-T3.7 for D3.4 and D3.5” by delivering 6 individual input reports at M34 (end of June), one for each task, which served as the starting point for the development of the final release of both toolkits. The same approach was followed at an earlier stage of the project when draft input reports were received for MS17 (M23) and used to deliver the early release of the toolkits (D3.2/D3.3) in M25. At that point, the focus was on the documentation of the early developments of tools, whereas MS20 and the final release of toolkits aim at providing details on the latest developments of tools and their applications to the 6 LLs.

For the development of D3.2/D3.3/D3.4/D3.5, the leading teams, namely ENG, ICCS and KWR worked in parallel and in close cooperation, in order to ensure that information and results are aligned and presented in a consistent way. The ultimate purpose of T3.8 is to highlight the complementarity of both toolkits and propose synergistic ways in which the tools developed could be used to provide a holistic picture of water-smartness at the water cycle scale. With that as a goal, the D3.4 report is structured as follows.

Chapter 2 and chapter 3 set the base around the water challenges and limitations, encountered in water management and Circular Economy (CE) and are the same for both toolkits reports (D3.4/D3.5). Similarly, the section that follows (Chapter 4), is repeated in both reports, and explains how both toolkits complement each other, contribute to a more holistic assessment, and support the increase of water-smartness. It needs to be highlighted that necessary adjustments were made in order to ensure that each toolkit report is autonomous, but at the same time that the two reports complement each other and assist readers in navigating them through the available contents. Chapter 5 of this report, which practically forms one of the main bodies of this deliverable, documents in a consistent way the features of the 10 tools that form the water cycle modelling and assessment solutions toolkit. Tool descriptions have been originally prepared for the purpose of MS20 (as foreseen in GA) by the tool owners and problem owners in T3.2-T3.7 and were revised to accommodate the needs of D3.4/D3.5 (i.e., final release of toolkits). Chapters 6 to 9 which complement tools' description in Chapter 5 have been allocated to the Venice, Lisbon, Alicante and Bodø LL respectively and document the actual application and use of tools in the different case studies. Given that the Lisbon case tools are distributed across both toolkits, the content for

the Lisbon LL is replicated in the D3.4 and D3.5 reports. This is done to ensure continuity and to clearly illustrate the advantages derived from the combined use of these tools. With regard to the LL sections (Chapters 6-9), those set the basis of the LL work by briefly describing the case studies, the key water-smartness challenges and ambitions and listing the selected tools and technologies applied in their pilots. The integrative use of tools is also included in such sections (and that is the reason for including contents in both reports for the case of Lisbon), while making any necessary connection with the WP2 technologies (when relevant). The sections that follow provide details on the pre-processing stage and input data, the set-up process, the results produced, and the early findings and lessons learned. The concluding sub-section in chapters 6 to 9 include a summary table where concise information is provided at LL level from the application of the different solutions while making references to WP2 technologies, when relevant. The information of D3.4/D3.5 is used for the creation of the early factsheets of the LLs in the WEM which is suggested to be updated with additional results and lessons learned at a later step of the project (M45) via online forms (available in the WEM).

Chapter 10 building on the autonomous LLs work, concentrates and highlights conclusions at the toolkit level while summarising key information for the 10 tools that form the monitoring, negotiation, and decision support solutions toolkit.

Regarding the appendix of this report, Annex A (Section 13) explains the Technology Readiness Level (TRL), as considered in the current deliverable, and used in Chapter 5 for defining TRL of each tool, whereas Annex B (Section 14) presents the template tables that were used to collect structured information for the tools and their applications to the case studies. As part of the synergies across work packages, the information gathered in tabular format regarding tools (as part of MS17 and the early release of toolkits D3.2/D3.3) was used to populate the Water Europe Marketplace of T7.1 with tools' information. After D3.4/D3.5 submission, the same approach will be followed, and the content and summary tables of the LLs will be used to formulate the first version of case study factsheet. Finally, Annex C (Section 15) provides a summary table of the different tools described in deliverables D3.4/D3.5. This is done for facilitating the readers to easily associate tool numbers to the appropriate name and basic information.

2 Water challenges and limitations

Engineers, practitioners, decision makers and different types of stakeholders related to water systems face a diverse set of conditions and challenges. Three of the global water challenges that are related to water security, as highlighted by UNESCO (Makarigakis and Jimenez-Cisneros, 2019) are a) water availability, b) water quality and c) water related hazards. As stated in the same source, pressures on water availability can be attributed to population and economic growth, agriculture, water scarcity and/or climate variability and change.

Overpopulation as well as improvements in living standards create constantly increasing water needs. These needs put pressure on available water resources, resulting in imbalance between water supply and demand and leading to water shortage conditions in cities (Foti et al., 2012; Brown et al., 2019). Urbanization (i.e., the tendency of the population to be concentrated into urban areas) leads to the transformation of once natural landscapes to urban lands and as a result the available freshwater resources are being limited (Okello et al., 2015). According to Thomas and Durham (2003), population growth particularly limits the amount of water available per person, because an increase in per capita water consumption driven by development will intensify water demand, straining the local water supply. To meet the increasing water demands, many cities extensively use groundwater as a supplement to the available surface water. Therefore, additional pressure is caused due to groundwater overexploitation and quality deterioration. As the supply of water must be assured for all and meet the basic needs despite (any) regional imbalances in water resources availability, water supply management is necessary in order to distribute it among different categories of users (Arsiso et al., 2017). Indicatively, Figure 1 depicts the relationship between global population and water withdrawal from 1950 to 2010.

Figure 1: Global Population and Water Withdrawal 1900–2010 (Zisopoulou and Panagoulia, 2021)

Water resources are also vulnerable as they are exposed to climate change (Ellen and Jay, 2008; Raskin et al, 1992; Rochdane et al, 2012). Recent research shows that climate change causes the increase in temperature, variability, and changes in precipitation patterns (Rochdane et al, 2012). Changes in the frequency and intensity of precipitation may have a significant impact on stream flow and the volume of water stored in reservoirs. As a result, increased occurrence of floods or droughts take place and affect the quality and quantity of water resources at local and regional level (Arsiso et al, 2017). The projected impacts of climate change on freshwater flows are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Projected impacts of climate change on freshwater flows (IPCC, 2007)

Changes in water resources have significant socio-economic impacts. Low water supply and droughts affect many sectors, such as agriculture, forestry, energy and drinking water provision. Irrigated agriculture, hydropower generation, use of cooling water and other activities related to water use are susceptible to changed flow regimes and reduced annual water availability (EEA, 2007).

The challenges referred to above are exacerbated by the mismanagement of available water resources. Groundwater is too significant to not be properly managed in the face of a changing climate and land use. Policy makers, environmental managers, and urban planners, who are concerned with the future availability of water supplies and the sustainability of water use, need to incorporate changes in groundwater management into broader environmental change scenarios (Okello et al., 2015). They need to find sustainable solutions for moderating the impact of climate change and urban development and focus on alternative water sources to face the existing and future pressures (Eriyagama et al., 2010; Kirsten and Mark, 2011).

Figure 3 describes the major water related pressures in a graphic form and arranges them under the three global water challenges highlighted by UNESCO (Makarigakis and Jimenez-Cisneros, 2019). Population and economic growth, agriculture, water scarcity, regional imbalance in water availability and climate change put pressure on water resources availability. Water quality, on the other hand, can be attributed to microbial and toxic pollution,

sedimentation, salinization and eutrophication, among others. Lastly, droughts and floods are the most known water related hazards. It is highlighted that this is not an extensive list of water related pressures and elaboration on each one of them falls outside the scope of this deliverable.

Figure 3: Water challenges and pressures

The above water related challenges place pressure on natural resources, which make the need of shifting from the traditional linear model (take-use-dispose) to a circular economy of vital importance (Govindan and Hasanagic, 2018). The principles of CE are founded on the fact that “today’s waste becomes tomorrow’s resources that yield economic, social and environmental benefits” (Mandy Mbavarira and Grimm, 2021). The fact that societies gain benefits from something considered waste, the reduction in energy consumption, the large number of alternative technologies, the constant availability of wastewater, the decrease in pressure on natural resources and the shift towards greener technologies and processes are some of the strengths and opportunities of circular economy in the wastewater sector highlighted by Guerra-Rodriguez et al. (2020).

Nevertheless, there are barriers in applying technologies as part of a circular economy. According to Govindan and Hasanagic (2018), such barriers are related to the a) high upfront costs, which are prohibitive for investors and companies who value profits more than environmental impacts, b) the lack of governmental laws and policies which could support

the shift towards a circular economy, c) the need to solve technological challenges in the products development in order to enable products to be designed with environmentally friendly technology, and d) the people's low awareness of the principles of circular economy. Little experience of circular economy in large-scale implementations and general distrust towards the use of reclaimed water are also considered as barriers in the implementation of circular economy (Guerra-Rodríguez et al., 2020). Mandy Mbavarira and Grimm (2021) support the view (based on a review of literature and input from expert interviews) that some of the key barriers of CE opportunities in the water industry are outdated legislation, health and safety risks (which hamper social acceptance), fluctuating fertilizer quality that cannot always be guaranteed with varying concentrations in waste water which in turn hampers market acceptance. Social acceptance and strong psychological effect in society against direct waste recycling also delay the adoption of CE solutions. Other barriers highlighted by the same authors are the expensive technologies e.g. on monitoring infrastructure and water attributes and the requirement of a high-level of IT readiness and capability for handling big data which increases water organisations overheads. The prioritization of investments which often are in favor of centralised infrastructure rather than complete decentralised systems and the fact that CE remains a complex concept and less something that can be practically adopted cause additional delays in the transition from linear to circular systems. The same authors conclude that digitalization supports CE and can help societies optimise the circularity gains (Mandy Mbavarira and Grimm, 2021). Towards the same direction, Lee et al.(2014) argue that in order to cope with water related challenges, access to water-related data and information is fundamental in order to build sophisticated strategies for water management.

By considering these limitations in CE and in water infrastructure, smart water solutions and tools seem to lead the way towards new water management approaches that will help to increase the efficiency of all elements in the water network (Lee et al., 2015) while supporting the adoption of circular economy technologies. Benefits that come along with this shift towards circularity, while utilizing digitalisation, include reduction of energy, unnecessary water loses and resources exploitation, better monitoring and reporting in quality, quantity and reuse of water, better preparation for water hazards, significant support in decision making and rise of stakeholders' and citizens engagement and awareness towards more sustainable behaviours which value and embrace circular economy opportunities (Mandy Mbavarira and Grimm, 2021).

3 The urban water cycle and the cycle of technology implementation

The major components and pathways of the urban water cycle (UWC) are highly affected by urbanisation and human interventions (Figure 4). Human interventions mostly originate from the need to provide water services to the urban population, including water supply, stormwater drainage and wastewater collection and management/disposal (Marsalek et al., 2014). The same applies to rural areas too. The three major water services have been highlighted in blue, yellow and green respectively in the below graph (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Urban water cycle – main components and pathways (source: (Marsalek et al., 2014))

The engineered methods alter the hydrologic cycle and form the urban water cycle, which is primarily consisted of eight main steps as depicted in Figure 5 i.e., source, treatment, distribution, storage, use, collection, treatment and discharge, within which the water “travels” from source and eventually is discharged back to the environment. Within those steps, the water practitioners need to be equipped with state-of-the-art technologies and tools to design systems in a robust way to meet water related challenges.

Figure 5: The main steps of the urban water cycle (graph created for the purpose of this deliverable)

As explained by Makropoulos et al. (2008), “the traditional approach is to consider the infrastructure that delivers potable water separately from the infrastructure that disposes of wastewater and separately to the provision of drainage for stormwater. There is growing need to re-evaluate this approach in order to seek ways to, *inter alia*, minimise the environmental impact of urban areas on supply sources and receiving waters.” Based on that traditional concept, conventional water management systems are built in a linear model which includes the three main steps of a) producing (potable) water, b) using it and c) disposing, as quickly as possible (Bouziotas et al., 2020). On the contrary, circular water systems and models (Figure 6), prioritise *reduction* of wastewater, *removal* of pollutants from water and waste water, *reuse* of waste water, *recycling* of water, *recovery* of resources as nutrients and energy and *rethinking* of water and wastewater to save and conserve water and to optimise water use, in all the relevant sectors (Morseletto et al., 2022; Smol et al., 2020). This new, circular path of water and wastewater, which comes to substitute the conventional linear management model (Bouziotas et al., 2019a), is an integral part of a CE, “where the value of products, materials and resources is maintained in the economy for as long as possible, and the generation of waste is minimised” (EU Commission, 2015). But as any other water/wastewater management model, it needs systemic innovation through a combination of new hardware technology, concepts and software solutions for the whole cycle of technology implementation: from optimal planning, what-if scenarios modelling, negotiations and decision making to monitoring, control and long-term performance assessment (Figure 7).

Figure 6: Circular economy model for water and wastewater management

While working under uncertainty and trying to deliver sustainable, robust and adaptive systems, robust decision-making and dynamic adaptive policy pathway approaches (Haasnoot et al., 2013; Walker et al., 2013) have been suggested by some researchers in the literature, in order to achieve economic, environmental and societal objectives. Primary steps considered in such approaches are: understand the current situation and conduct problem analysis (for future conditions too), investigate and evaluate actions to reach desired goals, develop contingency plans, implement corrective actions and monitor the actions/plans implemented (Haasnoot et al., 2013).

In order to work towards delivering sustainable, robust and adaptive systems, new advanced software solutions coupled with CE technologies and concepts across a diverse set of conditions and under water challenges need to be exploited by the different stakeholders and decision makers within all steps of the technology implementation route (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Steps in technology implementation

4 The B-Water Smart ICT solutions toolkits

Challenges related to water described in chapters 2 and 3 call for continuous and substantial innovations to **avoid wasting** such precious resource, due to **inefficient management of its lifecycle**. It is thus fundamental to improve **decision making** and **action planning** by leveraging on the **large amount of data available**, despite the fact that such data is actually **scattered, non-standardized** and generally of **low quality**.

The water sector is undergoing a gradual **digital transformation** that is affecting the entire water lifecycle, from water sourcing and storage, to distribution, use, treatment and reuse. The **level of maturity** that the digitalization process has reached throughout the water lifecycle varies from case to case, from simply incorporating sensors into operational procedures to capture relevant data, visualize trends and raise alerts about anomalous trends or events, to sophisticated and data-science-based approaches, data analysis that leverage state-of-the-art Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques, producing predictions/simulations, and supporting automated and optimized operations on the field.

When thinking about digital maturity, it is important to highlight that data-based tools alone can only add a layer of technology that allows for better data collection and increased monitoring. It is their combined and structured use that enables a **process of transformation** toward the vision of water smartness, where more resilient and sustainable water services are deployed and information is turned from Information Technology (IT) applications into **data-driven decisions** that help optimize resources (through circularity), minimize climate impacts, and enhance health and safety.

The aim of the monitoring, negotiation and decision support solutions toolkit (in combination with the water cycle modelling and assessment solutions toolkit) is to provide a set of complementary tools for enabling and enhancing efficiency for the fundamental steps that have to be followed by subjects that aim to improve their water smartness.

The complementarity of the tools is defined using a **high-level process**, which is a reference procedural framework for using the toolkits (see Figure 8). The following description defines the reference process that somebody may follow for improving water smartness through the use of digital tools. As a general note, the process is represented as a cycle because water smartness is not a goal (with a finish line), but a trend that has to be improved iteratively.

Figure 8: High-level process for iteratively improving water smartness through digital tools

The process is composed of two main loops. The main loop includes the fundamental steps that have to be followed to improve water smartness:

- **Context awareness:** the first, strategic step for planning any kind of change process is understanding the state of the system using data-based evidence. Data and information have to be shared among relevant stakeholders as much as possible in order to highlight threats and opportunities, good practices and critical situations. This is the step where the current “as-is” situation is depicted in order to allow decision makers to share a common view of the system and be able to recognize the gaps and the priorities of actions.
- **Decision making:** this step builds on the information collected in the previous one for delivering actual strategic decisions on what to do for improving water smartness. This includes decisions on new investments in technologies or infrastructures, new regulations for fostering CE and RR, risk-aware alternative comparison, etc.
- **Management/monitoring:** implemented actions have to be managed at operational level and their impacts have to be monitored on a regular basis to ensure that decisions are leading to the expected results in terms of water smartness.
- **Certification:** in some cases, the achievements of the change process can be certified with respect to some reference standard. This step is optional but represents a key added value for those subjects that have a structured and well-defined

management plan for their water smartness, ensuring great visibility and credibility of their efforts.

The second loop is focused on advanced analytics for providing detailed evidence in support of the decision-making step. This is a separate loop (nested in the main one) because it may require several iterations, refinements and data exploitations to achieve the necessary results in terms of predictions, simulations, demand/supply match-making and other analysis.

The main loop is supported by the **monitoring, negotiation and decision support solutions toolkit**, whereas the specialized loop for advanced analysis is supported by the **water cycle modelling and assessment solutions toolkit**.

Aspects such as change management or other horizontal matters not strictly related to water smartness are not considered in the reference process.

Table 3 below maps the roles of different tools in both toolkits within the steps of the process and provides a brief description of their supporting functionalities

Table 3: The impact of tools from both toolkits on the steps for improving water smartness

Step	Tool	Description (how the tool supports this step)
Context awareness	Water reuse strategic platform (#16), enabled by Digital Enabler (#32)	Both platforms can be used for collecting and making available to the relevant stakeholders the heterogeneous information that is scattered across the territory about treated water and sludge and about their potential reuse. This includes any data available in a structured or unstructured format such as:
	Sludge management platform (#19), enabled by Digital Enabler (#32)	quality and quantity of the product (sludge or water), producers, treatment plants and destinations; characteristics of the territory related to climate, urbanization, industrial plants, cultivated lands, state of soil, regulations at different levels, with information about barriers and drivers. Contextual information is presented through integrated visualizations in a coherent way in order to enable a more effective and data-driven decision process, allowing users to better understand the state of the territory in terms of issues and opportunities for reusing and valorising the available product.
	UWC observatory (#20)	The Urban Water Cycle Observatory of Lisbon has the aim to systematise, collect and facilitate access to data on the city water cycle. The system provides access to context data through two different channels. i) open data about urban water and wastewater (main water flows, consumption disaggregation, amount of treated wastewater and reused water production) is provided to citizens and city stakeholders through publicly accessible infographics; ii) entities that have in place a remote water metering can access

		visualizations about aggregated consumptions and costs per typology of water use, water consumption evolution and individual consumption analysis, leading to an insightful water management, supported by data analytics and automatic performance reports.
	Environmental dashboard (#30)	The Environmental dashboard aims at presenting aggregated data sources (water meters, demographic data sets) in maps and graphs for providing a picture of water consumption in the different districts of a city.
Advanced analysis	UWOT (#22)	UWOT allows users (water planners, developers and relevant consultants) to compare different water management technologies (including water saving, recycling, treatment and drainage) at different scales. The tool simulates the urban water cycle by modelling individual water uses and technologies and aggregating their combined effects at development scale. UWOT provides a range of technology combinations, which are ranked according to user-based criteria. This allows the user to determine which combination of technologies will be most appropriate or beneficial for their new development.
	Regional demand-supply matching GIS tool (#23)	This is a GIS tool designed for visualizing and processing open-source information on natural water availability and sectorial consumption. Information can be used to identify i) possible consumption hotspots and areas of water shortage, ii) alternative water resources or areas with available water sources and iii) water drain from one region to another region. Based on the analysis, the impacts of alternative water availability scenarios on water demand can be displayed.
	Short-term demand forecasting tool (#28)	The tool is intended to generate water demand forecasts for the next 24 hours. The user can interact with the graphical user interface to train machine learning models and use them to generate and visualize demand forecasts. Furthermore, the user is able to aggregate forecasts for multiple smart meters to achieve the desired spatial resolution.
	QMRA+ for water reuse and agriculture (#26)	Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment (QMRA) is a methodology that can be applied to assess risks of water (re)use and thus support decisions. The QMRA tool enables users to estimate the microbial health risk of using various water sources, including reuse of wastewater. A treatment system can be designed by selecting treatment steps from a wide array of possible treatment technologies, resulting in a product water quality. The application can assess the exposure of humans to this product water and the pathogens it may contain.

	SuTra (#31)	SuTRa calculates the subsurface removal of microbial organisms over a distance and with time using an analytical approach. The aim is to allow for a quick assessment of subsurface removal of microbial organisms after subsurface storage.
	Water-energy-phosphorous balance planning module (#25)	This tool is a matchmaking environment where sources and demand points are combined together. The supply and demand alternative combinations are assessed through a range of user-selected metrics (e.g., volume availability, cost, energy content, carbon footprint, nutrient content) over a targeted period.
	Reclaimed water distribution network water quality model (#24)	This tool provides a simulation model for mapping and quantifying risk in reclaimed water distribution networks.
	Risk Assessment for urban water reuse module (#27)	This tool is a human and environmental risk framework dedicated to water demand planners and decision-makers in urban management, municipal and water utility contexts. The tool assesses supply/demand combinations, based on a range of current risk standards and regulations. It works as a risk-related gatekeeper that must be cleared for any supply/demand combination to be considered for assessment in tool #17.
Decision making	Environment for decision support and alternative course selection (#17)	This tool supports water demand planners and decision-makers in urban management to select the best water source combinations to satisfy specific non-potable uses and to prioritize planning options in the governance of water sources and water uses in an urban setting. The tool provides the means to compare supply/demand matchmaking alternatives produced by tool #25 and potentially qualified by tools #24 and #27.
	Re-Actor (#18)	The RE-ACTOR tool aims at supporting water utilities, planners, and decision makers in the evaluation of new investments and actions related to water reuse and water treatment. The tool allows to simulate alternative scenarios in a territory to explore potential impacts related different actuations, such as new processes in a WWTP, installation of renewable technologies or new reclaimed water distribution infrastructure to supply new users with reclaimed water.
Management/monitoring	Stormwater reuse management system (#21)	The stormwater reuse management system will allow the combination of operational management of a stormwater tank and a connected subirrigation system for groundwater recharge and direct irrigation with the overall objective of reducing water scarcity in spaces or close to urbanised areas. The system includes innovative control concepts to actively manage existing rainwater infrastructures to unlock new applications for

		otherwise lost rainwater (e.g. agriculture, watering local parks and lawns, industry).
	Nessie system (#29)	The Nessie platform is an information system, able to acquire, process and store, and in general to manage, high-resolution data from IoT agents, such as sensors and smart meters, coupled with analytics and visualisation capabilities to present the information to the end-users. Beyond simple monitoring, possible advanced capabilities for the management of water consumption that could be built upon the tool are: i) the detection of leakages and bursts, ii) the comparison with past consumption data of the household, iii) the comparison with the water consumption of other households with similar socio-demographic characteristics, iv) the analysis of total consumption per appliance, v) the forecast of future consumptions and bills.
Certification	Climate-readiness certification tool (#33)	The climate-readiness certification tool is conceived to support householders, urban planners, the building industry, municipalities, urban planners and Climate Ready Certificates auditors in calculating and emitting the Climate-Ready Certificate (CRC), merging in one certificate the water efficiency, the water-energy nexus performance and the climate adaptation evaluation of households, buildings and neighbourhoods.

The monitoring, negotiation and decision support solutions toolkit, which is documented in the current report is comprised of ten tools which are listed in Table 4 below, along with the LL in which they are applied. Detailed information on each tool is provided in the Chapter 5.

Table 4: Tools of the monitoring, negotiation and decision support solutions toolkit

#No.	WP3 Tool (leading partners)	Living Lab using the tool
16	Water reuse strategic platform (VERI/ENG)	Venice
17	Environment for decision support and alternative course selection (BASE)	Lisbon
18	Re-Actor (CETaqua)	Alicante
19	Sludge management platform (VERI/ENG)	Venice
20	UWC observatory (Lisboa E-Nova, third party linked to CML)	Lisbon
21	Stormwater reuse management system (AQUAFIN/VITO)	Flanders
29	Nessie System (ICCS/NTUA)	Bodø

30	Environmental Dashboard (Nordkontakt AS)	Bodø
32	Digital Enabler (ENG)	Venice
33	Climate-readiness certification tool (ADENE)	Lisbon

5 The monitoring, negotiation and decision support solutions toolkit

5.1 Water reuse strategic platform (#16) and Sludge management platform (#19)

5.1.1 Tool description and attributes

The design and development of the water reuse strategic platform (#16) and of the sludge management platform (#19) have many steps and architectural components in common. In order not to duplicate descriptions and figures, both the platforms are documented here in a single section, highlighting- the specific features and modules that differentiate them, of each sub-section.

Both the platforms have the overall objective of identifying different valorisation pathways for both resources (water and sludge) based on the most sustainable option (from both environmental and economic perspectives), to support the users in the decision-making process with an objective and standardized evaluation also contextualized on the territory of interest. This entails the necessity of collecting and reporting multiple data from heterogeneous sources, providing cross-references among them, and making available easy-to-understand visualizations that highlight the added value of the combination of such data. More specifically, the aim of the two platforms is briefly described below:

- The overall aim of the **Water reuse strategic platform** is to enable freshwater saving and wastewater reuse (WWR). It will be an evaluation support system for identifying the optimum reuse opportunities of the treated municipal wastewater based on context and territorial data.
- The aim of the **Sludge management platform** is to support the identification of the optimum sewage sludge (from municipal wastewater treatment) valorisation strategy to foster resource reuse/recovery either towards agricultural application or energy production. The platform allows evaluation and ranking of treatment options and valorisations, considering information from different contexts.

The Water reuse strategic platform and the Sludge management platform are web applications hosted in a cloud infrastructure. The target group can access the platforms via web-browser (Chrome fully tested). Users can access:

- for the water reuse strategic platform, a map-based visualization of the regional river network with specific information related to the location and characteristics of wastewater treatment plants WWTPs, of their related discharging points (into the rivers), of agricultural/industrial water inlets (from the rivers) and of water quality measurement stations. Users can also get evaluations of some quantitative/qualitative indicators (see Section 6.2.4)
- for the sludge management platform, a map-based visualization of the regional soil maps with chemical/physical characteristics of the soils, with the location of WWTPs and with the quality level and quantity of the sludge produced; information about

ranked options of treatment Get evaluations of some qualitative/quantitative indicators (see Section 6.2.4).

- for both platforms, a catalogue of European, National and Regional regulations related to sludge and treated wastewater, with dedicated information on main barriers and drivers.

End-users of the platforms include the ones described in the following table.

Table 5: End-users of the platforms

End-user	What will get from the tool	Reasons for using the tool
Producers (i.e. utilities)	Information about: <i>i)</i> the state of the art related to use/destinations opportunities of sludge and water; <i>ii)</i> regulatory framework in terms of general and local leverages and barriers; <i>iii)</i> ranked valorisation alternatives depending on product quality.	The tool supports them in planning with a long-term perspective by exploiting the potential existing synergies that just through this method could easily be identified.
Authorities (Regions, Municipalities, environmental authorities)	Scientific, standardized, and reliable information about variables, characteristics, quality and reuse opportunities of resources especially in terms of actual risks connected. Then they could get support for individuating fair regulation by avoiding an excessively precautionary approach.	They get evidence for defining/revising regulations and plans towards fostering the best practices in the water sector.
End-users (such as sectoral associations e.g. for agriculture; industries/industrialists; urban areas managers)	Vision of opportunities, quality, risks and level of support/facilitation for reuse directions and addresses.	They have an integrated vision of the state of the art of reuse opportunities/resources valorisation pathways and shortcuts for reuse conveniences.
Technologies providers (i.e. technology producers and distributors)	An overall mapping of both treatment necessities from the emerged reuse opportunities and a point of suggestion for sharing with other technology providers.	To have a high territorial point of view of the distribution of necessities and individuate potential synergies and market shortcuts.

Both the **Water reuse strategic platform** and the **Sludge management platform** have a primary territorial scale which is regional. The potential water reuse opportunities that will be identified from the first one will be usually very near to the production plant or enabled by rivers and canals that transport treated water to the agricultural and industrial picking points,

but the whole regional perimeter will be covered. For sludge, there are additional reasons for this choice:

- From a regulatory point of view, there is the need for homogeneous rules about sludge management, reuse and valorisations. In Italy, different Regions may use and apply slightly different regulations, with different conditions, barriers and constraints.
- Critical mass of data: collecting and using data about plants, sludge quality/quantity, and soils related to a territory that is too small (urban/metropolitan), may fail to match necessities and opportunities emerging from different territories. This is why it is recommended to extend as much as possible the area and the scale at which the solution is implemented.

Table 6: Table for the Water reuse strategic platform attributes and description

Tool's attribute	Description
Type of product	A software supporting the Circular Economy
Name	Water reuse strategic platform
Description	<p>The overall aim of the Water reuse strategic platform is to enable freshwater saving and wastewater reuse (WWR). It is an evaluation support system for identifying the optimum reuse of the treated municipal wastewater based on context and territorial data.</p> <p>The Water Reuse Strategic Platform is a web application hosted in a cloud infrastructure. The target group can access the platform via web-browser. Users can access:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a map-based visualization of the Regional river network with specific information related to the location and characteristics of WWTPs, of their related discharging points (into the rivers), of agricultural/industrial water inlets (from the rivers) and of water quality measurement stations. Get evaluations of some quantitative/qualitative indicators. • a catalogue of European, National and Regional regulations related to sludge and treated wastewater, with dedicated information on main barriers and drivers.
Abbreviation	Not applicable
URL	https://portal-bws.opsi.lecce.it/
Costs	Not yet defined
Target audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Producers (i.e. utilities): they will get information about the state of the art related to use/destinations of treated wastewater, about regulatory variables, and for getting valorisation alternatives. The tool will help them for their planning at short/medium/long term • Authorities (Regions, Municipalities, environmental authorities): they will get affordable information about variables/characteristics of treated water resources and the territorial context, useful for defining regulations and plans. • Final destinations (treatment plants or final destinations such as agricultural

	<p>field, industries and urban areas): they will get information for depicting a mapping of availability of alternative resources.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technologies providers (producers of treatment plants or monitoring systems): they will get an overall mapping of treatment necessities from the market.
Actors, roles and interactions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Users of the platform (producers, authorities, end-users/destinations, technology providers) will have access to data visualization interfaces for getting context information (context awareness). • Admin: the administrator of the platform will set the overall variables and data resources to be used by the system
Unique selling points /Added Value/Innovation	<p>Situational awareness is a key success factor for enabling decision-making processes, but the heterogeneity and dispersion of the relevant data leads to partial knowledge and difficulty in sharing key information among the actors of the territorial context. The water reuse strategic platform acts as a one-stop-shop where users can easily access data and information in order to highlight issues and opportunities that otherwise would be difficult to identify.</p>
TRL	<p>TRL level of tool #16 is strongly linked to the availability of some data that is still in the collection/pre-processing stage. As soon as data is available, the system prototype and its functionalities will be demonstrated properly, with actual benefits for the territorial context. TRL 7 will be reached by the end of 2023.</p>
Technical requirements	<p>The water reuse strategic platform is a web application that can be accessed and used on web browser. It can be delivered in an “As a Service” mode. In addition, the software will be provided as a docker container in order to make the installation process as easy as possible.</p>
Environment	<p>Web browser</p>
Version	<p>0.1</p>
Initial release	<p>2023</p>
License type	<p>Open Source</p>
Programming language/technologies used	<p>Pre-processing: PostGIS, QGIS</p> <p>DBMSs: Postgres;</p> <p>Data Visualization: Dashram, Leaflet;</p> <p>Containerization: Docker;</p> <p>Backend: React JS</p>
Open interface	<p>The platform has an NGSI-LD open interface provided by the Orion Context Broker.</p>
Graphical User Interface / Headless software	<p>The platform is a web-based application and has a GUI accessible through web browser.</p>
Supported spatial scales	<p>The spatial scale of the water reuse strategic platform is at regional level.</p>

Supported temporal scales	Not applicable
Water Use Types	Urban, industrial, rural and agriculture
Compatibility with FIWARE	The water reuse strategic platform is compatible with FIWARE
Organisations	The water reuse strategic platform is owned by Veritas and by Engineering Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A.
Contact details	Patrizia Ragazzo, p.ragazzo@gruppo-veritas.it Davide Storelli, davide.storelli@eng.it
Data Manager	Davide Storelli, davide.storelli@eng.it
Technologies	Wastewater treatment technologies for water reuse
Tags	Wastewater, reuse, treatment, quality, valorization
Images	
Caption/Source	Map of the watercourses impacted by a specific WWTP effluents
Publications	Not applicable

Table 7: Table for the Sludge management platform attributes and description

Tool's attribute	Description
Type of product	A software supporting the Circular Economy
Name	Sludge management platform
Description	The aim of the Sludge management platform is to support the identification of the optimum sewer sludge valorisation strategy in order to foster energy and resource reuse/recovery. The platform allows evaluation and ranking of treatment options and

	<p>valorizations, considering information from the different contexts.</p> <p>The Water Reuse Strategic Platform and the Sludge Management Platform are web applications hosted in a cloud infrastructure. The target group can access the platforms via web-browser. Users can access:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a map-based visualization of the Regional soil maps with chemical/physical characteristics of the soils, with the location of WWTPs and with the quality level and quantity of the sludge produced. Get evaluations of some qualitative/quantitative indicators. Get ranked options of treatment. • a catalogue of European, National and Regional regulations related to sludge and treated wastewater, with dedicated information on main barriers and drivers. •
Abbreviation	Not applicable
URL	https://portal-bws.opsi.lecce.it/
Costs	Not yet defined
Target audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Producers (i.e. utilities): they will get information about the state of the art related to use/destinations of sludge, about regulatory variables, and for getting ranked valorisation alternatives depending on resource quality. The tool will help them for their planning at short/medium/long term • Authorities (Regions, Municipalities, environmental authorities): they will get affordable information about variables/characteristics of sludge resources and the territorial context, useful for defining regulations and plans. • Final destinations (treatment plants or final destinations such as agricultural field, industries and urban areas): they will get information for depicting a mapping of availability of alternative resources. • Technologies providers (producers of treatment plants or monitoring systems): they will get an overall mapping of treatment necessities from the market.
Actors, roles and interactions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Users of the platform (producers, authorities, end-users/destinations, technology providers) will have access to data visualization interfaces for getting context information (context awareness). • Admin: the administrator of the platform will set the overall variables and data resources to be used by the system.
Unique selling points /Added Value/Innovation	Situational awareness is a key success factor for enabling decision-making processes, but the heterogeneity and dispersion of the relevant data leads to partial knowledge and difficulty in sharing key information among the actors of the territorial context. The sludge management platform act as a one-stop-shop where users can easily access data and information in order to highlight issues and opportunities that otherwise would be difficult to identify.
TRL	TRL level of tool #19 is strongly linked to the availability of some data that is still in the collection/pre-processing stage. As soon as data is available, the system prototype and its functionalities will be demonstrated properly, with actual benefits for the territorial context. TRL 7 will be reached by the end of 2023.
Technical requirements	The sludge management platform is a web application that can be accessed and used on web browser. It can be delivered in an “As a Service” mode. In addition, the software will be provided as a docker container in order to make the installation process as easy as possible.

Environment	Web browser
Version	0.1
Initial release	2023
License type	Open Source
Programming language/technologies used	Pre-processing: PostGIS, QGIS; DBMSs: Postgres; Data Visualization: Dashram, Leaflet; Containerization: Docker; Backend: React JS
Open interface	The platform has an NGSI-LD open interface provided by the Orion Context Broker.
Graphical User Interface / Headless software	The platform is a web-based application and has a GUI accessible through web browser.
Supported spatial scales	The spatial scale of the sludge management platform is at Regional level.
Supported temporal scales	Not applicable
Water Use Types	agriculture
Compatibility with FIWARE	The sludge management platform is compatible with FIWARE
Organisations	The sludge management platform is owned by Veritas and by Engineering Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A.
Contact details	Patrizia Ragazzo, p.ragazzo@gruppoveritas.it Davide Storelli, davide.storelli@eng.it
Data Manager	Davide Storelli, davide.storelli@eng.it
Technologies	Nutrients/Material recovery technologies Energy recovery technologies
Tags	Sludge, reuse, quality, treatment, valorization

<p>Images</p>	
<p>Caption/Source</p>	<p>Map of soil characteristics and WWTPs, with specific focus on the soil characteristics is a specific point selected by the user</p>
<p>Publications</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>

5.1.2 Pre-existing background

Both the Water reuse strategic platform and the Sludge management platform were developed from scratch, after defining their functional requirements in an iterative way and by leveraging on two fundamental background resources:

- Domain expertise carried by Veritas allows the team to focus on the main priorities and develop data-driven functionalities that really respond to necessities of the end-users.
- Technical skills and resources are provided by Engineering. In particular the two platforms leverage some components of the Digital Enabler, ENG's Ecosystem Platform. Such components are used to enable faster data management procedures (collection, preparation, harmonization) and easier data visualization through charts and dashboards.

5.1.3 Developments and advancements within the project

Since both the Water reuse strategic platform and the Sludge management platform have been developed as completely new tools, with the necessity of exploring and consolidating the information context and the required functionalities through time, the adopted design and development approach is based on an Agile methodology, with iterative cycles of design, development and test (see Figure 9). The cycle is applied for each main architectural layer of the platform, that can be briefly simplified as Database (for storing and managing the data), Computational and evaluation logic (for providing key data elaboration) and User interfaces (for providing proper interaction flows and visualizations to the final user).

In parallel to the main design, development and test cycle, an accurate and extensive effort is carried on to identify, collect, integrate and prepare the data necessary to feed the platform. This effort is conducted mainly through interactions with stakeholders from the Venice

Community of Practice (CoP). Data included in such process are the following (collected in different formats, including excel, raster, text files and shapefile):

- Production plants with geolocation information;
- Industrial/urban pressure to each plant;
- Type of treatment chain of each plant;
- Quality and quantity of produced effluent and sludge;
- Characterization of soils with respect to their capacity to accept sludge (pH, levels of nitrogen, carbon, ...);
- Hydrographic network with withdrawal points and possible relations with production points;
- Relevant regulations and their quantitative data (limits and restrictions; drivers and barriers).

Figure 9 High-level design and development approach

The development process is divided in such two parallel threads to maximize reusability of results. Indeed, the objective is to ensure that the features developed in terms of user interfaces, computational/evaluation logic and database structure are as much as possible independent from the actual territorial context where the platform is applied, while the data collection and integration process is strictly related to local data sources and must be specifically implemented for harmonizing and preparing the data for its subsequent usage in the platform.

Design of the tool

Different cycles have been executed, involving the three layers mentioned above: user interface, computation and evaluation logic, data model.

As to the user interfaces, the design process led to the definition of several mock-ups. In particular, as to dashboards, considering the data expected to be ingested and/or to be made available to the platform, different charts and map-based visualizations were iteratively designed and discussed in order to come up with a comprehensive strategic set of dashboards, some of which are briefly described in the following table.

Some dashboard mock-ups

Production of sludge: this dashboard aims at providing information about production of sludge on the reference territory. The dashboard includes the following visualizations:

- Map showing the location of plants (with individual information available as tooltip by clicking on the specific element on the map)
- Pie chart showing the percentage of industrial/civil pressure on the plants.
- Heatmap showing, for each production plant, class of quality of each evaluation parameter
- Quality level of the sludge produced per type of plant (complex, medium, simple)

The following figure is the mock-up of the dashboard

Production of treated water:

- Map showing rivers and production plants
- Quantity of treated water produced through year
- Radar chart for visualizing the mean seasonal treated water that is drained and drawn with respect to a specific river.

The following figure is the mock-up of the dashboard

Mock-ups like the ones described above have undergone an iterative process of discussion and refinement, until actual implementations have been realized, also considering the data actually available, as described in Section 6.2.4.

Beyond mock-ups for data visualization, design work was also focussed on functionalities to insert data through dedicated Graphical User Interfaces. For example, the management approach of regulations and of their descriptions was initially designed through MS Excel and MS Word files, that were then used as models to implement the actual prototype.

1	livello	fonte normativa	titolo	note
2	UE	Dir 91/271	trattamento delle acque reflue urbane	recepita nel Dlgs 152/06
3		Reg 2020/741	recante prescrizioni minime per il riutilizzo dell'acqua a scopi irrigui	entrerà in vigore dal 26/6/23
4		Comunicazione Commissione Europea 2022/C 298/01	Orientamenti a sostegno dell'applicazione del regolamento (UE) 2020/741	
5		Documenti UE sull'EC, a partire dalla COM(2015) 614 final	recante prescrizioni minime per il riutilizzo dell'acqua	
6				
7	Italia	Dlgs 152/06 art 99	TU ambiente - parte III	Art. 99 - riutilizzo dell'acqua
8				1. Il Ministro dell'ambiente ...detta le norme tecniche per il riutilizzo delle acque reflue. 2. Le regioni...e sentita l'Autorità di vigilanza sulle risorse idriche e sui rifiuti, adottano norme e misure volte a favorire il riciclo dell'acqua e il riutilizzo delle acque reflue depurate
9		DM 30/7/99	Limiti agli scarichi industriali e civili che recapitano nella laguna di Venezia e nei corpi idrici del suo bacino scolante	
10		DM 185/03	norme tecniche per il riutilizzo delle acque reflue	v tab 3.26 pag 181 indirizzi di Piano
11		Delibera ARERA 27 dicembre 2019 586/2019/R/Idr (MTI-3)	Approva il Metodo Tariffario del servizio idrico integrato per il terzo periodo regolatorio (MTI-3), definendo le regole per il computo dei costi ammessi al riconoscimento tariffario.	
12				
13	Veneto	DCR 107/09	PTA (in particolare gli Indirizzi di Piano - Allegato 2)	
14				
15	concessioni irrigue			
16	Italia	RD 1775/33	Testo unico delle disposizioni di legge sulle acque e impianti elettrici	l'uso è soggetto a concessione la concessione è rilasciata se non ci sono possibilità

Figure 10 Spreadsheet used to design the data model to be used for regulations

RIFERIMENTI UE	
<p>(91/271/CEE) concernente il trattamento delle acque reflue urbane</p>	
<p>Principali contenuti Individua limiti e tipologie dei trattamenti delle acque, dando indicazioni sull'individuazione delle aree sensibili per lo scarico</p>	<p>Qualifica (barriera-iva-altro) Leva: Art.12 comma 1: "Le acque reflue che siano state sottoposte a trattamento devono essere riutilizzate, ogniqualvolta ciò risulti appropriato. Le modalità di smaltimento devono rendere minimo l'impatto negativo sull'ambiente". Il riutilizzo è subordinato a specifiche autorizzazioni (comma 2)</p>
<p>Commenti e ricadute Detta il principio all'art 12; non fornisce indicazioni tecniche.</p>	
<p>Norme correlate Il tema del riuso degli scarichi è diffusamente inserito documenti UE sull'economia circolare, a partire dalla COM(2015) 614 final D.Lgs.152/06 e s.m.l. - recepimento direttiva</p>	
<p>Regolamento CEE/UE 25 maggio 2020, n. 741 Regolamento (UE) 2020/741 del Parlamento europeo e del Consiglio del 25 maggio 2020 recante prescrizioni minime per il riutilizzo dell'acqua</p>	
<p>Principali contenuti Definisce i principi procedurali e tecnici per il riuso delle acque reflue urbane a scopi irrigui in agricoltura.</p>	<p>Qualifica (barriera-iva-altro) Leva:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gli Stati membri devono giustificare la scelta di non riusare le acque trattate - Definiti chiaramente i soggetti della filiera e i riferimenti per il piano di gestione del rischio - Qualsiasi parte responsabile del sistema di riutilizzo dell'acqua, compreso l'utilizzatore finale, può presentare una domanda volta al rilascio di un permesso <p>Barriera:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - La concreta applicabilità del Regolamento è sospesa fino a che l'Italia non avrà individuato almeno l'autorità competente e le procedure per il rilascio del permesso (la valutazione del piano di gestione dei rischi richiede tempo e competenza - art 6 c 5; anche più di un anno)
<p>Commenti e ricadute Dovranno essere definite le regole di ripartizione dei costi e di reperimento delle relative risorse</p>	

<p>(Includi eventuali incentivi). Dovranno essere definiti i limiti applicabili agli scarichi destinati al riuso per i parametri non normati dal regolamento (es, tabella allegata al DM 185/03 o tabella 4 scarichi su suolo, del D.Lgs. 152/06) Il Regolamento si applica dal 26/6/23.</p>	
<p>Norme correlate</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regolamento (CE) n. 852/2004 per la sicurezza alimentare ed altri riferimenti normativi riportati al punto 27 della premessa del Regolamento751/20 - Comunicazione Commissione [2022/C 298/01] - Orientamenti a sostegno dell'applicazione del regolamento (UE) 2020/741 recante prescrizioni minime per il riutilizzo dell'acqua - ISO 16075/2020 - orientamento per la gestione dei rischi nell'utilizzo acque non potabili - ISO 20426/2018 - orientamento per il riuso delle acque reflue trattate 	
NORMATIVA NAZIONALE	
<p>D.Lgs.152/06 art 99 - Riutilizzo dell'acqua</p>	
<p>Principali contenuti Fornisce indicazioni di principio sul riutilizzo dell'acqua</p>	<p>Qualifica (barriera-iva-altro) Art. 99 - riutilizzo dell'acqua 1. Il Ministro dell'ambiente [...] detta le norme tecniche per il riutilizzo delle acque reflue. 2. Le regioni [...] e sentita l'Autorità di vigilanza sulle risorse idriche e sui rifiuti, adottano norme e misure volte a favorire il rischio dell'acqua e il riutilizzo delle acque reflue depurate</p>
<p>Commenti e ricadute Detta il principio all'art 99; non fornisce indicazioni tecniche.</p>	
<p>Norme correlate DM 185/03 - Regolamento recante norme tecniche per il riutilizzo delle acque reflue in attuazione dell'articolo 26, comma 2, del decreto legislativo 11 maggio 1999, n. 152.</p>	
<p>DM 185/03 - Regolamento recante norme tecniche per il riutilizzo delle acque reflue in attuazione dell'articolo 26, comma 2, del decreto legislativo 11 maggio 1999, n. 152.</p>	
<p>Principali contenuti Individua le norme tecniche per il riutilizzo delle acque reflue domestiche, urbane ed industriali attraverso la regolamentazione delle destinazioni d'uso e dei relativi requisiti di qualità</p>	<p>Qualifica (barriera-iva-altro) Leva: Regolamenta qualsiasi riutilizzo di qualsiasi acqua reflua (ad eccezione del riutilizzo diretto da parte del produttore)</p> <p>Barriera:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I costi di affinamento sono a carico del gestore dell'impianto di recupero ma non c'è nessun'indicazione di come il gestore possa coprirli (v anche scheda MIT-3) - Mancano forme di incentivazione al recupero - I limiti di qualità sono complessivamente più restrittivi di

Figure 11 MS Word document used to design the data model to be used for details on regulations

Architecture

Data is collected from heterogeneous data sources and pre-processed to guarantee data quality and harmonization. The data is stored in ad-hoc data repositories, specialized for each type of data (raster images, JSON, csv, time-series, ...). When possible, data is transformed according to NGSI-LD standard and to available Smart Data Models to be managed by the FIWARE Orion Context Broker, a core component of the Digital Enabler. Data is then used for feeding functionalities of the platform and specifically for its components dedicated to data analytic and data visualization (Figure 12).

Figure 12 Overall software architecture of the two platforms

Table 8 provides more details about each architectural component and its main functionalities.

Table 8: Components of the overall architecture of tools #16 and #19

Component	Description
Data connectors	For the heterogenous data to be imported in the platform, the definition and development of ad-hoc software components are required to be able to collect such data from their original source. This could require semi-automatic or fully automatic procedures, depending on the source of data. For example, satellite data provided by a Geoserver endpoint could be automatically queried on a fixed time period in order to get relevant raster images or geoJSON files. In general, automatic procedures can be realized for almost any programmatic interface (API) exposed by a data source (DCAT for Open Data Portals, MQTT for IoT systems, ...). On the other hand, datasets (csv, excel, ...) that are provided via other channels (e.g. email, FTP, ...) must follow a semi-automatic procedure that may include a steps where a human operator uploads the dataset and performs some manual operations.
Data preparation	Data ingested are usually very heterogeneous in terms of data model, format, quality and any other aspect related to their usefulness for elaboration and combined use. For making data compatible with the necessity of the two platforms, some pre-processing procedures have to be realized. Those procedure differ for different type of data, especially among images and textual data.
Data storage	Structured textual data are stored on Relational Data Base Management Systems,

	Earth Observation images are stored on a GeoServer.
Context broker	A context broker provides context data management, exposing relevant data to third parties in a standard format. The context broker adopted supports the NGSI-LD API specification in order to ensure compatibility with FIWARE-based systems.
Analytics layer	This layer of the system provides algorithms to calculate key indicators defined for the territory. Currently agreed indicators are described in section 6.2.4
Frontend layer	This component will provide access to dashboards as a set of charts and map-based visualizations for end-users. Here, values of the indicators are provided to the user in order to support his decision processes.
Backend system	This component provides functionalities that allow platform administrators to set parameters and insert new data in the system.
IdM	This component allows identification, authentication, and authorization of users in order to ensure security of the entire platform.

Implementation

Based on the achievements represented by the mock-ups definition and the IT architecture, the platforms were conceived and implemented.

Data lake

Data pre-processing procedures are able to transform the available data from their heterogeneous format into a pre-defined relational structure that is managed by a PostgreSQL Data Base Management System.

Data pre-processing feature include the possibility to transform part of the data into NGSI-LD format and to publish it on the Context Broker component. The Context Broker component has been deployed as an instance of the FIWARE GE Orion Context Broker. It provides the means to make the water reuse strategic platform and the sludge management platform compliant to the FIWARE-based interoperability approach by allowing the publication of data through the NGSI-LD standard.

On the other hand, data about soils and their characterization and data about the river network are acquired as satellite images. Such images can be downloaded from the Geo portals of Regione Veneto and ARPAV. The download procedure can be performed both in a manual way by clicking on the available link and in a programmatic way by calling the Web Feature Service (WFS) endpoint provided by the Geoportal. In some cases, such files need manual pre-processing that is performed by using tools such as QGIS and PostGIS.

Access to the database is provided by RESTful APIs developed by leveraging the FastAPI framework. Figure 13 provides the list of some available APIs used to visualize the different layers, filter the soil characteristics and get the key indicators for of both tools #16 and #19.

BWaterSmart 0.1.0 OAS3
 /bwsapi/v1/openapi.json

Water module APIs ^

GET	/bws/api/v1/water/alldischarges/{limit}	Getalldischarges	▼
GET	/bws/api/v1/water/minornetwork/{dischargeid}	Minornetworkbydischarge	▼
GET	/bws/api/v1/water/minornetworkmulti/{dischargeid}	Minornetworkbydischarge	▼
GET	/bws/api/v1/water/allintakes/	Getallintakes	▼
GET	/bws/api/v1/water/allfonti/	Getallfonti	▼
GET	/bws/api/v1/water/allriversqualitybybasin/{bacino}	Getallriversqualitybybasin	▼
GET	/bws/api/v1/water/allriversquality/	Getallriversquality	▼
GET	/bws/api/v1/water/allstatochimicoybasin/{bacino}	Getallstatochimicoybasin	▼
GET	/bws/api/v1/water/allstatochimico/	Getallstatochimico	▼
GET	/bws/api/v1/water/interestedintakes/	Getinterestedintakes	▼
GET	/bws/api/v1/water/intakebyhydroid/{id_scarico}	Getintakebyhydroid	▼
GET	/bws/api/v1/water/minornetworkintakes/{dischargeid}	Getminornetworkintakes	▼
GET	/bws/api/v1/water/allpurifiers/{limit}	Getallpurifiers	▼
GET	/bws/api/v1/water/allmultibyDischarge/{dischargeid}	Getmnmmd	▼
GET	/bws/api/v1/water/allbasins/	Getallbasins	▼
GET	/bws/api/v1/water/allbasinsbyname/{name}	Getallbasinsbyname	▼
POST	/bws/api/v1/water/lia/	Getliametric	▼
GET	/bws/api/v1/water/lia_two/{dischargeid}	Lia Two	▼
GET	/bws/api/v1/water/allsp_2_15_azoto/{sp_az_id}	Getallsp 2 15 Azoto	▼
GET	/bws/api/v1/water/allazotobypoint/{requested_point}	Getallazotobypoint	▼
GET	/bws/api/v1/water/allmetbypoint/{requested_point}	Getallmetbypoint	▼
GET	/bws/api/v1/water/allpermuolibypoint/{requested_point}	Getallpermuolibypoint	▼
GET	/bws/api/v1/water/allsocbypoint/{requested_point}	Getallsocbypoint	▼
GET	/bws/api/v1/water/allzonevubypoint/{requested_point}	Getallzonevubypoint	▼

Discharge module APIs ^

GET	/bws/api/v1/discharge/dischargebybasin/{basinname}	Getalldischargesbybasinname	▼
GET	/bws/api/v1/discharge/alldischarges/{limit}	Getalldischarges	▼

Intake module APIs ^

GET	/bws/api/v1/intake/intakebybasin/{basinname}	Getallintakesbybasinname	▼
-----	--	--------------------------	---

Schemas ^

HTTPValidationError >
PointMeasureDTO >
ValidationError >

Figure 13 List of available RESTful APIs

Frontend layer

Data visualization features are provided by components that are part of ENG's Digital Enabler. In particular Dashram, a data visualization component has been used to allow easy dashboard management and use by the different users. Given the complexity of the visualizations to be developed for both tool #16 and #19, completely new plug-ins for the Dashram component had to be conceived and realized by leveraging the specialized Leaflet JavaScript framework.

Data from the PostgreSQL database are used by generating the Database views necessary for the specific charts to be produced. Each view represents the data table used to feed a chart.

Backend functionalities were developed by leveraging on the React JS library and creating ad-hoc web pages. For example, functionalities related to inserting/update of some information have been developed for regulations management.

Security and privacy

Keycloak⁵ is the component responsible for Identity and Access Management. It has been chosen for providing a security layer for both the water reuse strategic platform and for the sludge management platform. An identity and access manager tool enables organizations to guarantee, handle and monitor accesses from several users with different permissions and roles. This kind of tools provide, among other things, the possibility of performing password and role management and user activity monitoring. Keycloak is based on standard protocols and provides support for OpenID Connect, OAuth 2.0, and SAML.

5.1.4 Navigation and primary functionalities

This section provides examples of navigation of the main functionalities of the two platforms and of the backend system. A full user guide is out of scope of this deliverable, but will be realized later for training purposes.

The tools have a common entry point represented by a unique homepage. This homepage provides a brief introduction to the project and a set of cards that link to the actual functionalities of the tools.

⁵ <https://www.keycloak.org/>

Figure 14 Homepage

Before being able to access any of the tools, the user has to log-in with his/her username and password, which is associated to a specific user role with dedicated permissions.

Figure 15 Access management interface

5.1.5 Water reuse strategic platform

If the user accesses to the tool “Water reuse”, which corresponds to the Water reuse strategic platform (#16), he/she is firstly presented a map of the Veneto Region, with its water basins and with the possibility to show or hide five layers (water basins, ecological status of rivers, chemical status of rivers, agronomical withdrawals, discharge points of WWTPs). On the bottom-right corner of the screen, a legend is provided for the main symbols of the layers.

Figure 16 first screen of the Water reuse strategic platform (#16)

By right-clicking on the map, different options are provided with respect to the basin and to the whole Region. At basin level, the user can select:

- the visualization of the main information about the basin
- the visualization of the three main indicators

Figure 17 Options available on the map

When one of the options is selected, a dynamic panel is shown on the left of the screen, with the relevant information.

Figure 18 Dynamic panel for information visualization

As to the ecological status, if the corresponding layer is selected, a representation of the watercourses is shown, with colors representing the actual status of each segment where data is available.

Figure 19 ecological status layer

By right-clicking on one segment, it is possible to get detailed information about its ecological status.

Figure 20 details on the ecological status

As for the chemical status, if the corresponding layer is selected, a representation of the measurement points is shown, with colors representing the actual status of its measurement.

Figure 21 measurement points of the chemical status of watercourses

By right-clicking on one point, it is possible to get detailed information about its chemical status.

Figure 22 details on the chemical status at one specific measurement point

As for the discharge points of WWTPs, if the corresponding layer is selected, a representation of the discharge points is shown, with the possibility to right-click of each of them and get information and to highlight the watercourses affected by the discharged water.

Figure 23 main information about discharge points of WWTPs

Figure 24 watercourses impacted by a specific discharge

For such set of watercourses, it is possible to calculate the local indicator “Indirect Effluents Contribution to Agricultural Applications”.

Figure 25 options available on the selected watercourses (contribution to reuse index)

Finally, the user can access a second tab, on the top of the window, where the key indicators of the governance model are available for consultation. The next figure provides the visualization of some of such indicators, each one with its proper widget and related descriptions and information. The list of indicators is available in Table 21. Values represented here are not final, since some data are still to be integrated in the system after proper collection and pre-processing.

Figure 26 some key indexes for water management

5.1.6 Sludge management platform

If the user accesses the “Sludge management” tool, which corresponds to the Sludge management platform (#19), he/she is firstly presented a map of the Veneto Region, with the possibility to show or hide different layers (characteristics of soil, vulnerable zones, WWTPs)

Figure 27 first screen of the Sludge management platform, with available layers

Each soil characteristic can be individually selected along with their specific value intervals, which correspond to the different colors shown on the map.

Figure 28 selection of some layers and of some value intervals (sub-layers)

By right-clicking on a zone, the user gets information about the actual value of the characteristic selected in that specific point and the area (in hectares, ha) of the selected value interval.

Figure 29 details on a specific area

By enabling the layer related to WWTPs, the plants appear on the map, divided by population equivalent.

Figure 30 map of the WWTPs of the territory

Layers can be superimposed and overall information (with all the soil characteristics and vulnerability of the zone) can be obtained for any point on the map.

Figure 31 overall view on a selection of layers and on detailed information about a specific point on the map

Finally, the user can access a second tab, on the top of the window, where the Key indicators of the governance model are available for consultation. Next figure provides the visualization of some of such indicators, each one with its proper widget and related descriptions and information. The list of indicators is available in Table 21. Values represented here are not final, since some data are still to be integrated in the system after proper collection and pre-processing.

Figure 32 Some key indexes for sludge management

As a final example of tool #19's functionalities, Figure 33 shows how the systems provides a ranked list of reuse opportunities for sludge with different quality levels. Ranking is possible with respect to parameters related to carbon footprint and costs. Values represented here are not final, since some data are still to be integrated in the system after proper collection and pre-processing.

Figure 33 Ranked opportunities for sludge reuse based on sludge quality level

5.1.7 Backend system

Administrators can update some parameters and data managed by the system. For example, existing descriptions of regulations and/or add new regulations. A new regulation includes several input fields, as shown in the next figure, including the domain, the geographical level, and the source of the regulation.

BWS Portale Normative

Cerca Normativa

Inserisci una nuova normativa

Ambito * Livello * Fonte Normativa *

Titolo Normativa *

Note

Dettaglio normativa *

Titolo Dettaglio Normativa

Principali Contenuti *

Qualifiche

Leva

Barriera

Altro

Commenti e Ricadute *

Figure 34 creation of a new regulation

Updating and existing regulation can be done after searching it. Searching existing regulations can be done in two ways:

- by searching “full text” on the title
- by exploring a tree structure that allows to select firstly the relevant domain and then the geographical level (UE, National, Regional)

Figure 35 searching existing regulations can be done by exploring a tree-structure or by a full-text searching

5.1.8 Interoperability

The interoperability approach adopted in the Venice LL is inherited by the Digital Enabler, and its FIWARE-based approach. The platforms include some data in NGSI-LD format, exposing them on the FIWARE Orion Context Broker and allowing third party systems to subscribe to its entities. In particular, data about WWTPs are exposed by leveraging the “PontOfInterest”⁶ Smart Data Model.

Moreover, the Venice LL is collaborating directly with FIWARE

- to extend the data model “WaterQualityObserved”⁷ based on the parameters used in the case study and
- to create a new Smart Data Model about quality parameters of sludge. This data model is currently in the incubated state with the name “SludgeQualityObserved”.

As to the maturity levels defined in D3.1, both the water reuse strategic platform and the sludge management platform are considered as level 4.

5.1.9 Accessing tool and test data

The homepage is reachable at the following URL: <https://portal-bws.opsi.lecce.it/>

Please contact davide.storelli@eng.it to get access credentials.

⁶ <https://github.com/smart-data-models/dataModel.PointOfInterest>

⁷ <https://github.com/smart-data-models/dataModel.WaterQuality/blob/master/WaterQualityObserved/README.md>

5.2 Environment for decision support and alternative course selection (#17)

5.2.1 Tool description and attributes

Tool #17 – *Environment for decision support and alternative course selection* – is a multi-criteria decision framework designed to enable direct assessment, comparison and prioritization of decisional alternatives. The tool was released on M30 as planned.

In the context of the project, it is applied to the final prioritization between the supply/demand matchmaking alternatives developed in Tool #25 and qualified by Tools #24 and #27, as shown in the overall schematic below (Figure 36).

Figure 36: Relationship and overall workflow for the set of tools #25, #24, #27 and #17.

The high-level goal of tool #17 is to enable users to select the best water source combinations to satisfy specific non-potable uses, and to enable prioritization of strategic and tactical planning options on the governance of water sources and water uses in an urban setting.

The supply and demand alternative combinations are assessed through a range of standardized, user-selected performance, risk and cost metrics, complementing those employed to qualify the initial selection in Tool #25 (e.g., volume availability, cost, energy content, carbon footprint, nutrient content) and further qualification through risk assessment in Tool #27 as well as potentially Tool #24, if applicable.

The targeted end users of Tool #17 are water demand planners and decision-makers in urban management, municipal and water utility contexts.

The tool is deployable at any spatial scale as it applies to any supply/demand context.

The tool was developed by Baseform using its own proprietary Java-based, web-centric software platform designed for networked infrastructures.

It had a TRL of 5 at the outset of the project, as concerns the specific application intended in the project (particularly the metrics to be used). The tool was delivered on M32 as planned, with an estimated TRL of 7. Its usage and testing until the end of the project will help fully validate that assessment, particularly in its intended use cases.

Table 9: Attributes and description of the Environment for decision support and alternative course selection

Tool's attribute	Description
Type of product	A software supporting the Circular Economy
Name	Tool #17 - Environment for decision support and alternative course selection
Description	<p>A multi-criteria decision framework designed to allow for direct comparison of the supply/demand matchmaking alternatives produced by the water-energy- phosphorous balance planning module and potentially qualified by the reclaimed water distribution network water quality model and the risk assessment for urban water reuse module.</p> <p>The high-level goal of this tool is to enable users to select the best water source combinations to satisfy specific non-potable uses, and to enable prioritisation of strategic and tactical planning options on the governance of water sources and water uses in an urban setting.</p>
Abbreviation	n/a
URL	https://bwatersmart.baseform.com
Costs	Not available at this stage
Target audience	Water demand planners and decision-makers in urban management, municipal and water utility contexts.
Actors, roles and interactions	Water demand planners and decision-makers in urban management, municipal and water utility contexts.
Unique selling points /Added Value/Innovation	Standardized means to compare reused water supply/demand combinations through multiple criteria
TRL	TRL 7

Technical requirements	Computer, tablet or smartphone with internet access.
Environment	Any updated internet browser in any operating environment.
Version	4.0
Initial release	2023 (for the current version)
License type	Commercial
Programming language/technologies used	Java
Open interface	API, web services
Graphical User Interface / Headless software	Browser-based graphical user interface
Supported spatial scales	Neighborhood, city, region
Supported temporal scales	Monthly, annual
Water Use Types	Urban
Compatibility with FIWARE	Read/write compatibility only (through API or webservices)
Organisations	Baseform
Contact details	Diogo Vitorino (diogo.vitorino@baseform.com)
Data Manager	Diogo Vitorino (diogo.vitorino@baseform.com)
Technologies	Java
Tags	#reuse #water #multicriteria #supply #demand

Images

ZONE 2 | Data | Ranking | 3D Cube | baseform Sérgio Coelho | SAVE

METRICS	Planning				
	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027
A.600 0 - Status quo					
M00 Satisfied Demand	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
M01 Reclaimed water used	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
M02 Reclaimed water use vs availability	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
M03 Energy consumption	0.66	0.66	0.66	0.66	0.66
M04 Carbon footprint of energy consumption	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18
M05 P-fertilizer production avoided	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
M06 CAPEX	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
M07 OPEX	2.12	2.18	2.43	2.48	2.52
M08 Total cost	2.17	2.22	2.47	2.53	2.56
A.601 1 - Easy win					
M00 Satisfied Demand	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
M01 Reclaimed water used	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
M02 Reclaimed water use vs availability	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
M03 Energy consumption	0.43	0.43	0.43	0.43	0.43
M04 Carbon footprint of energy consumption	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11
M05 P-fertilizer production avoided	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Caption/Source

The images show respectively:

- the four tools in Baseform’s B-Watersmart deployment (URL below);
- Tool #17 main screen showing the metric selection expanded on the left, and the metrics’ values as received from #25 for the various alternatives;
- One of the alternatives’ comparison screens;
- The 3D comparison cube where the various alternatives (Z-axis) are assessed over time (Y-axis) and across the set of metrics (X-axis).

	The software is accessible at https://bwatersmart.baseform.com , for registered users.
Publications	https://baseform.com

5.2.2 Pre-existing background

Baseform software, as described in <https://baseform.com/np4/product/>

5.2.3 Developments and advancements within the project

The tool is based on a pre-existing app available in the Baseform system, that has been graphically redesigned as well as functionally adapted to connect directly to tool #25.

5.2.4 Navigation and primary functionalities

The figures below depict the logical navigation sequence across the tool’s key functionality.

Figure 37: The set of four tools represented by icons in Baseform’s environment, accessible at <https://bwatersmart.baseform.com>.

Figure 38: When the app is started, it displays the available analyses as well as the option to create a new one (top right). An analysis contains a set of alternatives, a set of metrics to assess them, over a set of timesteps. It may include the specification of different scenarios (external contexts).

Figure 39: The app's home screen and Data tab, with the main menu on the left, allowing for the specification of the key parameters: objectives (shown), timesteps, metrics, alternatives. There is also the ability to import or export from/to a dedicated Excel® format which facilitates sharing of results or further manipulation of the analysis.

Figure 40: Displaying the various metrics that, in this case, were imported directly from a linked Matchmaking analysis (Tool #25), along with the alternatives, using the option available through the last item on the menu. The user can also add new metrics directly on this environment.

EDIT METRIC

CODE
M01

NAME
Reclaimed water used

DESCRIPTION
BASEFORM Expected value of unmet demand over a 1-year period, calculated in UNMET. The risk of service interruption associated to a specific pipe depends not only on its likelihood of failure but also on the consequence that its failure can bring to the service. Therefore, this risk is calculated for each pipe as a combination of failure probability, calculated in FAIL, and component importance, calculated in CIMP. Failure estimates require that work order tables and pipe tables are updated for each step of the alternatives that involve changes in the infrastructure. In this case, only the

EXCLUSION CONDITION: RED IN THIS METRIC WILL MAKE ALTERNATIVE RED OVERALL

WEIGHT
medium (1.0)

REFERENCE VALUES
100.00 75.00 50.00 25.00

3
2
1
0

25 50 75 100

CANCEL DELETE SAVE

Figure 41: The Metrics Editor, where the user introduces the relationship between the metric's 'real world' values and a standardized 0-to-3 scale that is used throughout the app, effectively turning each metric into an index. Metrics may be given a relative weight from a closed list (0.5, 1, 2) – this is used later when ranking the alternatives.

Figure 42: Showing the alternatives available for this analysis – they can be imported from tool #25 or created here. The table lists all the values for every alternative, metric and timestep. The values shown are the standardized index values of each metric (0-3), with the ‘real world’ value shown in grey underneath. If the alternatives are created here, then its values are either typed in on this screen, or imported using the Excel® import/export facility.

The screenshot shows the 'Alternatives Editor' interface. The main table displays data for 'A.800 0 - Status quo' across years 2023 to 2027. The 'Edit alternative' dialog box is open, showing the following details:

- CODE:** 602
- NAME:** 2 - Reuse it
- DESCRIPTION:** Reutilizar água em usos não potáveis sempre que possível, tendo em consideração o consumo energético associado (trade-off com pegada de carbono) --> objetivo: reutilizar água em pelo menos 50% do consumo não potável

Buttons at the bottom of the dialog include CANCEL, DELETE, DUPLICATE AS..., and SAVE.

Figure 43: The Alternatives Editor, where a name and description are introduced (they may also have been imported from Tool #25).

Figure 44: The Ranking tab, where alternatives are color-coded (0-1 red; 1-2 yellow; 2-3 green) according to the values of the metrics. Hovering the mouse pointer over a colored dot displays the standardized value of the metric. If different weights are present, the size of the dots reflects it.

Figure 45: Ranking the alternatives over time by individual metric, with an overall value obtained through a weighted average.

Figure 46: Ranking the alternatives on a given year, with an overall value obtained through a weighted average.

Figure 47: The 3D cube provides an overview of the decisional problem with the 3 dimensions – alternatives over time and across all metrics – simultaneously displayed. This allows for a unique overall perception of the dynamics of decision among the alternatives.

Figure 48: a 2D slice of the cube can be obtained by clicking on a tick mark on any of the three axes, allowing for instant clarification along any of the dimensions of analysis. Here we see one of the alternatives under analysis.

5.2.5 Interoperability

The Baseform platform is not designed using the FIWARE model. However, compatibility with FIWARE is available at read/write level through API and/or webservice.

5.2.6 Indicative applications and synergistic benefits

This tool may be applied to any decisional problem of the same type (alternatives vs. metrics over time). In the particular implementation that is embodied in Tool #17, it is designed to work in tandem with Tool #25 and assess the supply/ demand matchmaking alternatives developed there.

5.2.7 Accessibility and test data

The tool is part of the set of four tools developed by Baseform (#17, 24, 25, 27) for application in the Lisbon Living Lab, where it has been undergoing testing and application to the specific cases being explored in this LL. Sets of test data are available with the software. Real case application data pertaining to the Lisbon Living Lab are available from LNEC and CML.

Accredited users may access the tool at the URL below. For the duration of the project, user credentials should be requested directly from Baseform through the following contact point: diogo.vitorino@baseform.com.

<https://bwatersmart.baseform.com>

5.3 Re-Actor (#18)

5.3.1 Tool description and attributes

The RE-ACTOR Tool is a DSS for the evaluation of new investments and actions related to water reuse and water treatment. The tool allows simulating alternative scenarios in a territory to explore potential impacts related to different actuations, such as new processes in a WWTP, installation of renewable technologies or new reclaimed water distribution infrastructure to supply new users with reclaimed water.

Figure 49 Re-Actor graphical summary: inputs and outputs of the tool.

As presented in Figure 49, the tool integrates an API (Parameter's Editor) that allows the administrator to modify costs, environmental impacts, and other technical parameters relevant for each technology or set of actions. On the other hand, on the Project's Editor, the user may create or edit projects that are composed of a baseline scenario and alternative modified scenarios.

A Baseline Scenario is defined by a group of Assets from a territory (e.g., WWTPs, DWTP, etc.) with specific parameters and characteristics. The user will then create Modified Scenarios by adding new assets or deleting assets from the baseline scenario or by applying actions to the existing assets (e.g., installation of renewable energies or modification of the treatment train of a WWTP).

Figure 50 Architecture of RE-ACTOR Tool

Table 10: Re-Actor's attributes and description

Tool's attribute	Description
Type of product	A software supporting the Circular Economy
Name	RE-ACTOR
Description	DSS for the evaluation of new investments and actions related to water reuse and circular economy solutions within the urban water cycle. Scope of application: regional level.
Abbreviation	-
URL	https://reactor.fidesol.org/login
Costs	OPEX – Domain and server maintenance (approx.. 400€/month), + staff costs of using it (dependent on time dedicated)
Target audience	Decision-makers on urban water investments. Water utilities. Competent administration.
Actors, roles and interactions	Technology providers, industries to provide with data to feed the economic and technical models Water utilities, planners, and decision makers as end-users
Unique selling points /Added Value/Innovation	Main added value of the RE-ACTOR is its agility to assess quickly different scenarios and its user friendly interface. The end-user will be able to easily analyse complex potential investments and scenarios to prioritize those showing highest cost-benefit potential.

TRL	TRL 7
Technical requirements	Internet and minimum requirements to access to the web app
Environment	Web app
Version	v1.0 – first alpha version developed
Initial release	2023
License type	Subscription-based licence
Programming language/technologies used	Python3, Django and docker for Back. Angular for Front.
Open interface	None
Graphical User Interface / Headless software	GUI – web app
Supported spatial scales	City/Regions
Supported temporal scales	N/A
Water Use Types	Urban, agriculture, industrial
Compatibility with FIWARE	Not compatible
Organisations	Cetaqua, AGBAR, Veolia, Aguas de Alicante
Contact details	Miquel Sarrias - miquel.sarrias@cetaqua.com <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ignacio Casals – ignacio.casals@aguasdealicante.es
Data Manager	Miquel Sarrias - miquel.sarrias@cetaqua.com
Technologies	Energy production: anaerobic (co)-digestion, micro-turbines, PV panels Membrane systems: Brine valorisation technologies Biological systems
Tags	DSS, environmental impact, economic impact, investment assessment, technologies

Images

**Bienvenido a Re-actor,
Gregorio**

Seleccione una de las dos opciones

Ponga un nombre a un Nuevo Proyecto

Nombre de Proyecto

Cargue un Proyecto

Seleccione un Proyecto

PROYECTO ANDALUCÍA
Valores globales de Conversión
EB_Proyecto Andalucía
Añadir Activo
Crear ER

AÑADA UN ACTIVO

EDAR ETAP

IDAM

2. CARACTERÍSTICAS BÁSICAS

Nombre de la instalación	Caudal de Diseño
B-WATERSMART	1000
Población servida	Sociedad
1000	B-WATERSMART

3. TREN DE TRATAMIENTO

Tratamiento Primario <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Eliminación N <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Tratamiento Secundario <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Eliminación P <input type="checkbox"/>
Tratamiento Terciario <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Físico-Químico <input type="checkbox"/>

<p>Caption/Source</p>		
	<p>Publications</p>	<p>N.A</p>
	<p>Publications</p>	<p>N.A</p>

5.3.2 Pre-existing background

An existing mock-up of a real-time Water Allocation Tool was initially conceived to be the pre-existing background of the RE-ACTOR tool. However, in an early phase of the B-WaterSmart project, after analysing main challenges of the Living Lab Alicante, it was decided to shift the goal of the tool to better address the challenges and ambitions of this LL and to enable better achievement of the projects' objectives and impact. Thus, instead of an optimisation tool for real-time resource allocation, a decision support system for the evaluation of new investments and infrastructures to analyse alternative scenarios was proposed, that also enables an assessment of the very technologies that are developed and demonstrated within

B-WaterSmart at the LL Alicante. It is for this reason that no existing background software was used, and the tool was developed from scratch.

5.3.3 Developments and advancements within the project

As described previously, the RE-ACTOR tool has been developed from scratch. Thus, within the B-WaterSmart project main requirements for the tool were defined and use cases were analysed in a joint work from Aguas de Alicante and Cetaqua. Then, the main structure and architecture of the tool was defined and a basic mock-up was elaborated. With help of that basic mock-up, the tool concept was discussed with the tool developers and an interactive mock-up was elaborated. This interactive mock-up has allowed to define graphic identity of the tool and define in depth processes, menus and use cases of the tool. In parallel, the type of assets included in the tool, set of actions, parameters required, and databases have been defined together with the calculation formulas and required parameters to assess technical, environmental, and economically the different actions and investments that have been included in the tool.

The development phase of the tool has included the front-end and back-end development of the RE-ACTOR tool, from the log-in of a user, the creation of a new project, the definition of a baseline scenario, the selection of a set of actions to be assessed and the evaluation of the impacts of this set of actions and their comparison to the baseline scenario.

5.3.4 Navigation and primary functionalities

The aim of this section is to briefly introduce the readers to the tool's interfaces and primary functionalities e.g., how to access the tool, menus, display windows, etc. serving as a very brief manual.

The tool differentiates between 3 different user roles: users, regional administrators and a global administrator. The global administrator is allowed to modify the tool databases and parameters, affecting the obtained results in the tool projects. This role also allows adding regional administrators, who are responsible for managing users and administering their roles regarding projects. Tool users are able to create new projects or load the ones they are permitted to. When creating a new project, the user will be asked to either create a new Baseline Scenario (BS) or to load an existing one from a previous project. A baseline scenario includes a set of assets (e.g. WWTPs, Drinking Water Treatment Plants (DWTPs), Sea Water Desalination Plant (SWDP)) with their characteristics and parameters defined. Then, the user can create several Modified Scenarios (MS) by removing assets, adding new ones, or applying a pre-defined set of actions to the existing assets (for example, installing renewable energies, installing a tertiary treatment in a WWTP or applying co-digestion to a WWTP with an anaerobic digestion process). Finally, the tool will allow the user to easily compare the environmental and economic impacts of the modified scenarios with the baseline scenario, allowing to identify the most promising ones.

Figure 51 Flow diagram of a user experience with RE-ACTOR Tool

5.3.5 Interoperability

Since the architecture does not rely on any kind of context broker or exposed API, FIWARE has not been integrated.

Different connections have been made with other services or tools, for example with the Photovoltaic Geographical Information System database from the EC-JRC (https://re.jrc.ec.europa.eu/pvg_tools/en/tools.html) for the calculation of solar energy generation for the entire Spanish territory.

5.3.6 Accessing tool and test data

Access to the RE-ACTOR tool is done through the web address <https://reactor.fidesol.org/login>.

To access the platform it is necessary for users to identify themselves by means of an email address and password. Using these credentials, the system identifies and authenticates the users, giving them access to the functionalities defined by the role assigned to each user. New users can only register if an existing user on the platform with roles invites them previously, so there is no open registration functionality. To get access to the platform, please contact the following email addresses: eric.santos@cetaqua.com, miquel.sarrias@cetaqua.com.

Figure 52 User login

5.4 UWC observatory (#20)

5.4.1 Tool description and attributes

Lisboa E-Nova developed the Urban Water Cycle Observatory of Lisbon (UWC) to systematise, collect and facilitate access to data on the city water cycle.

The Lisbon Urban Water Cycle Observatory is a data visualization instrument to monitor and communicate performance, support urban planning and decision making.

Following the motto “to know so to reduce”, the Observatory is integrated in the scope of Lisbon city's sustainability policies, covering water and wastewater dimensions, as well also other environmental dimensions of the city, namely energy consumption, urban waste management, greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions and mobility.

This Observatory includes two complementary tools:

- a public access tool, with open data information of the water and wastewater city dimensions (top-down approach)
- a private access tool, for individual entities to integrate and analyse, via a set of analytics, the water consumption data of their facilities (bottom-up approach)

The public access privileges the use of infographics providing information on the city's water matrix, on an annual basis, regarding main water flows, consumption disaggregation by type of water source (potable and alternative water sources, including reclaimed water), by type of use and by type of user, per capita indicators, amount of treated wastewater and reclaimed water production.

This set of data allows citizens and city stakeholders to be informed, to know their impact and feel motivated to participate and act towards increasing efficiency, assessing the impact of implemented policies, monitoring the benefits of behaviour changes and, consequently, continue to move towards the necessary change.

The private access is aimed at single entities that access the UWC Observatory upon request and whose facilities have water metering reported in digital data. This allows visualization of aggregated consumptions and costs per typology of water use and type of water source, water consumption evolution and individual consumption analysis, leading to an insightful water management, supported by data analytics and automatic performance reports.

In short, the UWC Observatory faces the upcoming challenges of sustainable water management and use, which need to be tackled as soon as possible to improve the “water smartness for responsible consumers”.

The public access had a first preliminary version launched in 2019. The developments made under the scope of the B-WaterSmart project highly improved it and were released in 2021 and a further improvement in 2023. As for the private access, it was launched in 2021.

The end users of the tool are slightly different for each access. The Public access end users are Citizens, Municipalities (specially Lisbon municipality in the scope of the Lisbon LL), Politicians, Decision makers, Urban management authorities, Academia, Researchers, NGOs, Media and other key stakeholders. As for the private access, the end users are mainly Municipalities (specially Lisbon municipality in the scope of the Lisbon LL), Local administration, Private institutions of public interest, and Entities with high water use and/or large number of water meters.

In terms of the scale application, the public access has a broader implementation to the city scale, as the private access can be implemented at an entity with a large number of water meters or even at a single water meter scale.

The water use type are also different for each access. The public access is focused on the Lisbon urban uses (Domestic, Non-Domestic, Green spaces, Urban Hygiene and Others) and Lisbon urban sectors for potable water (Domestic, Commerce and Industry, Central government, Institutions, Municipal and Economic losses). The private access can use any possible type of water source, as long it is digital data (of water meters/consumption), which is demonstrated in a “test user”.

The development of these accesses was made with contributions from different entities. The public access was idealized and developed by Lisboa E-Nova and implemented with the contribution of an external service. The private access was idealized, developed and implemented entirely by Lisboa E-Nova.

Regarding the programming language of the tool, the public access of the Observatory consists in an infographic based in a web portal build in HTML and CSS, the loading of data is done through PHP scripts using AJAX with Javascript (JQuery) and the data is stored in a MySql base. As for the private access, it is a web application, in which the backend is built with Django (Python) using a REST API for client access and the frontend is built with Vue.js (javascript) and finally the infrastructure is organised in docker containers.

Currently, the UWC Observatory has a TRL of 6.

Portuguese language:

- <https://observatorios-lisboa.pt/index.html> - Main website of Lisbon Observatories (public access)
- https://observatorios-lisboa.pt/info_agua.html - Water tab (public access)
- https://observatorios-lisboa.pt/info_aguasresiduais.html - Wastewater tab (public access)
- <https://privado.observatorios-lisboa.pt/login> - Private access

English language:

- <https://www.observatorios-lisboa.pt/en/index.html> - Main website of Lisbon Observatories (public access)
- https://www.observatorios-lisboa.pt/en/info_agua.html - Water tab (public access)
- https://www.observatorios-lisboa.pt/en/info_aguasresiduais.html - Wastewater tab (public access)

Table 11: Attributes and description of the UWC observatory

Tool's attribute	Description
Type of product	A service, offered as part of a Circular Economy enabling portfolio A methodology or a process related with the Circular Economy
Name	Urban Water Cycle Observatory of Lisbon
Description	The Lisbon Urban Water Cycle Observatory is a data visualization instrument for monitor and communicate performance, support urban planning and decision making. Following the motto “to know so to reduce”, the Observatory is integrated in the scope of Lisbon city’s sustainability policies, covering water and wastewater dimensions. This UWC Observatory is divided in two complementary tools: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a public access tool, with open data information of the water and wastewater city dimensions (top-down approach) • a private access tool, for individual entities integrate and analyse, via a set of analytics, the water consumption data of their facilities (bottom-up approach).
Abbreviation	NA
URL	Portuguese language: https://observatorios-lisboa.pt/index.html - Main website of Lisbon Observatories (public access) https://observatorios-lisboa.pt/info_agua.html - Water tab (public access) https://observatorios-lisboa.pt/info_aguasresiduais.html - Wastewater tab (public access) https://privado.observatorios-lisboa.pt/login - Private access (Portuguese language only) English language: https://www.observatorios-lisboa.pt/en/index.html - Main website of Lisbon Observatories (public access) https://www.observatorios-lisboa.pt/en/info_agua.html - Water tab (public access)

	<p>https://www.observatorios-lisboa.pt/en/info_aguasresiduais.html - Wastewater tab (public access)</p>
Costs	<p>Public access:</p> <p>No costs for using the public access of the Urban Water Cycle Observatory of Lisbon and download available data.</p> <p>Private access:</p> <p>No costs foreseen for the Lisboa E-Nova associated entities (including Lisbon Municipality) and private institutions of public interest.</p>
Target audience	<p>Public access:</p> <p>Citizens, Municipalities (specially Lisbon municipality in the scope of the Lisbon LL), Politicians, Decision makers, Urban management authorities, Academia, Researchers, NGOs, Media and other key stakeholders</p> <p>Private access:</p> <p>Municipalities (specially Lisbon municipality in the scope of the Lisbon LL),</p> <p>Local administration,</p> <p>Private institutions of public interest,</p> <p>Other Entities with high water use and/or large number of water meters.</p>
Actors, roles and interactions	<p>Public access:</p> <p>Citizens (Better-informed society, Citizens engaged and empowered for water efficiency - users), Municipality (Sustainability policies - users), Water and Wastewater utilities (data providers), Any other entities (users).</p> <p>Private access:</p> <p>Lisbon Municipality (living lab owner, tool user), Water and Wastewater utilities (data providers) and entities with high water use and/or large number of water meters (tool users).</p>
Unique selling points /Added Value/Innovation	<p>The public access of the Lisbon Water Observatory addresses the need for a transparent, simplified visualisation of water use and for a deeper understanding of possible levers to contribute to smart water use, to a secure water supply, increase resilience and save resources.</p> <p>The Private access responds to the need of users to have a platform with water consumption, data analysis in an integrated manner providing a holistic, transparent, and simplified view of water consumption per use and source, to support decision making and foster sustainable water use, as well allowing analysis per facility or aggregation of consumption by type of water use and associated costs, has well other indicators associated like energy and carbon footprint and nutrients recovery (specifically phosphorous).</p>

	Both the accesses foster the digitalization and use of big data, to promote efficiency and protection of the water resource.
TRL	TRL6
Technical requirements	Public access: Only an updated browser is needed to use the tool. Private access: Only an updated browser is needed to use the tool.
Environment	Not applicable
Version	Public access:3.0 Private access:2.0
Initial release	2021
License type	Free
Programming language/technologies used	Public access: Infographic based in a web portal build in HTML and CSS. The loading of data is done through PHP scripts using AJAX with Javascript (jQuery). The data is stored in a MySQL base. Private access: Web application, in which the backend is built with Django (Python) using a REST API for client access and the frontend is built with Vue.js (javascript). The infrastructure is organised in docker containers.
Open interface	Private access: The API can be integrated in external services.
Graphical User Interface / Headless software	Public access: Web application Private access: Web application
Supported spatial scales	Public access – City Private access – Entity and single water meters
Supported temporal scales	Public access – Annual data Private access – Annual, monthly, daily and quarter-hour data
Water Use Types	Public access:

	<p>Lisbon urban uses (Domestic, Non-domestic, Green spaces, Urban hygiene and Others) and Lisbon urban sectors of potable water (Domestic, Commerce and Industry, Central Government, Institutions, Municipal and Economic losses).</p> <p>Private access:</p> <p>Any possible type of water, as long it is digital data (of water meters/consumption), which is demonstrated in a “test user”.</p> <p>Currently, it has integrated only urban uses of potable water consumption from the entities already using the tool, since there is still no digital data of alternative water sources available.</p>
Compatibility with FIWARE	The tool is not FIWARE compliant
Organisations	Lisboa E-Nova – Agência de Energia e Ambiente de Lisboa
Contact details	<p>Public access:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rui Mendes, ruimendes@lisboaenova.org • Rui Dinis, ruidinis@lisboaenova.org • observatorios@lisboaenova.org <p>Private access:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rui Mendes, ruimendes@lisboaenova.org
Data Manager	<p>Rui Mendes</p> <p>ruimendes@lisboaenova.org</p>
Technologies	Resource for Circular Economy
Tags	<p>#Creative data to build awareness, engage and empower citizens</p> <p>#Better-informed society</p> <p>#Transparent and accessible information</p> <p>#Water smartness for responsible consumers</p> <p>#Sustainable water use</p> <p>#Improve water efficiency</p> <p>#Data analysis</p>
Images	<p>Characteristic images or schematic representations of the tool. In case provided as a separate file, all known formats up to a certain size which are supported by web browsers are accepted (e.g., jpeg, png). The file must not exceed the size of 5MB.</p> <p>Public access:</p>

<https://observatorios-lisboa.pt/index.html> – Main website of Lisbon Observatories (public access)

https://observatorios-lisboa.pt/info_agua.html – Water tab (public access)

https://observatorios-lisboa.pt/info_aguasresiduais.html – Wastewater tab (public access)

Private access:

Dashboard view of the private access (test user)

	<p>Individual view of detailed analysis to a specific water meter (test user)</p>
Caption/Source	See above
Publications	<p>Publications related with the tool, product or service</p> <p>https://lisboaenova.org/relancamento-dos-observatorios-lisboa/</p> <p>https://lisboaenova.org/lancamento-da-nova-versao-da-plataforma-observatorios-lisboa/</p> <p>https://www.lisboa.pt/capital-verde-2020/noticias/detalhe/relancamento-dos-observatorios-de-lisboa</p> <p>https://www.lisboa.pt/cidade/ambiente/qualidade-ambiental/agua</p> <p>https://www.adene.pt/camara-municipal-de-lisboa-distingue-adene-pela-cooperacao-no-portal-observatorios-lisboa/</p> <p>Revista (Magazine) Smart Cities Portugal, n. 36, Article “DAR DE BEBER ÀS CIDADES”, written by Rui Mendes, in which the Lisbon Observatories and the B-WaterSmart Project was mentioned.</p>

5.4.2 Pre-existing background

The base and the origins of the UWC Observatory (public access) were the Water Matrix of Lisbon. This was a document Lisboa E-Nova developed and updated annually.

http://lisboaenova.org/images/stories/Lisboaenova/Ebook_Agua/mobile/index.html#p=1

Additionally, there was a first published and very preliminary version of the Lisbon Water Observatory (public access), which had very limited data.

As for the private access, there was no pre-existing tool for water. There was just a first draft of a mock up for a private access of electricity data (not part of the scope of B-WaterSmart development).

5.4.3 Developments and advancements within the project

Public access:

In the scope of the B-WaterSmart project, the public access of the observatory evolved from a very preliminary version to a second version and much more evolved and mature version (2.0) and currently a more structured recent version (3.0), presenting an infographic with clear and transparent data, providing intelligible data to citizens and stakeholders.

The Lisbon Observatories public access is structured in five environmental dimensions:

- Energy
- Water
- Wastewater
- Urban Waste
- GHG Emissions
- Mobility

The Urban Water Cycle Observatory of Lisbon is integrated into the Lisbon Observatories. The integration of the Urban Water Cycle Observatory of Lisbon into an overarching platform for combined evolution monitoring and analysis, provides an overview and integrated data information of several environmental dimensions of cities, which promotes efficiency and circularity, linking water, wastewater, energy, GHG emissions, urban waste and mobility. It uses infographics with creative data to build awareness, engage and empower citizens.

Figure 53 Entry page of the Lisbon Observatories

The entry page of the Lisbon Observatories provides the Lisbon Citizen Profile for the several environmental dimensions presented (per capita indicators).

Information and knowledge are crucial elements for well-informed citizens to feel aware, empowered, and committed with public policy challenges. Only with accessible, comprehensive, and clear data will we enable the impact monitoring of our behaviour - as individuals and as part of a group - in the quality of life and environment we live and, therefore, maintain the path towards the sustainable transition.

The Lisbon Water Cycle Observatory public access consists specifically in the Water and Wastewater dimensions. The public access is available both in Portuguese and English languages and all data regarding water and wastewater can be downloaded.

WATER

The Water dimension discloses a set of comprehensive data about the potable water consumed in the city, including:

- Water consumption per year, in total volume and per capita,
- Water consumption by water source per year,
- Daily average water consumption per capita (total and domestic), frequently used indicators to compare cities performance,
- Water consumption by type of use and water source per year,
- Annual potable water consumption by sector in volume,
- Potable water consumption by sector in percentage,
- Potable water consumption by parish per year, including the disaggregation of the total volume, residential sector volume, Commercial & industry volume, in map and chart view.

Figure 54 Water dimension tab

WASTEWATER

The Wastewater dimension discloses data about the treated wastewater in the city and its disaggregation, including:

- Treated wastewater of Lisbon per year, in total volume and per capita,
- Total wastewater treated by WWTP per year,
- Treated wastewater generated per year in and outside city boundaries in total or by WWTP,
- Comparison between WWTP of the wastewater treated in and outside city boundaries,

Figure 55 Wastewater dimension tab

Private access:

As for the private access for water it was born and was developed entirely within the B-WaterSmart project, which is a Web application integrating water consumption of user's facilities, with several characteristics and also a set of data analytics to the data for a deeper understanding of use of water. It was developed as a first version, which was updated separating the front end from the back end, to have a much more modern and efficient approach.

The private access (user log requirement) comprises Water and Energy data.

In terms of architecture of the private access, the scheme presented in the following image illustrates its design.

Figure 56 Overall private access architecture

The Water dimension of the private access makes part of the Urban Water Cycle Observatory of Lisbon, having a bottom-up approach, since it is aimed at single entities to monitoring and analyse their water consumption. It allows visualization of water consumption per facility and its evolution, aggregation per type of use and water source, associated costs, performance indicators (e.g. m^3/m^2), identify water efficiency opportunities/measures and monitor their impacts after implementation, present georeferencing of facilities, indicators of energy and carbon footprint (specific consumption of energy and CO_2 and recovery of nutrients (specifically phosphorous for the reclaimed water used for irrigation).

There is also the possibility to perform individual analysis per facility, which can be more detailed depending on the frequency of available data per water meter, integrating monthly, daily or quarter-hour data. It is also possible for entities to set up the analysis of customised alerts for specific consumption levels for each facility, to generate automatic performance reports based on all the data analytics presented for each facility and to export all data and graphs produced.

Figure 57 Private access entrance page

In addition, it allows interoperability and communication with other tools via an API. This leads to an insightful management of water consumption supported by data analytics, alarmistic and automatic performance reports.

Therefore, the private access Observatory provides an integrated tool for water consumption management and data analysis, supporting decision making and fostering “water smartness for responsible consumers”.

This access is structured in four tabs:

- Dashboard
- Individual
- User
- Instalações (Facilities)

DATA ANALYSIS

The dashboard tab provides aggregated data (consumption and costs) by type of use and type of water (gardens, markets, fireman, etc of potable water, gardens of reclaimed water, etc) allowing monthly and yearly visualization.

The individual tab provides a set of data analytics for each facility. This analysis makes a depth assessment (facility water consumption ‘fingerprint’).

The results of the data analysis are presented in graphs, which are all possible to download to PDF or PNG and the background data for XLS or CSV.

The users access a list of all the facilities under management, with several available filters and georeferenced. Additionally, for facilities that have telemetry data available, both daily or/and quarter hour data, it’s possible to visualize a further deeper analysis on the consumption for a selected period, providing detailed graphic analysis.

ALERTS

It’s also possible to set analysis on the three types of alerts in the potable water supplier platform:

1. % of consumption above the average,
2. Amount of consumption above a defined value,
3. Continuous consumption above a defined value for a period of 6 to 24 hours.

REPORTING

There is also a feature to produce automatic custom reports for each facility, in which the user selects the analysis/graphs desired, to automatically produced a PDF file.

USERS AND FACILITIES MANAGEMENT

The user tab is related to the access and permissions. Each individual entity has a main login and can create several sub-logs with different access levels to information.

Finally, the facilities tab is focused on the facilities database list, which contain all the characteristics associated with each single facility. This data is also possible to download to Excel or PDF.

5.4.4 Navigation and primary functionalities

Since the public access is an open access interface with infographic, the following images present the navigation information of the website for the water tab, consisting in a visual guide of the tool. In terms of the wastewater tab the navigation is equal.

It starts with the Evolution of water consumption per year, in total volume and per capita, that give a clear view of the amount of water the City of Lisbon needs and its dimension.

Figure 58 Evolution of water consumption of Lisbon per year in total volume

The same data is presented per capita, providing the representativeness of each citizen in the city's demand for water.

Figure 59 Evolution of water consumption of Lisbon per year per capita

The tool then presents a disaggregation of the water consumption by water source, allowing to check the importance of each source.

Figure 60 Evolution of water consumption of Lisbon by water source per year

The indicator per capita is again explored, in which is presented the Evolution of daily average water consumption per capita (total and domestic), a very much used indicator to compare performance between cities.

Figure 61 Evolution of daily average water consumption per capita (total)

Figure 62 Evolution of daily average water consumption per capita (domestic)

The tool also disaggregates the water consumption by type of use per each one of the water sources. This way it's possible to quantify the consumption of the main water uses of the city and also its water sources, as well as evaluate the potential of switching between water source for some uses, contributing to a smart water use and management and leading to a circular economy in the water sector.

WATER CONSUMPTION BY TYPE OF USE

POTABLE WATER | TREATED WASTEWATER | SPRING WATER | GROUNDWATER

53 186 10³m³

Figure 63 Water Consumption by type of use

Due to the high percentage of potable water, the tool also disaggregates the potable water consumption of Lisbon City, presenting the Evolution of annual water consumption by sector in volume.

EVOLUTION OF ANNUAL WATER CONSUMPTION BY SECTOR

Figure 64 Evolution of annual water consumption by sector in volume

This information of the sectors is also presented again, such as Water consumption by sector in percentage. This allows to understand the share of each sector in the total consumption. Additionally, it is possible to see a deeper disaggregation of the non-residential sectors.

WATER CONSUMPTION BY SECTOR

Figure 65 Disaggregation of the total water consumption by sector in %

The following information is only possible to present in the water tab, which is the Water consumption by parish per year, which provides a spatialization of disaggregation of the total volume, residential sector volume and Commerce and industry volume, also possible to have a chart view.

Figure 66 Water consumption by parish administrative area in map view

The private access was also built to be simple to use and to be easily navigated, giving all the versatility to the user watching the information, the data analytics and the downloaded data. The following images present the navigation information of the private access, consisting in a visual guide of the tool.

The images presented contain real data, which were anonymized for a test user.

Dashboard tab

It starts presenting aggregated data by typology of use of the water consumption, as well type of water source and cost. This information (gardens, markets, fireman, etc) can be visualized per month or per year.

Figure 67 Main view of Dashboard

The following image presents the evolution of water consumption of the aggregated typologies of use. This includes the evolution of the typologies of the last 13 months or last 8 years, when watching it per month or per year, respectively.

Figure 68 Example of consumption of previous 13 months of each category

Beside water consumptions and costs, the tool also calculates and presents the energy and carbon footprint associated with the water consumption of each type of use, per month or per year.

Figure 69 Energy and Carbon footprint of the types of use

Additionally, the tool also calculates and presents an evolution of the amount of nutrients recovery, specifically phosphorous, per month or per year.

Figure 70 Evolution of nutrients recovery (Phosphorous)

It is also possible to have a more detailed information of a specific type of use, by seeing the facilities' water consumption associated to each typology of use (gardens in the following case).

Figure 71 Facilities consumption of a specific category

Individual tab

The main view of Individual tab firstly requires the selection of a facility to therefore, provide a set of data analytics to the water consumption of each facility at choice. The selection of a facility is helped by the several filters and related information specified in the search.

Figure 72 Main view of the Individual dashboard presenting all facilities available for the user account.

After the selection of a water meter, it shows the various characteristics of that facility and the evolution of the water consumption and cost, annual and monthly data.

Figure 73 Evolution of annual and monthly water consumption of a selected facility

When the water meter with telemetry is selected, it also shows the evolution of water consumption per day. There are also custom features available with data in different timelines, as well zooming in and out (telemetry only).

Figure 74 Evolution of the daily water consumption of a selected facility

Additionally, for water meters with telemetry, the tool has a deeper consumption analysis, related to a specific selected month, which has set as default the most recent month.

It starts by presenting the comparison of the water consumption in the last 12 months with homologous period. This provides a monthly assessment of evolution of water consumption in the last 24 months and each month.

Figure 75 Comparison of monthly water consumption with homologous period

The analysis proceeds by presenting the evolution of daily data specifying the days of the week. This gives a clear view of the type of day (weekdays, etc) and the minimum, average and maximum water consumption.

Figure 76 Evolution of daily consumption per day of the week

For the water meters with telemetry, which also have available quarter-hour data, the tool presents the average of 24-hour period comparison with previous month and homologous month. There is also a comparison between the current month and the previous month.

Figure 77 Average of 24-hour period comparison with previous month and homologous month of previous year

Another feature of the tool mentioned before, which is a crucial one, is the production of automatic custom performance reports. It only requires the selection of the analysis/graphs desired and PDF is automatically produced with this information.

Figure 78 Selecting graphs for custom report

Following this step, the PDF report is generated, as showed in the following image.

Figure 79 Automatic custom report generated in PDF

User

The User tab function is mainly to manage the logins. Each user has a main login and can create several sub-logins with different levels of access to information, for example to all water meters or only to certain specific water meters.

Figure 80 User tab

Instalações (Facilities)

Finally, the Facilities tab, allows to have access to all the database facilities list. This tab contains a list and characteristics associated to each facility, which can be downloadable to Excel and PDF.

Código local	Código cliente	Designação	Morada	Gestão	Modalidade	Tipo	Sub Tipo	Potável	Ativa	Latitude	Longitude
120827147	180286013	instalação teste 120827147	rua teste 120827147	gestão teste	pro	Jardins	Outro	✓	✓		
141372900	130653014	instalação teste 141372900	rua teste 141372900	gestão teste	plus	garagens	Outro	✓	✓		
150272098	158859471	instalação teste 150272098	rua teste 150272098	gestão teste	pro	Jardins	Outro	✓	✓		
184232099	198333782	instalação teste 184232099	rua teste 184232099	gestão teste	pro	Jardins	Outro	✓	✗		
185379953	163141987	instalação teste 185379953	rua teste 185379953	gestão teste	pro	bombeiros	Outro	✓	✓		
172515640	189992279	instalação teste 172515640	rua teste 172515640	gestão teste	pro	Jardins	Outro	✓	✓		
187731582	166144879	instalação teste 187731582	rua teste 187731582	gestão teste	plus	Jardins	Outro	✓	✗		
144414613	142437780	instalação teste 144414613	rua teste 144414613	gestão teste	plus	cemitérios	Outro	✓	✓		
189072875	137180509	instalação teste 189072875	rua teste 189072875	gestão teste	pro	Jardins	Outro	✓	✓		
158655812	126555402	instalação teste 158655812	rua teste 158655812	gestão teste	pro	chafarizes e bebedouros	Outro	✓	✓		

Figure 81 Facilities database list

5.4.5 Interoperability

The public access is an open access interface which anyone can access and use, as well download all available annual data in CSV format.

The data available for consultation and download refers to the Water and Wastewater data of the city. The Water tab provides for download a CSV file with yearly data of the evolution of the water consumption in Lisbon (total and per capita), disaggregated water consumption by water source, water consumption per capita (total and domestic), water consumption by type of use in each water source, disaggregated potable water consumption between the main sectors (domestic, commerce and industry, central government, institutions, municipal and economic losses). Additionally, the water consumption is presented in a map view (or chart), providing the total consumption, domestic consumption and commerce and industry consumption per parish administrative area.

[DOWNLOAD DATA](#)**Information sources**

CML - Câmara Municipal de Lisboa / DGEG - Direção Geral de Energia e Geologia / APA - Agência Portuguesa do Ambiente / EPAL - Empresa Portuguesa das Águas Livres / AdTA – Águas do Tejo Atlântico / Valorsul - Valorização e Tratamento de Resíduos Sólidos das Regiões de Lisboa e do Oeste

Analyze

Lisboa E-Nova – Agência de Energia e Ambiente de Lisboa

As for the Wastewater tab, it provides for download a CSV file with also yearly data of the evolution of treated wastewater in Lisbon's WWTPs (total and per capita), with a disaggregation of the wastewater treated per WWTP's and also the wastewater generated inside and outside Lisbon.

[DOWNLOAD DATA](#)**Information sources**

CML - Câmara Municipal de Lisboa / DGEG - Direção Geral de Energia e Geologia / APA - Agência Portuguesa do Ambiente / EPAL - Empresa Portuguesa das Águas Livres / AdTA – Águas do Tejo Atlântico / Valorsul - Valorização e Tratamento de Resíduos Sólidos das Regiões de Lisboa e do Oeste

Analyze

Lisboa E-Nova – Agência de Energia e Ambiente de Lisboa

As for the private access an API as developed that can be integrated in external services for interoperability. It is a REST API, which has an authentication system that uses (standard) "Json web token" authentication. Regarding the data format is Json and the used protocol is HTTPS.

The data available to extract directly in the API consists in all the data presented in the front end of the tool. Therefore, the data available in the API is listed below:

- Water consumption of all water meters (yearly and monthly)
- Water cost of all water meters (yearly and monthly)
- Water consumption per type of use (yearly and monthly)
- Water cost per type of use (yearly and monthly)
- Energy and Carbon footprint associated to the water consumption of each type of use (yearly and monthly)
- Annual Energy and Carbon intensity
- Water consumption of potable and non-potable uses
- Water consumption per square meter of irrigation (only for the type of use of gardens)
- Water consumption per water meter (yearly, monthly, daily and quarter-hour)
- Water cost per water meter (yearly and monthly)
- Energy and Carbon footprint associated to the water consumption of each water meter (monthly)
- Water meter local code
- Water meter client code
- Water meter address
- Water meter designation

- Water meter smart metering modality
- Water meter type of water use
- Water meter sub-type of water use (more detailed)
- Water meter organic (i.e. department)
- Water meter potability of water use
- Water meter activity (if it's in use or already deleted)
- Water meter latitude and longitude
- Water meter diameter
- Water costs and taxes

The user can also download data inside in the front end of the tool. There are three tabs where is possible to download the most important data to CSV.

In the first tab, the “Dashboard”, it’s possible to download the water consumption per water meter, providing a list of all water meters of the entity and the respective water consumption, which has the versatility to download yearly or monthly data, allowing to choose the wanted timeline of data. The downloaded CSV contains the water consumption (yearly or monthly), water meter local code, address and a designation (usually the name of the place supplied).

Figure 84 Download example of data of a specific water meter from the Individual tab of the private access of the UWC Observatory

data	hora	consumo	código local
2022-05-01	00:15		2951770
2022-05-01	00:30		2951770
2022-05-01	00:45		2951770
2022-05-01	01:00		2951770
2022-05-01	01:15		2951770
2022-05-01	01:30		2951770
2022-05-01	01:45		2951770
2022-05-01	02:00		2951770
2022-05-01	02:15		2951770
2022-05-01	02:30		2951770

Figure 85 Example of CSV file downloaded from a specific water meter in Individual tab of the private access of the UWC Observatory (water consumption data deleted due to private data)

Finally, the last tab, “*Instalações*” (facilities), it’s possible to download a list of all water meters and all the information associated to it, having the versatility to download it to Excel or PDF. The downloaded document contains the water meter local code, client code, address, designation, smart metering modality, type of water use, sub-type of water use (more detailed), organic (i.e. department), potability of water use, activity of the water meter (if it’s in use or already deleted), latitude and longitude.

Figure 86 Download example of the list of all water meters from the *Instalações* tab of the private access of the UWC Observatory

Código local	Código cliente	Designação	Morada	Gestão	Modalidade	Tipo	Sub Tipo	Orgânica	Potável	Ativa	Latitude	Longitude
CML	home	limpeza		Outro	Outro	FALSO	VERDADEIRO					
CML	home	Outro		Outro	Outro	VERDADEIRO	VERDADEIRO					
CML	home	recintos desportivos e de		Outro	Outro	VERDADEIRO	FALSO					
CML	home	serviços administrativos		Outro	Outro	VERDADEIRO	FALSO					
CML	home	Jardins		Outro	Outro	FALSO	VERDADEIRO					
CML	home	Jardins		Outro	Outro	VERDADEIRO	FALSO					
CML	home	Jardins		Outro	Outro	VERDADEIRO	FALSO					
CML	home	bombeiros		Outro	Outro	VERDADEIRO	FALSO					
CML	home	serviços administrativos		Outro	Outro	VERDADEIRO	FALSO					
CML	home	recintos desportivos e de		Outro	Outro	VERDADEIRO	FALSO					
CML	home	Outro		Outro	Outro	VERDADEIRO	VERDADEIRO					
CML	pro	Jardins		Outro	Outro	FALSO	VERDADEIRO					
CML	home	chafarizes e bebedouros		Outro	Outro	VERDADEIRO	VERDADEIRO					
CML	home	Mercados		Outro	Outro	VERDADEIRO	VERDADEIRO					
CML	home	chafarizes e bebedouros		Outro	Outro	VERDADEIRO	VERDADEIRO					
CML	home	Outro		Outro	Outro	VERDADEIRO	VERDADEIRO					
CML	home	serviços administrativos		Outro	Outro	VERDADEIRO	VERDADEIRO					
CML	home	serviços administrativos		Outro	Outro	VERDADEIRO	VERDADEIRO					
CML	home	Outro		Outro	Outro	VERDADEIRO	FALSO					
CML	home	serviços administrativos		Outro	Outro	VERDADEIRO	VERDADEIRO					
CML	home	limpeza		Outro	Outro	VERDADEIRO	VERDADEIRO					
CML	home	Outro		Outro	Outro	VERDADEIRO	VERDADEIRO					
CML	pro	Jardins		Outro	Outro	FALSO	FALSO					
CML	home	Outro		Outro	Outro	VERDADEIRO	FALSO					
CML	home	bombeiros		Outro	Outro	VERDADEIRO	FALSO					
CML	home	Jardins		Outro	Outro	FALSO	FALSO					
CML	home	limpeza		Outro	Outro	FALSO	VERDADEIRO					
CML	home	Outro		Outro	Outro	VERDADEIRO	VERDADEIRO					
CML	home	serviços administrativos		Outro	Outro	VERDADEIRO	VERDADEIRO					
CML	home	serviços administrativos		Outro	Outro	VERDADEIRO	VERDADEIRO					
CML	home	Outro		Outro	Outro	VERDADEIRO	VERDADEIRO					
CML	plus	recintos desportivos e de		Outro	Outro	VERDADEIRO	VERDADEIRO					
CML	home	limpeza		Outro	Outro	FALSO	VERDADEIRO					
CML	home	limpeza		Outro	Outro	VERDADEIRO	VERDADEIRO					
CML	plus	Jardins		Outro	Outro	FALSO	VERDADEIRO					

Figure 87 Example of CSV file downloaded of the list of all water meters in *Instalações* tab of the private access of the UWC Observatory (latitude and longitude data deleted due to private data)

Additionally, it is possible to download all data analysis presented in the front end, which means that all graphs are downloadable to XLS, CSV, PDF and PNG.

To conclude, in terms of B-WaterSmart interoperability maturity levels both accesses are in level 1, in which the tools have solutions to exchange data (Rest APIs, XLS files, CSV files, PDF and PNG) using non-standardized data structures, such as explained before.

5.4.6 Indicative applications and synergistic benefits

The private access of the UWC Observatory is running and in use by the Lisbon Municipality in the scope of the Lisbon Living Lab.

Additionally, there are two other entities, associated to Lisboa E-Nova, that are using this private access for water, such as the public passenger transport company (buses and trams).

This part of the tool makes use only of digital data, in which some are provided by smart metering, that contains more detailed data and provided with a higher frequency, therefore, much more useful and capable for supporting decision making and management. Therefore, it can be combined with smart metering technology/platforms to enlarge the potential of the tool, which leads to a sustainable water use.

Also making use of the Rest API it is possible to share data in a more expeditious and automatic way. These may lead to the implementation of interoperability examples of this private access tool (#20) with other tools developed inside the B-WaterSmart project, that make use of water consumptions of the municipal water meters and all the information that it's associated to it in the data base, such as the Water-energy- phosphorous balance planning module (#25). It can be combined also with other tools that promote circular economy, since it matches the water consumptions with their uses and therefore, it makes possible to adequate water sources to uses and identify the potential of using alternative water sources.

Complementary to this private access for water, Lisboa E-Nova has developed (outside the scope of B-WaterSmart) a private access for electricity, which as similar functions and navigation, in this case, focused on electricity consumptions, which data is received by FTP. This access for electricity is also running and in use by the Lisbon Municipality and by several other entities, such as Equipment Management and Cultural Entertainment Company, theatres, again a public passenger transport company (buses and trams) and other private entities of public interest. Therefore, there is the possibility to create synergies between other tools with electricity consumptions as well.

Table 12: Applications of UWC observatory out of the B-WaterSmart project

Indicative application of tool	
Title	Lisbon Urban Water Cycle Observatory
Description	The Lisbon Urban Water Cycle Observatory is a data visualization instrument for monitor and communicate performance, support urban planning and decision making, integrated in the sustainability policies of the Lisbon city.

	<p>This UWC Observatory of Lisbon is divided in two complementary tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a public access tool, with open data information of the water and wastewater city dimensions (top-down approach), already with data of the Lisbon city; • a private access tool, for individual entities integrate and analyse, via a set of analytics, the water consumption data of their facilities (bottom-up approach), already with all the water meters of the Lisbon municipality integrated.
Reference point	https://www.google.com/maps/place/Lisboa/@38.7425923,-9.1633032,10959m/data=!3m1!1e3!4m5!3m4!1s0xd19331a61e4f33b:0x400ebbde49036d0!8m2!3d38.7222524!4d-9.1393366?hl=pt-PT
Location	Lisbon
Country (-ies)	Portugal
URL	<p>https://observatorios-lisboa.pt/index.html – Main website of Lisbon Observatories (public access)</p> <p>https://observatorios-lisboa.pt/info_agua.html – Water tab (public access)</p> <p>https://observatorios-lisboa.pt/info_aguasresiduais.html – Wastewater tab (public access)</p>
Project	Not applicable
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water Scarcity, • Untapped efficiency potential of water resources, • Dependent on distant freshwater resources, • Increasing water demand by growing industrial sectors,
Tools/Product/Services	UWC observatory (#20)
Technologies	Resource for Circular Economy
Scales	Local (Private access: water meter scale), City (Public access)
Legislation	Not applicable
Synergistic benefits	“Lisbon Sustainability Policies” – the UWC Observatory of Lisbon is integrated in the Lisbon sustainability policies, monitoring the major water flows (public access) of the city, therefore, provides an accessible, comprehensive and transparent data, that enables the impact monitoring of our behaviour – as individuals and as part of a group – in the quality of life and environment we live and, therefore, continue the path towards the sustainable transition. It also provides an integrated tool for water consumption

	<p>management and data analysis to monitor and evaluate all specific measures implemented in any water meter of the user.</p> <p>“Water Efficiency Programme in the Lisbon Municipality” – the Lisbon municipality together with the support of Lisboa E-Nova, have an internal Water Efficiency Programme since 2015, that have the main objective of reducing the municipal water consumption, which already achieved high water savings with quick-win measures, supported by a very limited monitoring and analysis of water consumption data. Therefore, the UWC Observatory of Lisbon, brings provides an integrated tool for water consumption management and data analysis, supporting decision making and fostering “water smartness for responsible consumers”, which will highly empower the technicians to have a deeper analysis, knowledge and accessibility to data, to better manage water consumption and avoid losses.</p> <p>“Water-Energy-Phosphorous Balance Planning Module (Tool #25)” – the tool #25 may have access to the water consumption data of each specific water meter of the Lisbon Municipality (Lisbon living lab owner), since all the water meters are already integrated in the private access of the UWC Observatory.</p> <p>“API access” – the UWC Observatory of Lisbon private access has available an API to provide water data and allow interoperability with any other tool.</p>
Requirements and conditions	<p>Public access: Water and Wastewater utilities providing annual data of the city water cycle.</p> <p>Private access: Water and Wastewater utilities providing digital data of water meters, regardless the water source (drinking, reclaimed, etc).</p>
Key lessons	<p>Public access:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cities usually don’t have any public and accessible data regarding the urban water cycle that provide information to citizens. • Data is not information. By providing and turning data public to citizens it doesn’t represent cities are providing information to citizens. There is the need to work data to provide it as intelligible data, in a way citizens feel informed. • More than providing data, we must provide information. • The UWC Observatory is starting to be well known by citizens, resident’s associations, ONG’s, etc. • Data is highly used by entities and politicians for communication purposes and for the development of sustainability policies. <p>Private access:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of digital data allowed for a faster and deeper analysis of water consumption, which turned into water savings. • High capacity to identify quick wins as water efficiency measures and quickly repair new water losses.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity of a bottom-up monitoring for users (highly important for municipalities), which provide a deep analysis on their water consumption. • Managers of buildings, green spaces, etc, are not aware of the amount of water spent in their management space. The UWC Observatory comes to fill this gap. • There is a high resistance of the water users to spend and have costs with monitoring, which see it as an investment and fixed cost. However, the use of digital data and high water savings achieved may raise awareness to the water users, since savings in water and reduction in water use related costs (mainly quick-win measures) were immensely superior to the fixed cost of monitoring data. <p>Both accesses:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • You cannot manage without measure it. To have a sustainable management of the water use, in municipalities, entities, etc, throughout all the levels, from political to operational, there is the need to have an available monitoring of the water use. • Having a Monitoring and performance communication with a top-down approach with the public access and also a bottom-up approach with the private access (with special emphasis on the Lisbon Municipality), which if it was massively used by water consumers in Lisbon, would pave the way to reach the same data as the top-down approach. Therefore, by having both approaches of monitoring, it allows to have a better and deeper understanding on the city's water use, as well a better monitoring of any kind of policies or measures implemented.
Organisations	Lisboa E-Nova and Lisbon Municipality
Contact persons	<p>Public access:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rui Mendes: ruimendes@lisboaenova.org • Rui Dinis: ruidinis@lisboaenova.org • observatorios@lisboaenova.org • info@lisboaenova.org <p>Private access:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • info@lisboaenova.org • Rui Mendes: ruimendes@lisboaenova.org
Data Manager	Rui Mendes: ruimendes@lisboaenova.org
Costs	Public access: no costs for using the public access of the Urban Water Cycle Observatory of Lisbon and download available data.

	Private access: no costs for the Lisboa E-Nova associated entities (including Lisbon Municipality – Lisbon living lab owner) and private institutions of public interest.
Tags	<p>Creative data to build awareness, engage and empower citizens</p> <p>Better-informed society</p> <p>Transparent and accessible information</p> <p>Water smartness for responsible consumers</p> <p>Sustainable water use</p> <p>Improve water efficiency</p> <p>Data analysis</p>
Publications/Reference	<p>https://lisboaenova.org/relancamento-dos-observatorios-lisboa/</p> <p>https://lisboaenova.org/lancamento-da-nova-versao-da-plataforma-observatorios-lisboa/</p> <p>https://lisboaenova.org/atualizacao-dos-observatorios-lisboa-o-que-cada-um-de-nos-consume-produz-e-emite/</p> <p>https://www.lisboa.pt/capital-verde-2020/noticias/detalhe/relancamento-dos-observatorios-de-lisboa</p> <p>https://www.lisboa.pt/cidade/ambiente/qualidade-ambiental/agua</p> <p>https://www.adene.pt/camara-municipal-de-lisboa-distingue-adene-pela-cooperacao-no-portal-observatorios-lisboa/</p>
Images	<p>Public access:</p> <p>https://observatorios-lisboa.pt/index.html – Main website of Lisbon Observatories (public access)</p> <p>https://observatorios-lisboa.pt/info_agua.html – Water tab (public access)</p> <p>https://observatorios-lisboa.pt/info_aguasresiduais.html – Wastewater tab (public access)</p> <p>Private access:</p>

Dashboard view of the private access

Individual view of detailed analysis to a specific water meter

Caption/Source

See above

5.4.7 Accessing tool and test data

The public access is free and also has a specific email for any kind of contact, questions, clarifications, possible cooperation or synergies, etc. Therefore it can be accessed in the following three links:

<https://observatorios-lisboa.pt/index.html> - Main website of Lisbon Observatories (public access)

https://observatorios-lisboa.pt/info_agua.html - Water tab (public access)

https://observatorios-lisboa.pt/info_aguasresiduais.html - Wastewater tab (public access)

The private access is available upon request to the email of the tool (info@lisboaenova.org) or the contact point mentioned above, and via the following link:

<https://privado.observatorios-lisboa.pt/login> - Private access

5.5 Stormwater reuse management system (#21)

5.5.1 Tool description and attributes

The stormwater reuse management system developed in T3.4 allows the combination of operational management of a stormwater tank and a connected subirrigation system for groundwater recharge and direct irrigation with the overall objective of reducing water scarcity in spaces in or close to urbanised areas.

AQUAFIN investigates innovative control concepts to actively manage existing rainwater infrastructure using short-term weather forecasts, IoT data communication and reliable control technology to unlock new applications for otherwise lost rainwater. The technology is being tested on a stormwater basin equipped with a controllable sluice. Based on the system state and weather forecasts the sluice is controlled to optimise system performance for the conflictive objectives of maximising stormwater-reuse potential and minimising negative impacts on buffer capacity.

VITO focuses on the development of tools for the operational optimisation of a subirrigation system fed by water stemming from the stormwater tank. The focus of the application developed in the LL is on agricultural water re-use through a subirrigation system. Potential additional users may include municipal services in need of water, e.g., for watering local parks & lawns, farmers in close vicinity fetching water, or industry.

The stormwater reuse management system is designed as a cloud-based set of control algorithms with on-premise edge-device-based local control acting as a fallback. During B-WaterSmart, the system is installed in the Aquafin cloud-environment. All modules of the control are designed in python, local control is implemented in either python and structured text defined by IEC 61131.

Figure 88 provides a concept sketch of the stormwater reuse management system:

- a) conventional stormwater system: buffering stormwater during rain event, empty during dry weather.
- b) stormwater reuse management system: stormwater tank retrofitted with valve controlled based on rainfall forecasts. Buffering during rain event, providing reuse water during dry weather, e.g., for agricultural or industrial use.

Figure 88 Concept sketch of the stormwater reuse management system

Table 13 collects the above information about tool's attributes and descriptions in a tabular format to be used for the update of the detailed page of the tool (if needed) in the Water Europe Marketplace of T7.1. The detailed page of the tool can be accessed via the following URL: <https://mp.watereurope.eu/d/Product/63>

Table 13: Stormwater reuse management system's attributes and description

Tool's attribute	Description
Type of product	A methodology or a process related with the Circular Economy
Name	Stormwater reuse system for agriculture
Description	Technology demonstration of urban stormwater reuse for agriculture, introducing alternative water resources for irrigation. Development of a management tool to control

	water level in the basin and optimal distribution to the irrigation system based on water level, water demand, and weather prediction of precipitation/ storm events.
Abbreviation	NA
URL	For more information or a demo, contact Stefan.kroll@aquafin.be .
Costs	To be decided.
Target audience	(Waste)water operators (as a product to install) Farmers (as a service)
Actors, roles and interactions	(Waste)water utilities provide reuse water to farmers, municipalities and industry in need of water. The initiative for installation can come from the utility, but in practice it will probably best come from a municipality, a sector organisation, a cooperative of farmers, etc. (i.e. some party on the water demand side).
Unique selling points /Added Value/Innovation	Buffer infrastructure will be extended by a novel functionality in that the designed control system will enable it to serve as source of water in reuse concepts while maintaining its buffer capacity
TRL	Currently TRL 6 The evolution of tool #21 through to higher TRL's is completely linked to the progress of the WP2 technology #5. As described in the 2nd periodic report, technology #5 is delayed. However, behind the scenes a lot of work is already done to smoothen the transition of #21 to the demo scale. TRL 7 will be reached by the end of 2023.
Technical requirements	Not applicable, the service is currently designed to run on AQF & VITO infrastructure
Environment	Microsoft Azure (cloud environment) Linux on edge device
Version	Not applicable
Initial release	Not applicable
License type	Not applicable, the service is currently designed to run on AQF & VITO infrastructure
Programming language/technologies used	Python +IEC 61131-defined structured text for data communication between PLC-module of the device and the Python-based algorithm for local control
Open interface	Not applicable
Graphical User Interface / Headless software	Not applicable
Supported spatial scales	Neighbourhood-province
Supported temporal scales	Real-time, using forecast data of several hours
Water Use Types	Urban, agriculture
Compatibility with FIWARE	Not supported

Organisations	AQUAFIN, VITO
Contact details	Stefan Kroll (stefan.kroll@aquafin.be), Birte Raes (birte.raes@aquafin.be); Ingeborg Joris (ingeborg.joris@vito.be), Frie Van Bauwel (frie.vanbauwel@vito.be)
Data Manager	Birte Raes (birte.raes@aquafin.be)
Technologies	Urban Water buffer
Tags	stormwater, buffer, rainwater harvesting
Images	<p>The diagram illustrates two scenarios of stormwater management. At the top, a sun icon represents dry weather and a cloud with rain represents a rain event. Scenario (a) shows a conventional system: during a rain event, a tank fills with water; during dry weather, the tank is empty. Scenario (b) shows a system with a valve controlled by rainfall forecasts: during a rain event, the tank fills; during dry weather, the valve opens, allowing water to be reused for agricultural or industrial purposes, represented by icons of a truck, tractor, factory, and watering can.</p>
Caption/Source	Concept sketch of the stormwater reuse management system. a) conventional stormwater system: buffering stormwater during rain event, empty during dry weather. b) stormwater reuse management system: stormwater tank retrofitted with valve controlled based on rainfall forecasts. Buffering during rain event, Providing reuse water during dry weather, e.g., for agricultural or industrial use.
Publications	-

5.5.2 Pre-existing background

The solution has no pre-existing background and is being developed within the B-WaterSmart project.

5.5.3 Developments and advancements within the project

The stormwater reuse management system is designed as a modular system. A cloud-based service (Databricks job implemented in Python) acts as central component automatically ingesting rainfall-forecasts from external data sources (free or commercial). These data are converted into a timeseries format (Pandas), analysed in real-time and used as a basis for the decision whether to evacuate the controlled stormwater tank. This is done through the determination of setpoints for the water level in the tank in order to guarantee safe operation of the tank. The setpoints are communicated (protocol currently used in test-phase: MQTT) to the edge controller of the stormwater tank. Control messages issued by the cloud service and monitoring data sent by the edge device to the cloud are logged in their raw format (json). A more manageable cloud storage solution is still under consideration. Communication failure is monitored and reported based on simple timestamp watchdogs. Setpoint tracking is done through local control of the opening of the tank's valve. Both central and local control are designed in Python. As the current concept for hardware integration requires, local control is implemented in Python, but supported by a communication module written in IEC 61131-defined structured text running on the PLC module of the device. For future upscaling of the stormwater management control to other locations, all programming code on the edge device is kept as generic as possible for reduced hardware configuration efforts. The actual development of the tool is completed, but as part of the demonstration in combination with the stormwater infrastructure, further optimization and integration of demo-specific subparts is still ongoing.

Data on the water demand for other users is generated from real-time sensor data on groundwater levels in the field, and precipitation of the past 10 days from a local weather station. The crop-type is also included in determining the water demand of the user. Next to defining the water demand, water availability is calculated based on real-time data acquired from Aquafin. Moreover, Aquafin provides the predicted excess water volumes that need to be evacuated. Based on the water demand of the different users, the water availability, and the possible need for evacuating water, the subirrigation scheme is calculated and executed. The estimated amount of water that is predicted to be evacuated through the subirrigation, is communicated to the Aquafin algorithm. Communications between VITO and Aquafin go through an API developed by VITO. In case of technical failures, emergencies or freezing, alarms and possibilities to override the algorithm are built-in.

The system regulating the subirrigation part of the stormwater reuse management system, is developed using Python. The calculations of the water demand, the water availability and the subirrigation scheme are in a testing phase. The API for communication between Aquafin and VITO, the deployment in the cloud and the communication to the local hardware are under development.

5.5.4 Navigation and primary functionalities

The hardware consists of three PLC's at the location that are interconnected physically (cable types still to be decided). At first there is a Siemens PLC 1500 controlling the sluice through an Auma motor, based on a setpoint from the stormwater management tool and offering an HMI to the operators. At second there is a PLC Next providing the basin control part of the stormwater management tool both through cloud communication and through a local fallback control. At third there is a PLC for controlling the subirrigation system, the hardware supplier for this PLC will be Crodeon.

5.5.5 Interoperability

Data communication between the components designed by Aquafin and Vito is under development. Based on the design of the control algorithms the data that are to be exchanged between the individual partners of this case have been identified. The configuration of the API itself is currently ongoing. API- or broker-based interoperability with other cases or the public is currently out of scope. Additionally, FIWARE compatibility is not supported.

5.5.6 Indicative applications and synergistic benefits

The tool is developed in close collaboration with the technology #5 on stormwater reuse for irrigation, and forms an integrated and essential part of the pilot system.

The stormwater management tool helps in boosting value creation around water. As demonstrated in technology #5 (Urban stormwater reuse for agriculture), when integrated with innovative infrastructure, it contributes to ensure water for relevant users and to safeguarding ecosystems (i.e. ground water reserves) and it therefore is a potential instrument in developing innovative governance systems.

The data from the stormwater management tool with regards to e.g., system specifications, efficiency and predicted available water volumes will provide input for the UWOT modelling and regional analysis in LL Flanders.

5.5.7 Accessing the tool and test data

Not applicable since the scope of this tool is not to share data with a large group or anyone not involved in the case. The goal of this tool is to be a control algorithm applied by VITO and Aquafin. Tests are carried out internally in a modular fashion with each project partner testing and validating their internal code. A limited test-dataset has been made available for Vito by Aquafin.

As the final product is a full-scale application of the stormwater system, tests to failure are not envisaged as part of this case. There will be no virtual data required for testing the full-scale application, tests of system functionality are carried out by means of manually controlled test runs. These tests are carried out among the project partners.

In order to access the tool, please refer to the following contacts: Stefan Kroll (stefan.kroll@aquafin.be), Birte Raes (birte.raes@aquafin.be); Ingeborg Joris (ingeborg.joris@vito.be), Frie Van Bauwel (frie.vanbauwel@vito.be).

5.5.8 Application of the tool and lesson extracted

Please refer to D3.5, Section 6 for details about the application of tool #21 at the Flanders LL and about lesson extracted.

5.6 Nessie System (#29)

5.6.1 Tool description and attributes

Nessie is a complete digital solution developed by ICCS/NTUA for the collection, harmonization, processing, storing and visualisation of big amounts of high-resolution data from any IoT agents and 3rd party client applications, such as web applications, sensors, smart meters etc. Nessie currently provides a series of built-in analytics to support, among others, forecasts, anomaly detection and alerting, optimization of urban systems, advice provision, as well as some more case-specific functionalities, e.g., hydraulic simulation of open-channel systems, modelling of wastewater treatment processes. Further to built-in features, external analytics can be integrated seamlessly with Nessie, to consume data, via its API features, which are continuously being upgraded.

An overview of the Nessie system, and its components, is given in next figure.

Figure 89: Components of Nessie platform and data exchange with clients

Nessie Engine is composed by a Web Server and a Geolocation-aware Database. The Web server provides a means (application programming interfaces-API) through which 3rd party clients can insert, update, and retrieve data. Data can be either temporal (e.g., time-series) or non-temporal (e.g., a parameter set provided by an AI algorithm). The engine is responsible for receiving the data (included in the http request body), processing and storing them. It also provides a way to link data together (e.g., as in the case of an entity-relationship structure) and retrieve the data in a standard fashion using URNs.

The Web Server is responsible to authenticate the user, process the request and communicate with the database in order to store, update and retrieve data. All user HTTP

requests are served to the user by JSON objects, and all HTTP requests must comply with the RESTful notation. Some of the Web Server’s main components include:

- NginX Web Proxy
- Gunicorn Python Web Server
- Python/Django Framework
- Memcache daemon
- REST Application Framework
- Data analysis Layer (Pandas/NumPy)

The database server is a PostgreSQL (version 12) running with GIS support, which allows for geographical queries to be executed. PostgreSQL is a fast, reliable, and more robust solution than other open source (and free) database alternatives. It can be optimized quite easily and is replication-ready out of the box. Another advantage of PostgreSQL is the fact that it is licensed under BSD, which provides great flexibility in the utilization of the service.

Table 14 below includes information about tool’s attributes and descriptions in a tabular format to be used for the update of the Water Europe Marketplace of T7.1, if needed. The detailed page of the tool can be accessed via the following URL: <https://mp.watereurope.eu/d/Product/27>.

Table 14: Nessie system’s attributes and description

Tool’s attribute	Description
Type of product	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A software supporting the Circular Economy • A hardware product or a technological device around the Circular Economy • A service, offered as part of a Circular Economy enabling portfolio • A methodology or a process related with the Circular Economy
Name	Nessie system
Description	Nessie platform is an information system, developed within ICCS/NTUA, able to acquire, process and store, and in general to manage, high-resolution data from IoT agents, such as sensors and smart meters, coupled with analytics (to translate the data into information) and visualisation capabilities to present the information to the end-users.
Abbreviation	Nessie
URL	https://uwmh.eu/products/84-nessie-system.html https://mp.watereurope.eu/d/Product/27
Costs	Software is available for research purposes free of charge on a time limited license. For commercial purposes there are commercial agreement options.
Target audience	Nessie primarily targets water utilities, industries, technology providers, end-users, householders to get access, analyse and visualise real-time data from IoT agents.
Actors, roles and interactions	Technology providers and water utilities to give access to real-time data collected from smart meters. Householders and water utilities to get access, analyse and visualise data through the dashboard.

Unique selling points /Added Value/Innovation	In Bodo case, a web application will be developed to enable householders to monitor water consumption at the household level, using real-time data from smart meters. The application will integrate seamlessly with third-party algorithms and analytics, which continuously fed with data from smart meters, e.g., for the detection of leakages and bursts if available. Other possible analytics are: 1) the analysis and comparison with past consumption data of the household, 2) the comparison with the water consumption of other households with similar socio-demographic characteristics, 3) the analysis of total consumption per appliance, 4) the forecast of future consumptions and bills.
TRL	Level 7
Technical requirements	<p>Minimum technical requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Python version v2.8 • Django Web Application Framework v2.2 • Pandas Data Analysis Library for Python (for time-series data manipulation) v0.24 • NumPy (scientific computing library for Python) v1.18 • REST Framework for greater portability and easier maintenance 3.11. • GIS-ENABLED PostgreSQL (v>9.5) <p>For the end-users of the product, a browser to interact with the dashboard is required.</p>
Environment	Linux for development of the system. Any environment that supports a browser for the end-users.
Version	Not applicable
Initial release	2016
License type	Software is available for research purposes free of charge on a time limited license. For commercial purposes there are commercial agreement options.
Programming language/technologies used	Python, Unicorn/Python WSGI HTTP Server for UNIX and the NginX reverse proxy server. PostgreSQL v12, PostGIS
Open interface	Nessie has API features to interface with 3rd party systems, as well as through FIWARE ORION-LD Context Broker and FIWARE DRACO Enabler via IT connectors.
Graphical User Interface / Headless software	The tool has a user interface (dashboard) through which the end-user interacts.
Supported spatial scales	Single point measurements from IoT agents and meters.
Supported temporal scales	Any temporal scale, depending on the temporal resolution of measurements.
Water Use Types	Urban
Compatibility with FIWARE	Nessie is a FIWARE-compliant system: through existing IT connectors interact with FIWARE ORION-LD Context Broker and FIWARE DRACO Enabler.
Organisations	ICCS/NTUA
Contact details	Christos Makropoulos (cmakro@mail.ntua.gr) Panagiotis Kossieris (pkossier@mail.ntua.gr) Christos Pantazis (xpanta@outlook.gr)

Data Manager	Stavroula Manouri (stavroula.manouri@gmail.com)
Technologies	Any system comprising IoT agents, sensors, and meters, as well as third-party algorithms and analytics.
Tags	Circularity, circular economy, efficiency, smart metering, digital solution, real-time monitoring, decision making
Images	
Caption/Source	NESSIE platform : A visualisation and analytics platform able to acquire, process and store high-resolution data from IoT (incl. sensors and smart meters).
Publications	<p>Kossieris, P., Pantazis, C., Makropoulos, C., 2021. Data-models for FIWARE-enabled smart applications for raw-water supply system modelling, management and operation. <i>Advances in Hydroinformatics: SIMHYDRO 2021, SimHydro 6th International Conference</i>, June 16 – 18 2021 (in press).</p> <p>Makropoulos, C., Kossieris, P., Kozanis, S., Katsiri, E., Vamvakeridou-Lyroudia, L., 2014. From smart meters to smart decisions: web-based support for the water efficient household. <i>11th International Conference on Hydroinformatics, Proceedings HIC2014</i>, 17-21 August 2014, New York, USA, 2014.</p> <p>Kossieris, P., Panayiotakis, A., Tzouka, K., Gerakopoulou, P., Rozos, E., Makropoulos, C., 2014. An eLearning Approach for Improving Household Water Efficiency. <i>Procedia Engineering</i>, 89, 1113–1119. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2014.11.232.</p> <p>Kossieris, P., Kozanis, S., Hashmi, A., Katsiri, E., Vamvakeridou-Lyroudia, L.S., Farmani, R., Makropoulos, C., Savic, D., 2014. A Web-based Platform for Water Efficient Households. <i>Procedia Engineering</i>, 89, 1128–1135. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2014.11.234.</p>

5.6.2 Pre-existing background

Nessie system has been developed, and is evolving continuously, throughout EU-funded projects, such as iWIDGET, SUBSOL, Dessin and Fiware4Water project, to meet different requirements. Nessie has been deployed in a range of smart monitoring and control contexts. The very first version of Nessie was developed in the framework of iWIDGET project (2012 - 2015) to enable householders and water utilities to monitor, analyse and get advice on water consumption, using real-time measurements from smart water meters. In the framework of SUBSOL project, a new user interface was developed to support real-time monitoring and control of Sewer Mining Units, using real-time quality data from low-energy field sensors.

Nessie system was further upgraded with more advanced functionalities within SUBSOL project where the key requirement was the development of a transferable dashboard for the remote monitoring and management of Subsurface Water System. A customizable dashboard was developed through which the user can select the widgets of interest. These widgets can be customised on the fly according to specific needs, while the end-user has the option to preview the widgets before adding them to the dashboard. Recently, in the framework of Fiware4Water project, the Nessie system was deployed to support the real-time monitoring, management and control of the external conveyance system of EYDAP (the largest water utility in Greece serving the city of Athens), integrating more than 70 flow and quality sensors into a common system. Two distinct web home pages were developed under the same web dashboard to host flow and quality aspects of the system. To integrate Nessie with FIWARE, different IT connectors have been developed to establish communication with ORION-LD Context Broker and FIWARE DRACO Enabler. Indicative screenshots of Nessie's dashboard in the above-mentioned contexts are given the figure below.

Figure 90: Indicative examples of Nessie's dashboards from past implementations.

Figure 91: Nessie system supporting the real-time monitoring, management and control of the external conveyance system of EYDAP.

5.6.3 Developments and advancements within the project

In the framework of BWS, Nessie system (tool #29) is being expanded to meet the requirements and needs of the Bodø case, focusing on the development of a digital platform that allows householders to monitor and manage the water consumption of their household. Building on experience from the iWIDGET project, Nessie system has been customised, evolved and enhanced to support the fast, reliable, interoperable and real-time retrieval of high-resolution data, their processing and communication to third-party systems, as well as their presentation to the end-users via a new dashboard. In the context of B-WaterSmart, we go one step further and we are developing the new generation of Nessie, called “Nessie as a Service (NaaS)”, to allow the seamless integration of Nessie core system with external systems, developed by third-party entities, through a flexible state-of-art API. Apart from the functionalities that allow the different data sources and third-party models/algorithms to communicate with the core Nessie platform, NaaS allows to create entire environments managed by third-parties partners. Additionally, a fully upgraded new user-interface has been developed, comprising fully customisable dashboard features, easily adjusted by the householder (selection of type of data to be presented, selection of the visual display, selection of advanced widgets etc). The new system has been implemented in the context of FIWARE standard, establishing communication with FIWARE Context Broker (i.e., Orion or Stelio) to consume data according to NGSI-V2 & NGSI-LD requests. The above new technology is implemented in the Bodø case to retrieve data from smart meters, integrate Nessie with the new analytics/applications that are being developed (e.g., tool for the detection of leakages and bursts developed by NTNU) and customise the dashboard to the peculiarities to Bodø’s end-users (householders).

The major B-WaterSmart developments with regard to Nessie are described in more detail in Sections 5.6.4 to 5.6.6 that follow.

5.6.4 Service based operations (Nessie as a Service)

As discussed above, a key development in the context of B-WaterSmart with respect to Nessie is its transformation from a *close system* to an “*as a service system*”. Nessie as a Service (NaaS) supports the seamless integration of third-party developers to develop an entire environment. Specifically, it allows a third-party developer to:

- Create update and remove users,
- Create, update, delete devices, sensors, and smart meters,
- Assign devices, sensors, or smart meters to new users,
- Create simulation scenarios for AI algorithms to process and store their results,
- Insert real-time data,
- Retrieve real-time or historical aggregated data.

In a technical level, Nessie as a Service (NaaS) is the implementation of Nessie’s RESTful API that has been developed, so that third party applications can perform CRUD operations on Nessie’s Database. Nessie’s RESTful API uses HTTP methods, such as GET, POST,

PUT, and DELETE, to perform operations on its resources (Sensors, Sensor's time series data etc) identified by unique URLs, known as endpoints. The API focuses on representing the state of these resources and allows clients to access and manipulate them using simple and intuitive HTTP requests. By adhering to REST principles, a RESTful API promotes scalability, modularity, and interoperability, making it an efficient and widely adopted solution for building distributed systems. In addition, NaaS supports the messaging pattern pub/sub, short for publish/subscribe, which enables the seamless processing and dissemination of data, ensuring that insights are delivered promptly to the appropriate recipients for immediate action. On top of those functionalities, there is an authentication/authorization layer which ensures and secures the data integrity and safety.

In the context of Bodo case, NaaS is being deployed to retrieve, store and make data available to third-party developers (e.g., NTNU), as well as consume data from them.

5.6.5 FIWARE compatibility

Nessie as a Service (NaaS) was developed so that the system can communicate with the external world using API queries in order to:

- Create data,
- Update data,
- Retrieve data.

Also, since Nessie is FIWARE compatible it can receive and transmit IoT messages through a FIWARE enabled Context Broker, such as ORION-LD. Although NaaS operates under both NGSI-v2 and NGSI-LD specifications, we prefer using the NGSI-LD since it is an upgrade from NGSI-v2.

The NGSI-v2 protocol is a RESTful protocol that is used for exchanging context information between IoT devices and the context broker. It is built on top of HTTP and JSON and provides a standard interface for all IoT interactions at the context information management level. The protocol is used for context broker interactions and all interactions beneath this port occur using the native protocol of the attached devices. NGSI-v2 is preferred over NGSI-v1 because it provides more functionality such as subscriptions, pagination, and filtering.

On the other hand, NGSI-LD specification enhances NGSI-v2 by providing a means to interconnect and link entities and properties with each other. More specifically, the main differences between NGSI-v2 and NGSI-LD are that the underlying data model is the Property Graph Data Model and entity IDs shall be URIs (URLs or URNs) in NGSI-LD. NGSI-LD is an information model and API for publishing, querying, and subscribing to context information. It is meant to facilitate the open exchange and sharing of structured information between different stakeholders. Much like JSON-LD being JSON plus linked data concepts, NGSI-LD is NGSI-v2 plus linked data concepts.

In order for Nessie as a Service to be an IoT-ready application and handle IoT-compliant real-time messages, ORION-LD context broker has been selected. One of the various Context

Brokers supported by the FIWARE foundation. ORION-LD is a context broker and a vital building block for context data management which supports both the NGSI-LD and the NGSI-v2 APIs. It is currently a fork of the original Orion Context Broker extending support to add NGSI-LD and linked data concepts. ORION-LD implements the NGSI-LD API. It is also an NGSI-LD publish/subscribe broker.

ORION-LD must be installed along with a document-based database such as MongoDB which is used to save subscription information. MongoDB is a general-purpose database that can provide many benefits to your application development processes. It can help in building applications that are more future proof with its scaling capabilities and flexible schema. The main reason for using a document-based database to save information is the flexibility that such a database offers. Developers may describe any conceptual interpretation of the project's ontological schema and use this as a basis for the necessary publish/subscribe information. So as to enable subscribers to be notified when needed.

Optionally, FIWARE Draco enabler may be used to keep historical data. FIWARE Draco is a system that processes and distributes data. It is part of the Core Context Management Chapter of FIWARE. Internally, Draco is based on Apache NiFi, which is a dataflow system based on the concepts of flow-based programming. It supports powerful and scalable directed graphs of data routing, transformation, and system mediation logic. Data consumed by FIWARE Draco as stored on a PostgreSQL database for historical and analytical use.

5.6.6 User Interface

In the context of B-WaterSmart, a new user interface has been developed with various new features that allow end-users to create their own custom dashboards by selecting different widgets for various purposes. Based on the latest developments, the GUI is interactive and responsive so as to make the user experience better. The following figure (Figure 92) depicts the main administrator and user functionality.

Figure 92: Nessie as a Service – main data model

Nessie allows for three types of users. Project administrators, standard users, and viewers:

Project administrators are assigned by the project leaders in collaboration with our team. They can create, update, or delete other users (standard users or viewers) and they can assign data sources (either sensors, smart meters, or other kind of an external data source such as a 3rd party API) to each user.

Standard Users can login with the credentials given to them by the project administrators and create custom dashboards that satisfy their needs. Accordingly, users can assign different widgets to each dashboard. Each widget must be combined with a certain data source, such as the real-time values of a smart meter for example.

Viewers can only be created by the project administrators and can only be given permission to observe or survey certain data sources in real-time. Viewers cannot create dashboards or assign widgets to dashboards. A viewer can be a 3rd party application, an API consumer, a person related in some way to a standard user that needs to keep track of some sensor information. Viewers can only access the API or be allowed to subscribe to ORION-LD for receiving push notifications.

Standard users log in with the credentials given to them by the project administrator, and are immediately presented by a quick view of the smart meters or sensors that had been previously assigned to them. Then, the users can start creating different dashboards and select different measurements to be displayed at each dashboard. Data on the dashboards are real-time and graphs and values are automatically updated thanks to the FIWARE enabled architecture and Nessie as a Service configuration and setup.

Currently the following widgets are supported: Graphs with lines or bars, single numbers (e.g., total consumption), percentage bars, table with quick view of all the sensors or smart meters most recent values, and ratios between a sensor's timeseries and a single number (e.g., hourly consumption vs previous year's daily average consumption). Nessie as a Service can keep historical data in its database, so users can view and compare historical data between different sensors or smart meters. Users can also create aggregated data depictions, such as hourly, daily, weekly, monthly, and yearly values, all on a timely fashion (Figure 93 shows some of the widgets that are currently supported).

Future widgets may include, boxplot graphs, spider graphs, Sankey diagrams, heatmaps, various gauges, and maps with geolocation data.

Figure 93: Indicative widgets that a user can add to their own dashboard.

5.6.7 Advanced Analytic

Further to the above-described functionalities, the on-line dashboard will enable end-users to obtain information on their per use (per appliance) consumption of their household, allowing them to detect, and hopefully change, inefficient domestic water uses. To accomplish this, an advanced analytic is being developed to break down (disaggregate) the total water consumptions, as measured by the installed smart water meters, into the various water-related uses (e.g., taps, washing machine, dishwasher, garden irrigation) in the household. Here, we adopt a non-immersive approach, and we address the water consumption break down challenge algorithmically. Specifically, we build and assess machine learning models to classify water consumption measurements into the different uses. Both supervised and unsupervised techniques are studied and compared to select the proper one, while both water-use parameters (i.e., intensity, duration, time of occurrence) as well as additional explanatory variables (e.g., temporal dynamics of water demand, time of the year, total daily consumptions) are used as predictors that feed the models. When data from the smart water meters become available, the analytic will be tested and aligned for the LL.

5.6.8 Navigation and primary functionalities

As discussed above, the products of third-party clients (e.g., data from smart meters or outcomes of an algorithm/analytic) become available to the end-users via a dashboard. The

dashboard can be accessed via any web browser. Indicative examples of user interface of Nessie, developed to support different monitoring and control systems, are given in section 5.6.2. Depending on the requirements of each case, Nessie provides different functionalities with respect to analytics encompassed. For the purpose of the B-WateSmart project, Nessie aims at assisting in better information at a householder level (e.g., flow, pressure, temperature) from smart-metering data. Based on that data, end users will be able to detect leaks and they will be supported in the demand management of water resources at a household level while raising awareness in water demand patterns and consumption. Generic features, which can be met in almost all cases, are the monitoring of real-time data from IoT agents, provision of overview intuitive information, access to historical data and their statistical comparative analysis. These analytics are provided to the end-users via the dashboard, as highlighted in the figures below (Figure 94, Figure 95, Figure 96).

Figure 94: Overview of latest measurements from sensors.

Figure 95: Comparison of measurements on the basis of common axis graphs.

Figure 96: Comparison of statistical characteristics of selected properties, along with box plots.

Sensor	Value	Timestamp
IW_GRE_18_005E4F/WaterCold	0.0001	2015-12-01 22:45
IW_GRE_19_006053/WaterCold	0.0003	2015-12-01 22:45
IW_GRE_19_006053/Electricity	0	2015-12-01 22:45
IW_GRE_7_059E14/WaterCold	0	2015-12-01 22:45

Figure 97: Table of most recent measurements and an interactive graph from the user dashboard.

5.6.9 Interoperability

As discussed above, FIWARE-enabled IT connectors have been developed to support the communication of Nessie with ORION-LD Context Broker and the FIWARE DRACO Enabler to enable the consumption of real-time data as well as the persistent storage of historical data. An implementation of Nessie system in a FIWARE-enabled context, is provided in the Figure 98 below (FIWARE components are indicated with blue borders).

Figure 98: A FIWARE-enabled system architecture implemented to integrate Nessie with FIWARE.

5.6.10 Indicative applications and synergistic benefits

As discussed above, Nessie system has been used in the development of digital services. Here, we focus on such a service that is highly relevant with Bobo demo case. This is the web platform developed in the framework of iWIDGET project to enable householders and water utilities to monitor, analyse and get advice on water consumption, using real-time measurements from smart water meters.

Table 15: Applications of the Nessie system (#29) out of the B-WaterSmart project

Indicative application of tool	
Title	iWIDGET project – householder platform
Description	In this case a web platform was developed to enable householders to monitor, analyse and get advice on water consumption, using real-time measurements from smart water meters.
Reference point	Athens demo case, UK demo case, Portugal demo case
Location	Athens demo case, South of England demo case, Lisbon demo case
Country (-ies)	Greece, South of England, Portugal
URL	http://www.i-widget.eu/ (the link is no longer active since the i-Widget project ended in 2015. Information about this can be accessed in the following publication: Savić, D., L. Vamvakeridou-Lyroudia, and Zoran Kapelan. "Smart meters, smart water, smart societies: The iWIDGET project." <i>Procedia Engineering</i> 89 (2014): 1105-1112 which is available via the below link: https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877705814023467
Project	iWIDGET
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High drinking water demand due to dense or growing resident population and economy, • Improve water efficiency
Tools/Product/Services	Nessie system (#29)
Technologies	Smart water meters
Scales	At residential level
Legislation	not applicable
Synergistic benefits	Integration of third-party software (a data-driven approach to forecast annual water bill) with Nessie that provides to third-party software a user-interface with the end-user (householder) as part of a complete monitoring solution.
Requirements and conditions	A key requirement is the existence of smart water meter in a household.
Key lessons	This case provides a leaving paradigm of a digital solution targeting directly the end-users (householders) and demonstrates the feasibility and efficiency of such solutions.
Organisations	Water utilities of 3 demo cases and research partners.
Contact persons	Christos Makropoulos (cmakro@mail.ntua.gr) Panagiotis Kossieris (pkossier@mail.ntua.gr)
Data Manager	Panagiotis Kossieris (pkossier@mail.ntua.gr)

Costs	-
Tags	Water efficiency, smart metering, digital solution, real-time monitoring, decision making, support end-user
Publications/Reference	<p>Makropoulos, C., Kossieris, P., Kozanis, S., Katsiri, E., Vamvakeridou-Lyroudia, L., 2014. From smart meters to smart decisions: web-based support for the water efficient household. 11th International Conference on Hydroinformatics, Proceedings HIC2014, 17-21 August 2014, New York, USA, 2014.</p> <p>Kossieris, P., Panayiotakis, A., Tzouka, K., Gerakopoulou, P., Rozos, E., Makropoulos, C., 2014. An eLearning Approach for Improving Household Water Efficiency. <i>Procedia Engineering</i>, 89, 1113–1119. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2014.11.232.</p> <p>Kossieris, P., Kozanis, S., Hashmi, A., Katsiri, E., Vamvakeridou-Lyroudia, L.S., Farmani, R., Makropoulos, C., Savic, D., 2014. A Web-based Platform for Water Efficient Households. <i>Procedia Engineering</i>, 89, 1128–1135. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2014.11.234.</p>
Images	
Caption/Source	The iWIDGET web application for the monitoring and control of household water consumption for smart water meter data.

5.6.11 Accessing the tool and test data

Nessie system is available for research purposes free of charge on a time limited license. For commercial purposes there are commercial agreement options. The system has been implemented as operational tool in the above-mentioned demo cases and projects and due to this the access by system operators is restricted. For the LL of Bodø, the system hosts information protected by GDPR. A link to the actual tool for demo purposes only (without any restricted data) is provided below:

<https://bws.uwmh.eu/dashboard/init>

For further details on how to access the application, please contact Dr. Panagiotis Kossieris (pkossier@mail.ntua.gr).

Information and material about the tool can be accessed through the Water Europe Marketplace (<https://mp.watereurope.eu/d/Product/27>) and the Urban Water Management and Hydroinformatics group (<https://uwmh.civil.ntua.gr/products/84-nessie-system.html>). An overview presentation of Nessie system, its capabilities and past implementations, as well as a step by step guide to connect a third party system with Nessie System through its API are available in video format in the project's website (<https://b-watersmart.eu/the-nessie-platform/>) and the WE Marketplace (<https://mp.uwmh.eu/d/Product/27>).

5.7 Environmental Dashboard (#30)

5.7.1 Tool description and attributes

Environmental dashboard (Miljødashboard) has been developed with a view to present data sources in maps and current graphs. Data has been aggregated and gives a picture of water consumption in the different districts. A separate interface will also be established for technical staff, which will then have a more detailed interface. The platform will also be linked to demographic data sets so that users get a picture of the average per capita and per household. Environmental dashboard is developed with three user groups in mind. Those are: 1. technical staff, 2. decision and administration, 3. audience.

Table 16 below included information about tool's attributes and descriptions in a tabular format to be used for the update of the Water Europe Marketplace of T7.1, if needed. The detailed page of the tool can be accessed via the following URL: <https://mp.watereurope.eu/d/Product/65>.

Table 16: Environmental Dashboard's attributes and description

Tool's attribute	Description
Type of product	A software supporting the Circular Economy
Name	Miljødashboard - Environmental Dashboard
Description	The Environmental Dashboard is suitable for visualizing different data sources, and with various levels of detail. Apart from the water domain, the Environmental Dashboard is also used for traffic mapping and water management (as part of other projects).
Abbreviation	NA.
URL	https://www.miljodashboard.no/
Costs	The product is not priced at the current stage. In the future, we will also work with a business model that takes care of the product's living costs.

Target audience	It is being developed with three user groups in mind. 1st technical staff, 2nd administration, 3rd audience.
Actors, roles and interactions	Water utilities, industries, technology providers, end-users, their roles and their interactions.
Unique selling points /Added Value/Innovation	Water utilities, industries, technology providers, end-users), their roles and their interactions
TRL	Level 7
Technical requirements	Ordinary PC, tablets, or any smart phone.
Environment	all
Version	V.2.0
Initial release	2023
License type	Commercial
Programming language/technologies used	Frontend is programmed in html.
Open interface	Platform is suitable for presentation of data for Scada systems, but not limited to it. We have demonstrated several different data sources and can work with the known APIs.
Graphical User Interface / Headless software	Solution presents data in GUI, available at https://www.miljodashboard.no/
Supported spatial scales	We aim for three levels with varying degrees of detail depending on the needs of the target end-users (technical staff, administration, audience).
Supported temporal scales	The solution will present data in real time, but also has functionality for selecting entire weeks, with hourly data.
Water Use Types	City, and districts. Primarily households.
Compatibility with FIWARE	NORD have implemented the FIWARE standard in accordance with NGSI-v2 for all the data collected from Bodø Kommune. The templates from FIWARE were used, so that data in the Environmental Dashboard can be used in other parts of Europe. However, since Techni-meters have their own standard, and data sets varies – the original format has been kept.
Organisations	Nordkontakt AS
Contact details	Vemund Kristiansen, vemund.kristiansen@nordkontakt.no
Data Manager	Vemund Kristiansen, vemund.kristiansen@nordkontakt.no
Technologies	-

Tags

Environment, with several themes. Water, power, waste, air quality, and traffic - (vehicles, cyclists, and pedestrians).

Images

Velkommen til
Bodos miljødashboard

Her får du en oversikt over din og ditt

E-post
email@example.com

Passord

Husk meg

LOGG INN

Har du ikke bruk? Registrer deg nå

fit.no
koydstato.no

Overordnet layout

Global Navigasjon

Overordnet er den globale navigasjonen på toppen og for brukerne navigere mellom de ulike sidepaneler.

Toppanel

Toppanelen er viktig spesielt. Det skal være enkel og intuitiv og gir alle nødvendige opplysninger for brukeren og for kartet og andre brukere som er inne på.

Wiget

Wiget er viktig for brukeren og skal være enkel og intuitiv og gir alle nødvendige opplysninger for brukeren og for kartet og andre brukere som er inne på.

Kartbehandling

Kartbehandling er viktig for brukeren og skal være enkel og intuitiv og gir alle nødvendige opplysninger for brukeren og for kartet og andre brukere som er inne på.

Filtrering

Filtrering er viktig for brukeren og skal være enkel og intuitiv og gir alle nødvendige opplysninger for brukeren og for kartet og andre brukere som er inne på.

Caption/Source	Above are some screenshots to illustrate the principle of platform, and an example that will show water consumption in districts. There will be an iterative process to further develop the solution to indicate the degree of leakage.
Publications	No official publication about the tool has been prepared yet.

5.7.2 Pre-existing background

We have had a version 1.0 that demonstrated the presentation of different data sources on different platforms. Version 2.0 developed in this project elevates the graphic and functional so that it is very intuitive to use. It is currently in use at the local waste company.

5.7.3 Developments and advancements within the project

NORD has integrated the data sources provided by Bodø Kommune, NTNU and Techni. The data collected, are all available in NORD's API portal. API access has been given to verified BWS partners.

NORD's API provides several extra products for scientists/partners to make use of – such as minimum nightly average flow, consumptions for each zone etc. This saves other parties a lot of work when using data.

NORD and Techni has identified a need for a certificate change with Techni's prototype household sensors.

5.7.4 Navigation and primary functionalities

The overall layout is presented in the figures below (Figure 99, Figure 100, Figure 101). The dashboard lets you query based on the top Navigation bar – and compares the consumption of the present day with one day back (example feature). The Environmental dashboard is integrated with the NIVUS sensors NTNU provided.

Overall layout

Figure 99: Schematic of overall layout of the Environmental Dashboard

Figure 100: Update of functionality

Figure 101: Overall layout of the Environmental Dashboard & Update of functionality

Figure 101 illustrates the water consumption in separate districts. The first view consists of a comparison of zones compared to each other, and how much of the total consumption a zone is related to.

The second view compares the consumption on a daily basis one week back in time. This allows the user to compare patterns on a weekly/daily basis. The comparison and data can all be selected on the top navigation bar.

The third view is a leakage estimation based on minimum night flow, which also changes by the top navigation bar.

5.7.5 Interoperability

NORD has made use of data models and standards from FIWARE, so that the Environmental Dashboard can be used and applied in other parts of Europe. This also means that the data sources we have integrated, are also available in FIWARE standard. The data model used is the NGSI-v2 Standard. NORD also provided API documentation in our API portal. TRL level 7 of the tool is accomplished as planned.

NORD has achieved level 3. Interoperability with BWS partners.

NORD had meetings with BWS partners on several occasions and provided help using the APIs, and how to fetch data. NORD is also investigating to implementing the new standard NGSI-v2-LD, which would make us LEVEL 4 FIWARE compatible.

5.7.6 Indicative applications and synergistic benefits

NORD takes this platform with it to other projects and develops its own modules for several topics. Environment has several themes including water, power, waste, air quality, and traffic. The data gathered by the Environmental Dashboard provides the opportunity for multiple applications of relevant interest for the Bodø water utility, as well as for the Norwegian water sector. SINTEF, in collaboration with NORD and Bodø, has assessed alternative potential use cases to demonstrate the value of the NORD API (tool #30). As result, the very first application developed by SINTEF to promote the NORD solution is a web-application allowing a water utility to compute the drinking water balance at different levels of resolution in time and space. The connection with NORD's API allows to access the data of the meters located in Bodø's water distribution network. When the user demands to import data from the web-application front-end, multiple requests are sent from the back end to the Environmental Dashboard to retrieve relevant data. SINTEF's use case employ therefore tool #30 to enable the estimations of water losses and associated indicators, by considering the different components of the water balance based on the IWA methodology (Alegre H., et al., 2006), as shown in the following figure.

System	Input	Volume	Authorised Consumption	Billed Authorised Consumption	Billed Metered Consumption		Revenue Water
				Unbilled Authorised Consumption	Billed Unmetered Consumption	Unbilled Metered Consumption	
Water Losses			Apparent Losses	Real Losses	Unauthorised Consumption	Customer Meter Inaccuracies	Non Revenue Water
					Leakage on Transmission and Distribution Mains	Leakage and Overflows at Storage Tanks	
			Leakage on Service Connections up to point of Customer Meter				

Figure 102: Components of the IWA Water Balance considered in the use case of the Environmental Dashboard

The user can calculate periodic water balances with inputs entered either manually or automatically. The automatic water balance estimations allow to monitor continuously real and apparent losses, as well as revenue non-revenue water, pointing out if and how bursts or increase of background leakages occur over time.

5.7.7 Accessing the tool and test data

Data is available through API, and data related to household data has been shared successfully with ICCS. Water-network data has been shared with NTNU. In general, all the tools and APIs needed to integrate are functional but is continuously being added features for.

The Environmental dashboard can be accessed through: <https://environmentdashboard.no/user/> . Publication is password protected.. Please refer to Vemund Kristiansen, (vemund.kristiansen@nordkontakt.no) to get access.

Test data are available from other projects too. Indicative examples are:

"Smartere Transport": This project aims to compile all data sources that collect traffic information for the entire city. This is compiled and presented in the same framework, Environmental dashboard as a separate traffic-module.

"A Cleaner Arctic": In this project, we have joined forces with the local waste company to establish a station for mapping environmental toxins at the landfill. The station is equipped with a wide range of sensors. The project aims to deliver new insight into the landfill's impact on the environment.

5.8 Digital Enabler (#32)

5.8.1 Tool description and attributes

Digital Enabler™ is a data driven, native cloud, ecosystem platform. Designed and engineered by Engineering’s R&D Labs over the past years, today it is one of the few available, fully functioning, ready to use, Cloud Ecosystems Platforms available on the market.

As an “Ecosystem” platform, Digital Enabler enables new data economy business models, fostering innovation & enhancing current capabilities.

It allows you to Harmonize, Synchronize, Integrate, Visualize, Mashup, Federate and Analyze data to power your digital transformation & provides a single point of (data) knowledge that can be used to develop new value-added services as well as digitally enabling older technologies and applications.

Figure 103 – Overall functional flow of the Digital Enabler

Digital Enabler should be used wherever data needs to be enriched. The Digital Enabler platform can:

- Create an Open innovation Area, to manage and develop new ideas;
- Discover and normalize different types of data source (Open Data, Enterprise Data, IoT devices & Infrastructure and many more...) increasing your base knowledge;
- Evaluate data quality of sources, improving overall data quality;
- Provide real time data management / event driven information for alerting and monitoring;
- Dynamically Model & Integrate Data
- Visualize, analyze and render Data via its Mash up and Mock Up capabilities and Front End Dashboards, creating new digital capabilities, applications and services that power up the new «Data Economy» ecosystem.

It is entirely based on Open Standards and Open API, and it is FIWARE based.

Unique selling points

1. It enables organizations to rapidly join the new «data economy» ecosystems.
2. Industry, domain & technology independent.
3. No hardware or software installation is required.
4. You can scale up/down users whilst keeping your costs fully under control.
5. Increases the value of existing assets and promotes new business solutions.
6. Reduced time to market and improved responsiveness to business demands by rapidly and easily going from mock-up to «ready to publish» app (mobile & web).
7. Great usability, thanks to its fast prototyping and integrated WYSIWYG (*What You See is What You Get*) visual user interface, to visualize, analyze and render data via mash up and mock up capabilities and front-end dashboards.

5.8.2 Pre-existing background

The Digital Enabler was previously used mainly for developing data driven solutions in the smart city domain, plus some initiative in the smart industry and smart agriculture areas.

Its functionalities and components can be summarized as follows:

1. Data Source Discovery Engine: finds data sources available on the web.
2. Device Manager: registers and manages IoT devices with different protocols.
3. City Data Work Space: stores and manages data from different sources.
4. Data mash up Editor: harmonizes data regardless to their sources.
5. Open Innovation Area: for co-creation processes between city stakeholders.
6. APIs Portal: for the interaction with the Digital Enabler platform via Open API.
7. Dashboard Manager and Presenter: for the creation of dashboards useful to visualize, correlate and analyze data.
8. Citizen Data Vault: to manage personal data in compliance with EU GDPR.
9. Mock-up Editor: allows fast prototyping and APP deployment.

5.8.3 Developments and advancements within the project

Enhancements done within the B-WaterSmart project are mainly related to three areas:

- Data integration: development of new data connectors and pre-processing procedures that will enable the DE to extend its capabilities for supporting end-to-end data lifecycle management in the domain of smart water. Moreover, new components for the management of satellite images have been integrated.
- Data models: inclusion of two new FIWARE-compliant data models for water and sludge quality representation
- Data visualization: definition and development of new charts and dashboards for the smart-water domain.

The aforementioned enhancements are driven by the development of the water reuse strategic platform (#16) and of the sludge management platform (#19). Their developments will be integrated in the overall structure of the Digital Enabler, representing an extension for the water industry.

5.8.4 Interoperability

The Digital Enabler includes the FIWARE Orion Context Broker among its components and is already at maturity level 4 as of definition provided in D3.1.

5.8.5 Indicative applications and synergistic benefits

The Digital Enabler has never been used in the Smart Water domain. The project B-WaterSmart is used to extend its features to cover specific necessities of this domain. Until now, the main field of application of the DE was on Smart Cities. The following table reports information about one of the reference Smart City case studies of the DE. This can be of help when thinking about its future use in the water industry.

Table 17: Application of Digital Enabler (#32) out of the B-WaterSmart project

Indicative application of tool	
Title	City Enabler for Smart Cities
Description	<p>SELECT for Cities is a European project that aims to develop an open, standardized, data-driven, and user-centric platform for European cities, with the common challenge to develop “cities as large-scale Internet of Everything labs”.</p> <p>The solution we provided is called City Enabler, a city-oriented customization of our proprietary solution "Digital Enabler", and it has been used to build use cases for the City of Antwerp and the City of Helsinki.</p> <p>The City of Helsinki’s use case is focused on environmental monitoring. The aim is to increase the degree of innovation, enabling stakeholders through data collection to develop a variety of completely new data-driven services for citizens, and to advance IoE platform capability from a problem-solving approach towards a new solution creation. The Digital Enabler was used to integrate data from different sources and services, provide tools for data analytics, and enable development of new innovative services to, for example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easily and quickly get reliable information about the current state of the air quality and other environmental indicators; • Reveal dependencies of current air quality and other indicators from possible impact factors, especially traffic, active construction works, weather condition, industries, timing, etc • Make short-term estimations on air quality and other indicator changes based on mixture of historical data and conditions; <p>The use case of the city of Antwerp was deployed in the Smart Zone, a zone dedicated to real-life testing of technology and scenarios. The area of the Smart Zone is central, comprising many shops and sights, many visitors, and as a result much traffic. It is being established for the long term as an innovation hub for implementing and testing</p>

	essential technology, as well as related business aspects, across diverse topics and scenarios. The City Enabler was applied in the Smart Zone as part of the infrastructure that connects and combines all input gathered in the diverse IoT scenarios as well as other data sources, allowing the development of advanced services and functionalities such as: integration with different data streams, dashboards for the city officials, information to the citizen/tourist in an interface which appeals to them.
Reference point	Helsinki: 60.18301338043742, 24.933513550647316 Antwerp: 51.223470012692246, 4.405675610500012
Location	Helsinki Antwerp
Country (-ies)	Finland, Belgium
URL	https://www.eng.it/resources/platform/digital-enabler/doc/city-enabler-brochure.pdf
Project	<p>Select4Cities is a European Pre-Commercial Procurement Project aimed at developing a data-driven, Internet-of-Everything (IoE) platform for large-scale urban co-creation. The SELECT for Cities competition is built around the premise that cities across the world are seeking new methods, technologies and tools to foster open innovation to solve challenges, create value for their citizens and business, and to become 'smart cities'.</p> <p>Internet of Everything (IoE) is one of the dominant drivers transforming the way people manage and live in urban environments. This new connected approach involves physical spaces as well as objects and provides a massive opportunity for the creation of new smart services and businesses especially in the areas of logistics, transport, environment, security and wellbeing. However, IoE progress to date has been slow due to a number of barriers such as the lack of common standards, a fragmented marketplace, and lack of ways to systematically test and introduce new solutions in the cities.</p> <p>To combat this challenge, and accelerate innovation, Select4Cities ran a competition open to European companies to develop an open, standardized, data-driven, service-oriented and user-centric platform that enables large-scale co-creation, testing and validation of urban IoE applications and services.</p> <p>More information about Select4Cities can be found here: http://www.select4cities.eu</p>
Challenges	Not applicable to the water domain
Tools/Product/Services	Digital Enabler (#32)
Technologies	Not applicable
Scales	City
Legislation	Not applicable

Synergistic benefits	Benefits were generated thanks to the integration of heterogeneous data sources from the specific territories and from the possibility to open the processed data to external third parties. This allowed the system to enable open innovation processes and let application developers from around Europe to develop new data-driven services.
Requirements and conditions	We needed to extend the DE by using components for the management of satellite images.
Key lessons	Availability of data is of paramount importance, and data retention is one of the main obstacles to the development of a truly data-driven system.
Organisations	Engineering Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A.
Contact persons	Davide Storelli Davide.storelli@eng.it Engineering Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A.
Data Manager	Davide Storelli Davide.storelli@eng.it Engineering Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A.
Costs	Not applicable
Tags	Smart City, environment, data integration, dashboard, decision maker
Publications/Reference	Not applicable
Images	<p>The diagram, titled "Unlock the potential of city data", illustrates a workflow of six interconnected components. It features a central horizontal line with six circular icons representing each component, connected by lines. Above the line are components 2, 4, and 6, and below the line are components 1, 3, and 5. The components are: 1 Datasource Discovery Engine (magnifying glass icon), 2 IoT Device Manager (person with gear icon), 3 Data Mashup Editor (bar chart icon), 4 City Data Workspace (document with gear icon), 5 Dashboard Manager (dashboard icon), and 6 City Front-End (share icon).</p>
Caption/Source	Main City Enabler components

5.8.6 Accessing tool and test data

The functionalities of the DE are made available to tools (#16) and (#19). Access to its individual components can be provided upon request to the contact person (davide.storelli@eng.it).

5.9 Climate-readiness certification tool (#33)

5.9.1 Tool description and attributes

The Climate Ready Certification tool is the online platform that calculates and issues the Climate-ready certificate (CRC), an assessment tool that combines three dimensions: water efficiency, water-energy nexus and climate adaptation in one certificate. The CRC can be applied to residential and small service/commercial buildings, as well as to “neighbourhoods” considering both the buildings and outdoor areas within the frontier established for the neighbourhood. It is designed to be applied to individual households, buildings and neighbourhoods and the evaluated projects can be in different stages: design, new construction, or in-use.

The CRC methodology expands from an already existing initiative by ADENE, AQUA+®, a certification system that focuses on the water efficiency dimension, adding water-energy nexus and climate adaptation evaluation criteria. The CRC certificate is issued by the CRC auditors via the online tool, and made available to the project owner: householders, buildings managers, urban developers, urban planners and municipalities, also via the platform. The platform is developed in .NET, Sharepoint 2019 framework, in C# language. The climate adaptation and water-energy nexus modules are to be freely available to anyone who accesses the tool link, for simulation purposes of the CRC performance assessment while the water efficiency module (AQUA+) will be restricted to AQUA+ users.

The basis of the CRC methodology, and main input to the online platform development, is an excel spreadsheet that differentiates between the different project scales: individual households, buildings and outdoor areas. The evaluation basis is a set of criteria applicable or not to the different project scales and considering different weights according to the relevance of the criteria to the item under certification. The classification identified in each CRC varies from F (less efficient) to A+ (most efficient). It encompasses one global classification and three sub-classifications, related to each of the evaluated dimensions: Water Efficiency, Water-Energy Nexus, and Climate Adaptation.

The online platform (beta version) will be launched in the beginning of October of 2023, to avoid the holiday period, for impact poupose.

Table 18: Climate-readiness certification tool’s attributes and description

Tool’s attribute	Description
Type of product	A methodology or a process related with the Circular Economy.
Name	Climate-Ready Certificate.
Description	Climate-readiness certification tool is the online platform that calculates and issues the Climate-ready certificate (CRC). This certification combines in one certificate three dimensions: water efficiency, water-energy nexus and climate adaptation The

	evaluated projects can have different scales: individual households, buildings and neighbourhoods and be in different stages: design, new construction, or in-use.
Abbreviation	CRC
URL	http://climatecertificates.adene.pt - Official public launch in early October 2023, to avoid the holiday period, for impact purposes.
Costs	The simulation of the CRC performance assessment will be free and accessible to CRC auditors who visit the CRC portal, for the modules developed during B-WaterSmart (Water-Energy Nexus and Climate Adaptation). The module Water Efficiency is AQUA+ a registered trade mark of ADENE, and is accessible to AQUA+ auditors with the AQUA+ certification system.
Target audience	Urban planners, building developers, property owners and municipalities. The main users of the platform are the Climate Ready Certificates auditors.
Actors, roles and interactions	<p>CRC Auditor – Can simulate and issue the Climate-Ready certificate.</p> <p>Project owners: householders, buildings managers, buildings developers, urban planners and municipalities – can access the platform to access the CRC information</p> <p>Anyone who visits the platform – can simulate the global performance of the project (household, building, or neighbourhood), regarding water efficiency, water-energy nexus performance and climate adaptation.</p>
Unique selling points /Added Value/Innovation	<p>A single certificate to access the water efficiency, the water-energy nexus performance and the climate adaptation evaluation of households, buildings and neighborhoods. The evaluated projects can be in the design phase, new construction, or in use.</p> <p>This certificate informs the users about the performance of their buildings/urban area and should be used as a decision support tool for project options related to water efficiency and climate adaptation in the different phases of the project development. For developers and buildings owners this certificate, issued by a third-party auditor, can promote the quality of their buildings to their potential clients.</p>
TRL	7
Technical requirements	The platform is web based.
Environment	Sharepoint
Version	1
Initial release	Public official release of the tool - October 2023
License type	Free for Water-Energy Nexus and Climate Adaptation modules. AQUA+ (Water Efficiency module) is payed.

Programming language/technologies used	C#, Sharepoint
Open interface	The platform will receive data from the World Resource Institute: https://www.wri.org/data/aqueduct-global-maps-30-data
Graphical User Interface / Headless software	GUI
Supported spatial scales	Households, Buildings and Neighborhoods
Supported temporal scales	Annual
Water Use Types	Urban and domestic.
Compatibility with FIWARE	The platform is FIWARE compliant.
Organisations	ADENE
Contact details	Pedro Cardoso – pedro.cardoso@adene.pt
Data Manager	Pedro Cardoso – pedro.cardoso@adene.pt
Technologies	AQUA+ TM
Tags	Water-Efficiency; Water-Energy Nexus; Climate Adaptation; Efficient building

<p>Images</p>	
<p>Caption/Source</p>	<p>First page of the Climate-Ready Certificate template (PDF file).</p>
<p>Publications</p>	<p>The methodology manual will be delivered with the online platform, and freely available.</p>

5.9.2 Pre-existing background

B-WaterSmart Climate-Ready certification tool expands from AQUA+®, a voluntary certification system (<https://www.aquamais.pt/>), developed by ADENE to assess and classify water efficiency and reuse performance in households, promoting water-efficient fixtures and

equipment, rainwater harvesting, greywater systems, smart metering, leakage control, water-energy nexus and guidance to operators and occupants. AQUA+ was distinguished as the National Winner in the category “Supporting the Sustainable Transition” of the European Enterprise Promotion Awards 2021 and is also one of the two projects selected to represent Portugal in the European Enterprise Promotion Awards (EEPA) final in Slovenia.

5.9.3 Developments and advancements within the project

The CRC methodology expanded from AQUA+® adding criteria to evaluate two additional dimensions: water-energy nexus and climate adaptation. It is available not only for households but also for buildings and neighbourhoods. The methodology’s first approach is finished, and it is now in the test phase via its applicability to several pilots (including buildings, households and neighbourhoods) of the Lisbon Living Lab. It will continue to be applied to more pilots to generate the maximum amount of data in order to calibrate and continue to improve the methodology.

5.9.4 Climate-Ready Certificates Methodology

The CRC methodology encompasses three dimensions: water efficiency, water-energy nexus and climate adaptation. Overall it has 96 evaluation criteria: 53 criteria in the water efficiency dimension, 23 criteria in the water energy nexus, and 20 in the climate adaptation. All these criteria are evaluated in the three different scales of applicability: household, building and neighborhood, though some of the criteria are not applicable to the households and outdoor spaces analysis. The methodology has closed questions, that can be answered by a single option, multiple options or percentages. Each criteria has associated a score and the answers are ordered by descending score. The answer with the higher score is always the first option displayed. In the case of a criteria that does not apply and as such is not evaluated, the auditor can exclude it and its score is proportionally distributed to the other methodology criteria. Figure 104, Figure 105 and Figure 106 present a snapshot of some of the methodology criteria. In Figure 107 the weights attributed to the evaluated areas are presented.

W1 Alternative water sources and water distribution	
W1.1. Alternative water source system	
W1.1.1	Alternative water source system - Is the building provided by a certified/licenced/standard compliant system or in process of certification (by a competent authority) for:
W1.1.1.1	Rainwater harvesting
W1.1.1.2	Greywater reuse
W1.1.1.3	Treated wastewater
W1.1.1.4	Surface or groundwater
W1.1.1.5	Desalination
W1.1.1.6	None of the above
W1.1.1.7	It was not possible to determine (Justify)
W1.1.2	Alternative water source destinations - Is the building alternative water used for:
W1.1.2.1	Irrigation (unrestricted/restricted)
W1.1.2.2	Pavement washing
W1.1.2.3	Toilet flushing
W1.1.2.4	Washing machines
W1.1.2.5	Water fountains, etc.
W1.1.2.6	Other (specify)
W1.1.2.7	None of the above
W1.1.2.8	It was not possible to determine (Justify)
W1.1.3	Volume of the rainwater deposit - Is the rainwater deposit volume...
W1.1.3.1	Between $\pm 20\%$ of the adequate value
W1.1.3.2	Outside $\pm 20\%$ of the adequate value
W1.1.3.3	Non existent
W1.1.3.4	It was not possible to determine (Justify)
W1.1.4	Water reuse management and monitoring - Is the consumption of the alternative water monitored by a dedicated flowmeter?
W1.1.4.1	Flowmeter accoped with management system
W1.1.4.2	Regular flowmeter
W1.1.4.3	Other meter
W1.1.4.4	None of the above
W1.1.4.5	It was not possible to determine (Justify)
W1.2 Water distribution and building water networks	
W.2.1	Existing networks to water reuse - Is the building prepared to be supplied with alternative water sources on:
W1.2.1.1	Outdoor uses
W1.2.1.2	Indoor uses
W1.2.1.3	None of the above
W1.2.1.4	It was not possible to determine (Justify)
W1.2.2	Water separation in drainage - Is the building prepared to allow the separation of:
W.1.2.2.1	Greywater drainage
W.1.2.2.2	Rainwater drainage
W.1.2.2.3	None of the above
W.1.2.2.4	It was not possible to determine (Justify)
W1.2.3	Water losses in pipes - Does the building network show:
W1.2.3.1	No evidence of water losses
W1.2.3.2	Possible occurrence of water losses (evidence through observation)
W1.2.3.3	Evidence of water losses
W1.2.3.4	It was not possible to determine (Justify)
W1.2.4	Network age - For how long has the building (averaged by pipe length) network been operated since commissioning or the last rehabilitation?
W1.2.4.1	Less than 20 years
W1.2.4.2	Between 20 and 40 years
W1.2.4.3	More than 40 years
W1.2.4.4	It was not possible to determine (Justify)
W1.2.5	Does the building main supply pipe allow or provide:
W1.2.5.1	Flowmeter with data logger and data management dashboard
W1.2.5.2	Flowmeter with supply interruption
W1.2.5.3	Flowmeter with alarm for leak occurrence
W1.2.5.4	Data monitoring with daily (or greater) frequency
W1.2.5.5	Data monitoring with detailed characterisation (per use)
W1.2.5.6	None of the above
W1.2.5.7	It was not possible to determine (Justify)

Figure 104 Example of an evaluation criteria for the Water Efficiency Dimension

N5 Fixtures	
N5.1	Pressure/Head loss
N5.1.1	What is the value of the water static pressure at the first water end-use point (cold water)?
N5.1.1.1	[0.15, 0.3] MPa
N5.1.1.2	[0.125, 0.15[or]0.3, 0.45] Mpa
N5.1.1.3	[0.1, 0.125[or]0.45, 0,6] Mpa
N5.1.1.5	< 0.1 Mpa or >0,6 Mpa
N5.1.1.6	It was not possible to determine (Justify)
N5.1.2	What is the value of the head loss at the most distant shower head, with the maximum flow? (hot water)
N5.1.2.1	< 0.05 MPa
N5.1.2.2	[0.05, 0.1[MPa
N5.1.2.3	[0.1, 0.15[MPa
N5.1.2.4	[0.15, 0.2[Mpa
N5.1.2.5	>= 0.2 MPa
N5.1.2.6	It was not possible to determine (Justify)
N5.1.3	What is the value of the head loss at the most distant shower head, with the maximum flow? (cold water)
N5.1.3.1	< 0.01 MPa
N5.1.3.2	[0.01, 0.03[MPa
N5.1.3.3	[0.03, 0.05[MPa
N5.1.3.4	[0.05, 0.07[Mpa
N5.1.3.5	>= 0.07 MPa
N5.1.3.6	It was not possible to determine (Justify)
N5.1.4	What is the value of the head loss at the last water point with the maximum flow? (cold water)
N5.1.4.1	< 0.01 MPa
N5.1.4.2	[0.01, 0.03[MPa
N5.1.4.3	[0.03, 0.05[MPa
N5.1.4.4	[0.05, 0.07[Mpa
N5.1.4.5	>= 0.07 MPa
N5.1.4.6	It was not possible to determine (Justify)

Figure 105 Example of an evaluation criteria of the Water-Energy Nexus Dimension

C2 Project Area	
C2.1	Mapping climate risks - Coastal flooding
C2.1.1	What was the level of coastal flooding risk identified for the project area?
C2.1.1.1	Null or negligible
C2.1.1.2	Low
C2.1.1.3	Moderate
C2.1.1.4	High
C2.1.1.5	It was not possible to determine (Justify)
C2.2	Mapping climate risks - Floods
C2.2.1	What was the level of flooding risk identified for the project area?
C2.2.1.1	Null or negligible
C2.2.1.2	moderate
C2.2.1.3	High
C2.2.1.4	Very High
C2.2.1.5	It was not possible to determine (Justify)
C2.3	Mapping climate risks - Droughts
C2.3.1	What was the level of drought risk identified for the project area, (SPI index, 12 month integration)?
C2.3.1.1	<-2,00
C2.3.1.2	-1.50 a -1.99
C2.3.1.3	-1.00 a -1.49
C2.3.1.4	-0.50 a -0.99
C2.3.1.5	> -0.49
C2.3.1.6	It was not possible to determine (Justify)
C2.3.2	What is the Water Scarcity (WEI+) index for the project hydrographic region?
C2.3.2.1	> 40%
C2.3.2.2	20%, 40[%
C2.3.2.3	[10%, 20[%
C2.3.2.4	< 10%
C2.3.2.6	It was not possible to determine (Justify)
C2.4	Mapping climate risks - Heat Waves
C2.4.1	What was the level of heat wave risk identified for the project area (°C)?
C2.4.1.1	<1,5
C2.4.1.2	1,6 - 2,0
C2.4.1.3	2,1 - 2,5
C2.4.1.4	2,6 - 3,0
C2.4.1.5	3,1 - 3,5
C2.4.1.6	3,6 - 4,0
C2.4.1.7	4,1 - 4,5
C2.4.1.8	It was not possible to determine (Justify)

Figure 106 Example of an evaluation criteria of the Climate Adaptation Dimension

	Household	Building	Outdoor spaces
Water efficiency			
Alternative water sources and water distribution	10%	30%	40%
Outside uses	15%	20%	50%
Fixtures	45%	20%	10%
Devices (washing machines)	15%	5%	-
Domestic hot water system (DHW)	15%	25%	-
	100%	100%	100%
Water-energy nexus			
Alternative water sources	5%	10%	20%
Water distribution and building networks	20%	20%	40%
Irrigation (soils, green roofs, green façades)	5%	10%	20%
Swimming pool	10%	10%	10%
Fixtures	15%	5%	-
Appliances	15%	5%	-
Domestic hot water system (DHW)	20%	25%	-
Energy Monitoring and control	10%	15%	10%
	100%	100%	100%
Climate adaptation			
1. Local Policies and Strategy	0%	0%	0%
2. Project Area	60%	50%	40%
3. Project Response	40%	50%	60%
	100%	100%	100%
Summary			
Water efficiency	40%	34%	25%
Water-Energy Nexus	40%	33%	25%
Climate adaptation	20%	33%	50%
	100%	100%	100%

Figure 107 Distribution of weights for the different project typologies

So far, the certificates have been issued manually. A PDF file is generated with the information contained in the CRC methodology template, consisting of an Excel file. Once the web tool is publicly launched (early October 2023), the auditors will be able to select the building typology or a neighborhood to be certified, fill in the CRC methodology directly in the web tool and the platform calculates the class for each dimension, the overall class and issue the CRC certificate.

Figure 108 CRC certificate emission flux

5.9.5 Climate-Ready Certificates Pilots

The methodology has been tested in one neighborhood (Praça de Entrecampos), three buildings (in Praça de Entrecampos, Bairro da Boavista and ADENE's), four detached houses (three in Bairro da Boavista and one in Seixal) and thirteen households/dwellings in multi-family apartments (nine in Praça de Entrecampos, two in Bairro da Boavista, one in Peniche and one in Carcavelos). The detailed results of this exercise will be presented in the report for MS32 (due in month 45). Figure 109 summarizes the global classifications of the certified pilots until August 2023.

	ID	Project type	Global Classification
Households	Rua Sanches Coelho, Lote 4A, (several typologies), Lisboa	New construction	D
	Rua Luciano Freire, n.º 69, Seixal	In-use	C
	Bairro da Boavista, Rua das Magnólias Bloco D, (Several typologies), Lisboa	New construction	D
	Av. Portugal, n 100, 1º D, Carcavelos	In-use	C
	Praça de Entrecampos, Rua Francisco Lyon de Castro n14, 2B, Lisboa	In-use	D
	Bairro da Boavista, Rua 6, (three houses), Lisboa	In-use	D
	Peniche Apartment, Peniche	In-use	E
Buildings	Rua Sanches Coelho, Lote 4A	New construction	D
	Bairro da Boavista, Rua das Magnólias Bloco D	New construction	D
	ADENE's Building	In-use	D
Neighborhoods	Praça de Entrecampos	New construction/in project	C
	Bairro da Boavista	In-use	C

Figure 109 Pilot's global classification

Two technical sessions have been organized to present and discuss the CRC methodology, one aimed at ADENE staff , including representatives from several departments and another one aimed at the partners of the Lisbon Living Lab (LLL). The contributions/suggestions

gathered during the technical sessions were considered in the final revision of the methodology. Also, the participants were invited to test the CRC methodology in their houses. ADENE provides the tools and technical support, needed to accomplish the audits. Some more pilots have already been identified, consisting of one neighborhood with a garden and a library, a sports facility (outdoor and administrative building) and also households/dwellings.

5.9.6 Navigation and primary functionalities

The final product consists of a bilingual platform (Portuguese and English) that allows an/a intuitive/user friendly interaction between the users and ADENE. Namely, ADENE can ensure the qualification and management of all potential users of the CRC methodology, the management of the audit questionnaires, to be filled in by each user (to simulate the performance index) or qualified technicians (to issue the certificate). Regarding the qualified persons and entities, can manage the audit process, carry out audits and ensure client management.

The Platform includes a public area, accessible to all users, and a private area, only accessible through authentication, with different functionalities defined for different types of users. The website developed by ADENE has the following domain: climatecertificates.adene.pt.

Briefly, the functionalities of the platform include: i) Registration (per type of user, including data record in the database); ii) Login; iii) Edition of personal data; iv) Creation of a new process; v) Certification; vi) Completion of the methodology questionnaire and vii) certificate issue.

The platform will also provide a consultation area aimed at the different actors involved in the process.

5.9.7 Interoperability

The data format, regarding the methodology questionnaire, is FIWARE compatible (in terms of the used units, e.g., flow rate, pressure etc.). Although, the input values correspond to preselected values and the output consists of a PDF file, including predefined classifications and improvement measures.

5.9.8 Indicative applications and synergistic benefits

The platform uses data from the World Resource Institute: <https://www.wri.org/data/aqueduct-global-maps-30-data>. These data are used to evaluate the related climate risks in case the project doesn't encompass a more detailed risk assessment for its location. Also, the platform is prepared for using different data sources, related to the applicable climate risks.

Table 19: Applications of the Climate-readiness certification tool out of the B-WaterSmart project

Indicative application of tool	
Title	The use of the Climate-readiness Certification tool for architecture project improvement.
Description	<p>This text describes the usability of the tool #33 through a personalised story, for a better comprehension of the certification process.</p> <p>Bruno works in an architecture office and makes projects for new buildings. His speciality is "net zero energy" buildings, which are buildings where the energy consumption of the house is lower than the energy production using local renewable energy sources. In this balance, Bruno also considers the energy embodied in the materials used to make the house, thus giving preference to more sustainable materials.</p> <p>Scenario:</p> <p>Bruno has been doing sustainable house designs for several years, and with increasing sensitivity to environmental causes Bruno's business is going very well. However, one day Bruno sees on the news the water shortage problems in Algarve and thinks about it, because the houses he built are sustainable from the energy point of view, but neglecting the water and the climate adaptation dimensions. The subject stays in Bruno's mind and one day he finds out from a friend who does energy audits under the Energy Certification System for Buildings that there is also a voluntary assessment of water efficiency, water-energy nexus and climate adaptation. Bruno becomes very interested and does some research on this system to find out how he can adopt these practices in his projects. He discovers the CRC methodology, already applied to several houses in Lisbon and contacts ADENE to evaluate how he can also apply the methodology to the houses he is designing. He is told that he can take a training to act as a certified auditor for CRC and registers for the next training on the 26th of September 2024.</p> <p>Bruno signs up for the training and on 26th of September he goes to ADENE to attend it. For one day, he learns about good water and climate adaptation practices and the CRC assessment methodology for households, buildings and neighbourhoods. The training assessment has been completed with excellent results and afterwards the registration email for the CRC platform was sent by ADENE's Academy. While registering, Bruno indicates that he wants to be a consultant, rather than an auditor, as he only wishes to improve his projects, thus getting access to an environment on the CRC platform where he can fill in the evaluation form, being able to evaluate and improve all his projects. Nowadays, Bruno doesn't finish any of his projects without first uploading the data on the CRC platform, in order to calculate its water efficiency, water-energy nexus and climate adaptation class. This information is then passed on to real estate agents or clients, who are very pleased to know it and end up using the CRC platform themselves, to request for an auditor to assess the water efficiency of the project and proceed with the issue of the water efficiency rating.</p>
Reference point	https://goo.gl/maps/wo7a82EyAPcRfnea6

	Faro, Algarve.
Location	Faro, Algarve, Portugal.
Country (-ies)	Portugal
URL	climatecertificates.adene.pt
Project	The CRC methodology was already applied in one neighbourhood (Praça de Entrecampos), three buildings (in Praça de Entrecampos, Bairro da Boavista and ADENE), four detached houses (three in Bairro da Boavista and one in Pragal) and thirteen households/dwellings (nine in Praça de Entrecampos, two in Bairro da Boavista, one in Peniche, one in Carcavelos). Other pilots have been already identified.
Challenges	Water Scarcity, High drinking water demand due to dense or growing resident population and economy, Untapped efficiency potential of water resources, Dependent on distant freshwater resources,
Tools/Product/Services	Climate-readiness certification tool (#33)
Technologies	AQUA+ TM
Scales	Households, buildings and neighbourhoods.
Legislation	-
Synergistic benefits	The platform will receive data from the World Resource Institute: https://www.wri.org/data/aqueduct-global-maps-30-data
Requirements and conditions	For the full application of the methodology in new construction phases, the projects must already have contracts with a water utility company.
Key lessons	The major bottleneck found so far was the lack of technical documentation from the projects to be certified.
Organisations	ADENE and Câmara Municipal de Lisboa.
Contact persons	Pedro Cardoso – pedro.cardoso@adene.pt
Data Manager	Pedro Cardoso – pedro.cardoso@adene.pt
Costs	Free for Water-Energy Nexus and Climate Adaptation modules. AQUA+ certification system (Water Efficiency module) is payed.
Tags	Water-Efficiency; Water-Energy Nexus; Climate Adaptation
Publications/Reference	The methodology manual will be delivered with the online platform, and freely available. This manual has case studies and examples of the CRC methodology application.

Images

aption/Source

The first image corresponds to the entrance of the Bairro da Boavista pilot (building); the second and third images are examples of pressure tests conducted during the technical visits and the last image displays the technical area (pumps) of the pilot correspondent to ADENE's building.

5.9.9 Accessing tool and test data

The URL to access the tool is: <http://climatecertificates.adene.pt> The person in charge of making the accessibility and data test is Pedro Cardoso (pedro.cardoso@adene.pt)

6 Tools and Methods for LL Venice

6.1 Key WS challenges, ambition and case study description

The key challenge of the case study is to create the conditions for unlocking important reuse potentials in the water sector that are currently untapped. The case study focuses on three specific resources: water (especially effluents by urban wastewater treatment plants, WWTPs), nitrogen (recoverable from concentrated streams of WWTPs), and sludge produced in urban WWTPs. These three resources are specifically targeted throughout three pilot technologies (one for water and two for nitrogen) and two strategic IT tools (water reuse platform and sludge management platform, described in previous Section 5.1). But this is not all: beyond the identification of innovative technologies for extracting value from water, the challenge in the Venice LL is to create a context enabling their actual use; a virtual environment where the risks are objectively evaluated and the solutions are mediated minimizing the risk of potential penalizations of the supply chain. The actions and activities pursued for this target, by working together in the CoP, can be shortly resumed as follows:

- i)* Building a shared, updatable, scientific knowledge base;
- ii)* Clarifying actual risks linked to resource recovery practices to minimize precautionary approaches and prejudices;
- iii)* Identifying the most sustainable and suitable opportunities of reuse/valorisation, guaranteeing an objective and repeatable process;
- iv)* Fostering fairer policies and laws drafting/revision towards resource recovery practices, with clear directions and without ambiguities;
- v)* Allowing an appropriated update and maintaining a participatory model of governance (the CoP) in which the key strategic stakeholders of the water chain are working together.

Figure 110 reports the Venice LL strategic agenda in which all technologies and tools (included the CoP, which is a real instrument) are connected in a network of contributions and relationships to the LL strategic objectives and to the project expected impacts.

Figure 110 – The LL Venice ambition

6.2 Application of tools and methods

6.2.1 Selected tools and technologies of pilots

The overall ambition of the LL is to setup a regional case where multiple technologies, along with strategic knowledge digital platforms, can be used as foundation to build a resilient and water-smart system by demonstrating the convenience and opportunities of CE logics. In particular, the Venice LL is targeting three main objectives, each of them addressed through specific BWS technology: *i.1*) freshwater saving and general purified wastewater reuse, (developed through DSS tool #16, in its turn based on tool #32), by analysing potential water reuse opportunities and supporting the users in the decision-making process with a standardized scheme of evaluation, contextualized on the territory of interest (for full details, see the water reuse platform in chapter 5.1); *i.2*) freshwater saving and purified wastewater reuse specifically for industrial purposes (pursued through the pilot technology #4), by demonstrating the feasibility and convenience of this kind of direct reuse for the Fusina municipal WWTP effluent; *ii*) nutrient/energy recovery (addressed by pilot technologies #11), by fostering best practices in wastewater treatment to recover N from WWTP concentrated streams and produce salt (mainly ammonium sulphate) to be potentially used for agricultural/other applications; *iii*) sewage sludge valorisation (developed through DSS tool #19, in its turn based on tool #32), by analysing in a standardized manner the state of the art of sludge management and by considering/weighing the best related treatment and

valorisation solutions, to support the decision-making processes, also in relation to the territorial context (see Chapter 5.1 for a detailed description).

6.2.2 Integrative use of tools, pilot interaction and data flows

Tools developed in WP3 (#16 and #19), leveraging on components and resources from #32, address the Venice LL challenges as described in the previous section. In particular #16 - Water reuse strategic platform, provides decision support to general freshwater saving and the reuse of effluents from municipal WWTPs, while #19 - Sludge management platform, addresses sewage sludge valorisation. It is to be noted that the general and standardisable results from the water pilot (using technology #4) could potentially be integrated into the water reuse strategic platform (#16) and the results for nutrients (using pilots #11) could potentially generate data to be added/integrated to the sludge management platform (#19), supporting the knowledge background for water reuse and nitrogen recovery practices (see Figure 111 and Figure 112).

Figure 111 – The LL Venice pilots and their interaction with WP3 tools

In general, the two platforms complement each other in integrating and providing information to end-users about the two products considered in the Venice LL (the two primary products of WWTPs: treated wastewater and sludge), thus representing together a one-stop-shop for stakeholders willing to take a context-based and data-driven decision about actual and potential CE initiatives and strategies. Although their scope is complementary and the information, indexes and parameters are generally different, they share some common ground that allows users to have a systemic and coherent view on both domains.

First of all, the two platforms share the same spatial scope: the regional one. This is because reuse of both water and sludge have to leverage on information that provide context beyond the local one (with respect to the WWTP) in order to better match necessities and opportunities emerging from different territories and spot the optimal opportunities.

Moreover, both domains share the same data about WWTPs that generate the two products and physically use the same Data Base Management System, so that, if necessary, data from one domain can be used in the other. For example, data about soils characteristics could be used for irrigation purposes.

Figure 112 – The LL Venice tools and data flows

6.2.3 Pre-processing stage and input data

Since tools #16 and #19 have been developed by leveraging on discussions, feedbacks, and collaboration with local stakeholders of the Venice LL, they are based on multidisciplinary and objective schemes, but they must be adapted to other territorial contexts for what concerns values or other specific needs. The multidisciplinary work envisages both the thematic involvement of specific stakeholders on specific focuses (such as retrieving data in terms of source, consistency and methods) and the wider meetings involving quite all the several stakeholders of the valorization chain on more transversal or fundamental issues (such as the analysis of the potential implications linked to the sharing/making available of the data) to precisely identify barriers and pursue the most appropriate solution to reaching objectives.

Therefore the development/adaptation of the tools implies the orchestrated participation of all the stakeholders both in the definition of the concrete objectives to be reached and for the suitable/best information to be put in place (in their turn definable only after identifying those already existing and relative implications), and in the identification of solutions to any direct/indirect problems that may emerge during the work (e.g. policy or institutional implications of data/information retrieval, potential conflicts of interest associated with the sharing of the information).

This requires clarity and sharing of objectives at the start but also a certain ability to remodel and/or renegotiate along the way, finding mediations and solutions where appropriate, to guarantee the achievement of objectives.

The following conceptual tasks, which are interconnected, partly addressed simultaneously and partly in sequence, have to be developed with an important contribution from the local stakeholders. They must be performed to ensure value is delivered to the stakeholders and effective results are produced in an efficient way. The approach is incremental and should be based on agile principles, thus releasing incremental value as soon as possible throughout the cycles.

Identification of the geographical extent of the case of application. Optimal extent for the Venice case is the Regional one, which corresponds to the actual Veneto Region. This choice is determined by the coherence of the local context in terms of regulations (which does not allow to extend too much the geographical extent of the case) and by the necessity to consider enough territory to allow planning strategies on an appropriate scale.

Involvement of key territorial stakeholders for highlighting the specific local characteristics, issues and opportunities. Depending on the local context, different types of stakeholders may be involved. Just as an example, subject involved in the Venice CoP include: Regione Veneto, ARPAV, Città Metropolitana di Venezia, Consorzio di Bonifica Acque Risorgive, ANBI Veneto, Consiglio di Bacino Laguna di Venezia, Viveracqua, Geni civili delle Regione Veneto. Such list includes authorities, government bodies, expert groups and practitioners, water utilities and others.

Co-design of useful indicators and map-based visualizations for supporting decision making of the different stakeholders. This can be done building upon indicators already defined in the Venice LL. Such indicators can be adapted and/or extend to fit the peculiar needs of the territory. The co-design process may use any kind of collaboration technique. In the Venice CoP several meetings have been organized, both with the transversal CoP and with the vertical ones, dedicated to specific subjects. Other specific meetings have been organized with individual stakeholders of CoP subgroups, depending on the necessities and subjects.

Collection of data and information to feed the tools, which can be divided into three main groups:

- Regulations and norms that impact on the case study. This can be done by reusing regulations at EU and, if it is the case, at Italian level that have already been collected for the Venice LL. Regional regulations must be collected for cases different from the Veneto one. National regulations different from the Italian ones must be collected for cases that are not in the Italian territory.
- technologies and treatment trains available on the territory. Similar to the regulations, data available from the Venice LL can be reused and/extended/modified as necessary to the target application.
- data to be used to feed indicators and maps, which may include quality and quantity of effluent and sludge produced, information about WWTPs, river networks, soil conditions, risks connected to WWTP products, etc. Data is collected during the whole process from the involved stakeholders.

Preparation of collected data. Standardized descriptions of technologies and regulation have to be produced, taking into account the input fields prompted by the platform. See Figure 113 for an example of an input-form related to regulations. The input fields include information such as title, source of the regulation, short description, barriers and drivers, comments, notes of the editor, which can be inserted by appropriate roles that have dedicated access rights to the tools.

The screenshot shows the 'BWS Portale Normative' interface. At the top, there is a search bar with the text 'Ricerca per titolo normativa (es: Trattamento acque reflue)' and a blue 'Avvia Ricerca' button. Below the search bar, the page is organized into a grid of sections for a regulation titled 'Trattamento delle acque reflue urbane'. The sections include:

- Fonte Normativa:** Dlg 91/271
- Note Eventuali:** Recepita nel D.Lgs 152/06, Art. 12 c 1: Le acque reflue che siano state sottoposte a trattamento devono essere riutilizzate, ogniqualvolta ciò risulti appropriato. Le modalità di smaltimento devono rendere minimo l'impatto negativo sull'ambiente.
- Titolo Dettaglio:** (91 /271 /CEE) concernente il trattamento delle acque reflue urbane
- Principali Contenuti:** Individua limiti e tipologie dei trattamenti delle acque, dando indicazioni sull'individuazione delle aree sensibili per lo scarico.
- Commenti e Ricadute:** Detta il principio all'art 12; non fornisce indicazioni tecniche.
- Inserito da:** 56
- Qualifiche:** Leva: Art.12 comma 1: "Le acque reflue che siano state sottoposte a trattamento devono essere riutilizzate, ogniqualvolta ciò risulti appropriato. Le modalità di smaltimento devono rendere minimo l'impatto negativo sull'ambiente". Il riutilizzo è subordinato a specifiche autorizzazioni (comma 2)
- Norme Correlate:** Il tema del riuso degli scarichi è diffusamente inserito documenti UE sull'economia circolare, a partire dalla COM(2015) 614 final D.Lgs 152/06 e s.m.l. - recepimento direttiva
- Note Utente:** Non sono state inserite note

Figure 113 - Input fields for managing regulations

Quantitative and qualitative data about effluent and sludge must undergo a normalization procedure so that they can fit the platform database. Layered maps and other geographical data have to be inspected and prepared case-by-case and integrated in the data management layer of the architecture.

Implementation of dashboards. Based on the data collected and prepared and on the indicators that have been agreed with local stakeholders, different map-based visualizations and quantitative evaluations can be implemented and published to the different actors

involved. Dashboards can be accessed selectively by the different types of stakeholders or can be freely accessible, depending on the specific necessities of the case.

6.2.4 Setup process and application

The setup process of tools #16 and #19 require great effort in collecting data and preparing those heterogeneous data for feeding the database of the tools. Once data is received from the relevant stakeholder, depending on the type and quality of data, several operations had to be performed. Such operations may vary for other territories. The next table summarizes the preparation procedures followed for each type of input data and the assumption made for their use.

Table 20 Input data and data preparation procedures

Input data	Data preparation
WWTP information	Information about the WWTS on the Veneto region include their name, geographical position, the name of the reference discharge point, the name of the related watercourse and dimension in terms of design “population equivalent” (PE) served by the plant. This information was pre-processed to make it compliant to the POI Smart Data Model so that WWTPs could be exposed as NGSI-LD entities on the FIWARE Orion Context Broker.
Water quantity	Water quantity requires three main data: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. quantity of effluent produced by the WWTPs and discharged in the river network; Data was carefully collected from the different WWTPs (more than 200). In particular, <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. discharged effluent for years 2020, 2021 and 2022 with unit of measure m³/year b. plants dimension in terms of design PE was classified with respect to different intervals. c. information about risk due to industrial pressure on the WWTP; d. information about treatment procedures per WWTP 2. quantity of water used by the different agricultural and industrial water withdrawal that take water from the river network; Data was collected from both the Regional offices of the Civil Engineering and the ANBI Veneto (regional reclamation consortia association). Actual data is about quantity of water that is allowed to be drawn by each subject from a specified river. The unit of measure is in modules, each of which is 100 l/s 3. volume of water in the rivers is derived from a specific study published by Basin District Authority of Eastern Alps (Piano di Gestione delle Acque – River Basin Management plant). The study provides flow-rate of some of the main rivers and canals of the Veneto Region. The flow rate is provided for each section of the watercourse. Preprocessing of such data was necessary to combine it with the river network already available. The work was done by leveraging on functionalities of QGIS and PostGIS.
Water quality	Water quality includes the following data:

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Chemical and ecological status of watercourses, measured by a network of stations. ARPAV provided the data related to year 2021 with qualitative evaluations for each station (good state, bad state). Specific information on the actual motivation of bad states has to be derived from documents available online on the ARPAV web portal (www.arpa.veneto.it). 2. Chemical and microbiological data from the ARPAV monitoring stations (more than 500 stations) along the significant river courses, for a period of at least 3 years. 3. Chemical and microbiological data of effluent discharged by the WWTPs into the rivers, provided by Veneto Region Water Utilities and/or ARPAV;; a pre-processing work is performed to make the data homogeneous and usable for the tool. Such work includes standardization of names/units of measure, management of values below the detection limit, management of values close to legal thresholds with assessment of number and standard deviation, etc.
Sludge quantity	<p>For each WWTP several data have been collected and uniformed, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • quantity of sludge produced during years 2020, 2021 and 2022, • destination of use for sludge produced in 2022, • information about some treatment phases • risk level associated to the produced sludge
Sludge quality	<p>Data about quality of sludge produced by the WWTPs collected from the different subjects (Veneto Region Water Utilities and/or ARPAV) and a pre-processing and harmonization work is being performed to make the data homogeneous and usable for the tool. Such work includes standardization of names/units of measure, management of values below the detection limit, management of values close to legal thresholds with assessment of number and standard deviation, etc.</p>
Hydrographic network	<p>The necessary data about the river network was provided by ARPAV through a shapefile. Pre-processing procedures were necessary to integrate such data to the rest of the heterogeneous data in order to allow correlation and aggregation of relevant information to the river network. Examples of elaboration include use of QGIS and of its operators for performing complex geographical queries need to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • associate discharge points, agriculture/industrial withdrawal points and water quality measurement stations to the correct segment of the related watercourse; • calculate distances of discharge points, agriculture/industrial withdrawal points, and water quality measurement stations with respect to the source of a main river. This operation is needed to allow the ordering of such entities along the flow of a river. • Associate to each discharge point the list of downstream watercourse segments.
Soil characteristics	<p>The necessary data about the soils and their characteristics was provided by ARPAV through different shapefiles:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • soil usage: artificially modeled territories, agricultural territories, wooded territories and semi-natural areas, humid environment, water environment. • organic carbon present in the surface layers of the soil • metals present in the surface layers of the soil • soil loads of agricultural nitrogen (from livestock and fertilizers) This is not an actual measured data but an estimation at municipal level that combines registered loads, presence of farms and fertilizers sales

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> protected zones (i.e. areas vulnerable to nitrates,..) soil slope <p>Pre-processing procedures where necessary to filter and integrate such data in order to allow correlation and aggregation of relevant information. Examples of elaboration include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Filtering of soils to get only agricultural territories (soil usage) that have a slope lower than 15% (soil slope). Intersection of agricultural territories with protected zones in order to allow different computation for protected and non-protected zones. Generation of separate layers for each type of metal and for each class of concentration.
Regulations	The reference regulations and laws about sludge and wastewater management have been collected and studied at EU, National and Regional level. For each regulation a brief description has been produced with specific information about barriers and drivers. Such information has been entered in the system through a dedicated web application. The application allows not only to enter the descriptions, but also to update them and keep track of the different versions.
Technologies and treatment chains	Data to evaluate/rank environmental and economic impacts (Carbon footprint, O&M costs...) of the different treatment chains are collected from stakeholders and literature and harmonized to allow effective import into the system

Data prepared and inserted in the system database are used to display maps and calculate reference indicators. The following table provides information about the reference indicators and metrics (definition and computation method) identified to measure the state of the art of reuse/valorization on water and related resources in the territory. Through these key indicators it is possible: 1) to calculate gaps with targets already defined, making the diagnosis transparent and shared, by creating the conditions for a common working strategic plan; 2) to individuate the state of the art of valorization with respect to a potential, for defining in a shared manner the un-exploitations and the targets to be reached, given related conveniences and opportunities measured.

Since the collection data is not still totally completed and there is still some interactive work inside the CoP to be done to improve the functionality of the tools, such table must not be considered as definitive.

It might be updated depending on results of the further interactions inside the CoP and data collection that are in course.

Table 21 Indicators supported by the governance model

Name	Geographical scale	COMPUTATION Method
EXPLOITATION index	at REGIONAL SCALE	Water Used/(ResourcesVolume - Min. Outflow) x 100 [%]

Indirect Effluents Contribution to Agricultural Applications	at REGIONAL SCALE at Basins SCALE at sub-basin SCALE	Water discharged with effluents [m3/year]/Freshwater withdrawals for agricultural Uses [m3/year] [%]
Effluents Contributions to Freshwater Restoration	at REGIONAL SCALE at Basins SCALE	Water discharged with effluents [m3/year]/Resources Volume [m3/year] [%]
Effluents Compliance with Quality Reuse Requirements	at REGIONAL SCALE at Basins SCALE	Average quality of some key-parameters/average quality required for the same parameters
Resources Compliance with Quality Reuse Requirements	at REGIONAL SCALE at Basins SCALE	Average quality of some key-parameters/average quality required for the same parameters
AGRICULTURAL	at REGIONAL SCALE	Agricultural withdrawals [m3/year]/Total withdrawals [m3/year] [%]
Electricity production	at REGIONAL SCALE	Withdrawals for Elett.Prod. [m3/year]/Total withdrawals [m3/year] [%]
INDUSTRIES	at REGIONAL SCALE	Withdrawals for INDUSTRY [m3/year]/Total withdrawals [m3/year] [%]
WATER SERVICES	at REGIONAL SCALE	Withdrawals for DRINKING WATER production [m3/year]/Total withdrawals [m3/year] [%]
Carbon footprint (CF) (Avoided)	at REGIONAL SCALE	Carbon Footprint Huber-Bosch Avoided (CFHB - CFSA) ([kg CO ₂ e/kg N]HB*KgN Recovered/year - [kg CO ₂ e/kg N]SAA*KgN Recovered/year) [kg CO ₂ e/year]
Avoidable CF potential	at REGIONAL SCALE	Carbon Footprint Huber-Bosh Avoided [kg CO ₂ e/year]/ Total Potential of CF-Huber-Bosh (HB) avoidability
Potential Organic Carbon for Soil Restoration	at REGIONAL SCALE	Potential Soil Restoration for Organic Carbon [ton/year C]/ Total stressed Soil Area [hectars] [ton/He year]

Potential Soil Sludge Receptivity	at REGIONAL SCALE	TOTAL SOIL RECEPTIVITY (N controlling) = $[\sum (\text{differences between the theoretical applied and limit for each receptive soil}) / \text{N\% in SLUDGE [ton/year] Applicable Sludge}]$
(N controlling)-Sludge Valorization Index	at REGIONAL SCALE	Agricultural Recovery [ton/year] / Potential Soil Sludge Receptivity [ton-year]
Quality Sludge Agricultural Potential	at REGIONAL SCALE	Agricultural Potential Recovery [ton/year] / Total Production [ton-year] [%]
Sludge Agricultural Valorization	at REGIONAL SCALE	Agricultural Recovery [ton/year] / Total Agricultural Potential Recovery [ton-year] [%]
Sludge Energy Potential	at REGIONAL SCALE	Energy Potential Valorization [ton/year] / Total Production [ton-year] [ton-year] [%]
Sludge Energy Valorization	at REGIONAL SCALE	Energy Valorization [ton/year] / Total Energy Potential Valorization [ton-year] [%]
Fertilizer Production Avoided	at REGIONAL SCALE	Mineral N Avoided [ton/year]/ Total Mineral N Applied [ton/year] [%]

Deployment

Both platforms and their components are containerized (user Docker technology) and can be easily deployed on a machine by running the Docker Compose command.

6.2.5 Results

Complete application of the tools #16 and #19 has not been performed at this moment since the data collected is still partial. However, preliminary feedback from CoP members highlights the commitment of the stakeholders in the collective process of defining the tools and putting together the key data so that the tools can be used effectively. Moreover, members of the CoP, when provided with presentations of the state of the tools, always underlined the opportunity of such tools to overcome/avoid information silos that exist/tend to form among the different stakeholders of the water and sludge domain.

Thus, considering that one of the overall objectives of both tool #16 and #19 is to create shared awareness and enable a process of value creation among territorial stakeholders to support standardized, objective and transferable evaluations (and interlocutions) among relevant parties, a first consolidated result is the work done inside the CoP to create the

conditions for an objective and common awareness on opportunities and barriers of reuse itself.

The process of collaboration for building the tools and collecting the necessary data, has contributed to keep raising awareness among stakeholders about the necessity and opportunity to work together towards common objectives. This has been done by finding the right/mediated solutions for final objectives but also for practical issues connected to the tool building, such as the responsibility, implications, risks, expositions in sharing relevant data, or the best way to integrate competencies for achieving higher value for the territory and each subject.

Moreover, such standardized/transferable evaluations are based on a **governance shared evaluation model** represented primarily by the set of indicators defined for the tools (see section 6.2.4) and that are being calculated with data collected from the different stakeholders. Such indicators allow data-driven and **objective decisions** to be **justified and traced** based on evidence and, when necessary, to update such decisions if indicators undergo a significant evolution.

Due to the short duration of the testing phase of the tools on the case study so far, this section will be completed and reported on Milestone 32 at month 45.

6.3 Lessons extracted

Since final results are not available at this moment, this section will be completed and reported through Milestone 32 at month 45, however some preliminary comments can already be extracted.

Tools #16 and #19 have been developed from scratch, based on the requirements and discussions from the CoP and with the support of the existing software components of the Digital Enabler (#32). The complexity of the visualizations and indicators that have emerged, especially related to the available data and to the necessity to perform heavy pre-processing upon them, led to a more challenging work than expected.

Continuous involvement of stakeholders from the Regional territory is a key enabling factor for developing and customizing the tools with respect to the specific characteristics of the case study. This is particularly important concerning data collection and preparation since relevant data are frequently dispersed across different subjects, affected by semantic inconsistencies, structured in different ways, or updated with different frequencies. Some data are not available at all, so assumptions and alternative ways have to be found to estimate their value. Moreover, the sharing of relevant data/information can have political, role and risk implications which are delicate (and could be critical) which require a lot of communication and mediation skills and are time consuming. Making an IT tool of this magnitude requires objective attention and adequate time both in the preliminary phase and in the development phase.

The overall process of development and the future maintenance of the tools require some capabilities in terms of technical skills for integrating (new) data, but especially a key role in facilitating the community and stakeholders towards the realization of common objectives. Such facilitation was necessary until now for data collection and for the definition of required indicators and visualizations, but after the tools are rolled-out, the facilitator should continue to provide its services to keep the tools updated and the overall community active.

Replicability of the tools is expected to be high in terms of the overall governance model, but adaptations are needed for what concerns data integration, since it is likely that other territories (especially out of Italy) have different subjects to be involved, with different data management procedures and different reference data models and procedures. This is why we decided to pursue a standardization effort at least for what concerns water quality and sludge quality parameters. Such effort is leading to the definition of a new FIWARE Smart Data Model related to sludge quality and to the extension of the existing FIWARE Smart Data Model related to water quality.

6.4 Summary table of the LL

Table 22: Summary table for LL Venice

Title	Enable reuse of treated wastewater, nutrient recovery and sewage sludge valorisation in the Venice LL
Description	<p>In the Venice Living Lab the application of resource recovery and circular economy in the field of water, especially wastewater, are strategic to achieve climate change resilience. Currently, the pursuit of these goals is slowed and prevented due to several issues (technical but mainly regulatory) related to wastewater process management, not much to effluents from wastewater treatment plants, rather when referring to nutrients and sludge. The limits and slowdown of the virtuous paths towards resource recovery and circular economy are also sensibly linked to a lack of shared and transparent knowledge on the quality and opportunities connected to the reuse itself, and to an over evaluation of risks which together lead to a low social acceptance. There are several goals in Venice LL: i) the contribution to complete the reuse goals envisaged (but not still reached) by another important funded regional project (the Integrated Fusina Project PIF) which, alongside other important reclamation goals for the industrial area, provides for the reuse of the effluent of the municipal treatment plant (WWTP) Fusina for "non-potable" purposes; ii) the possibility of resource recovery from wastewater processes for high quality fertilizer production and carbon footprint reduction; iii) tackling the tough issue of the management of sludge produced by municipal WWTPs, still profoundly conditioned by a limited vision and knowledge which condition the choice and can hinder the pursuit of the most sustainable management pathway (such as its physiological destination to the environment and to the soil).</p> <p>The main technical solutions prosed are: i) a combinatory pilot plant (UF unit + RO unit + EDI unit), tested on Fusina WWTP effluent for industrial water reuse; ii) two pilot stripping technologies, tested on concentrated WWTP stream(s) for ammonium sulphate production; iii) two IT platforms, the Water Reuse Strategic Platform and the</p>

	Sludge Management Platform, to assess the best reuse opportunities and valorization pathways firstly at local/Regional scale and then transferable at National/EU scale for water and sludge respectively.
Reference point	https://goo.gl/maps/FBnME73MamtBh1pT9
Location	Veneto Region
Country (-ies)	Italy
URL	https://decidim.cop-venice.eu/
Project	B-WaterSmart
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water Scarcity, • Limitations to water reuse and recovery due to low acceptance, • Untapped efficiency potential of water resources, • Need for reuse and recovery schemes for wastewater & sludge,
Tools/Product/Services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water reuse strategic platform (#16) • Sludge management platform (#19) • Digital Enabler (#32)
Technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compact combinatory treatment technologies for industrial water reuse (#4) • Ammonia recovery from concentrated WWTP streams (#11)
Scales	Regional (across several municipalities and/or administrative borders, incl. rural areas),
Legislation	Several legislations are applicable at EU, Italian and Regional level. The full list is available through the specific functionality of the tool.
Synergistic benefits	To be reported in MS32
Facts of the applied technologies	NA
Key Performance Indicators	To be reported in MS32
Requirements and conditions	To be reported in MS32
Key lessons	To be reported in MS32
Lessons learned from technology operation	<p>Continuous involvement of territorial stakeholders is a key enabling factor for developing and customizing the tools with respect to the specific characteristics of the case study. This is particularly important for what concerns data collection and preparation since relevant data are frequently dispersed across different subjects, affected by semantic inconsistencies, structured in different ways, updated with different frequencies. Some data are not available at all, so assumptions and alternative ways have to be found to estimate their value.</p> <p>The overall process of development and the future maintenance of the tools require some capabilities in terms of technical skills for integrating (new) data, but especially a key role in facilitating the community and stakeholders towards the realization of common objectives. Such facilitation was necessary until now for data collection and</p>

	for the definition of required indicators and visualizations, but after the tools are rolled-out, the facilitator should continue to provide its services to keep the tools updated and the overall community active.
Technology performance and best practices	Replicability of the tools is expected to be high in terms of the overall governance model, but adaptations are needed for what concerns data integration, since it is likely that other territories (especially out of Italy) have different subjects to be involved, with different data management procedures and different reference data models and procedures. This is why we decided to pursue a standardization effort at least for what concerns water quality and sludge quality parameters. Such effort is leading to the definition of a new FIWARE Smart Data Model related to sludge quality and to the extension of the existing FIWARE Smart Data Model related to water quality.
Outcome of assessments	To be reported in MS32
Organisations	VERI, ENG, ETRA, HYDR, DEPU, SINTEF
Contact persons	Patrizia Ragazzo (VERITAS, p.ragazzo@gruppovertas.it); Nicoletta Chiuccini (VERITAS, n.chiuccini@gruppovertas.it); Rita Ugarelli (SINTEF, rita.ugarelli@sintef.no)
Data Manager	Davide Storelli, davide.storelli@eng.it, Engineering Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A.
Costs	To be defined
Tags	Sludge management, water reuse, nutrient/energy recovery, resource recovery, circular economy
Publications/Reference	NA
Images	<p>The image shows a screenshot of the BWaterSmart Info interface. On the left, there is a dark sidebar with the BWaterSmart logo and the text 'BWaterSmart Info'. Below the logo, there are three sections: 'Fiume PRINCIPALE' (represented by a blue line), 'Fiume SECONDARIO' (represented by a black line), and 'AFFLUENTI' (represented by a red line). Below these sections are two buttons labeled 'SONINA' and 'PIAVE'. On the right, there is a map showing a network of water infrastructure. A legend in the bottom right corner identifies symbols for 'Scarico' (black square), 'Presa agronomica' (green square), 'Fiume' (blue line), and 'Rilevazione' (black circle). The map also shows various geographical features and labels.</p>

Caption/Source

Map of the watercourses impacted by a specific WWTP effluents
 Map of soil characteristics and WWTPs, with specific focus on the soil characteristics
 is a specific point selected by the user

7 Tools and Methods for LL Lisbon

7.1 Key WS challenges, ambition and case study description

Lisbon has a smart management strategy for all key areas of urban development. The city aims at providing high quality of life for an increasing population and growing economy, whilst tackling climate change challenges based on a green-blue problem-solving infrastructure. As such, the key smart-water **challenges** of the Lisbon Living Lab (Lisbon LL) targeted in BWS are (i) a growing resident population and economy, dependent on distant freshwater resources (up to 100 km), (ii) climate challenges (e.g., droughts and floods) and (iii) need to increase urban green areas. Actions to address these challenges include (i) improving the water supply / demand management and ultimately the city’s water-energy-phosphorus (WEP) footprint while increasing the green areas, (ii) promoting the safe use of alternative sources (e.g., reclaimed water), and (iii) promoting climate-ready (water-energy efficient, climate-change proof) housing. Figure 114 presents the **Lisbon LL ambition**.

Figure 114: The Lisbon LL ambition.

The Lisbon LL gathers six partners working for these goals:

- **CML** (Lisbon Municipality) is the Lisbon case-study problem owner; as such, CML makes the city’s data and resources available as a living lab in the project, promotes the Lisbon Community of Practice (CoP), participates in the BWS Innovation Alliance, tests the Lisbon LL solutions developed within the project and plays a key role in disseminating and promoting the adoption of these solutions among its extensive

networking platforms. CML also develops the urban water cycle observatory, through a linked third-party – LEN (Lisboa E-Nova).

- **LNEC** (Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil) is the mentor and R&I partner for the Lisbon LL, responsible, among others, for the development of the knowledge, methodologies and analytics behind the tools of (health and environment) risk assessment, reclaimed water quality modelling in the distribution network, WEP balance, and decision support of alternative courses of action based on performance-cost-risk indicators. LNEC also participates in the development of the water reclamation protocol for potable water reuse in beverage industry for artisanal craft beer production.
- **ADTA** (Águas do Tejo Atântico) is the water utility enabler of Lisbon LL, providing real data (on wastewater treatment and water reclamation) for several tools and is responsible for conducting the pilot tests needed to develop the water reclamation protocol for potable water reuse in craft beer production.
- **ADENE** (Agência para a Energia) is a solution provider responsible for developing the knowledge and the tool for climate-readiness certification.
- **Baseform** is a solution provider responsible for developing the software for the risk assessment, reclaimed water quality modelling in the distribution network, WEP balance and decision-support tools.
- **ICS-UL** (Instituto de Ciências Sociais da Universidade de Lisboa) is a cross-cutting R&I partner integrating the social sciences and humanities and is the Lisbon CoP moderator.

Case study description

Lisbon LL aims (i) to demonstrate the potential for safe potable water reuse in the beverage industry in the **mid to long run**, and (ii) in the **short term**, to promote water (and related energy and phosphorus) efficiency, water smart allocation (fit-for-purpose quality), circular economy, and safe non-potable urban water reuse, work that is to be developed within the following tasks:

- Task 2.4.1 Protocol for water production from wastewater;
- Task 2.4.2 Water matrix and concepts behind water observatory;
- Task 2.4.3a Urban WEP balance;
- Task 2.4.3b Risk management - health component;
- Task 2.4.3c Risk management - groundwater component;
- Task 2.4.3d Reclaimed water quality modelling in the distribution system;
- Task 2.4.4 Water-smart for climate ready certificates.

7.2 Application of tools and methods

7.2.1 Selected tools and technologies of pilots

Lisbon LL developed methods, algorithms, and software for a smart allocation of the water

quality (fit-for-purpose) and quantity (water efficiency) in the city (Figure 115), delivering the following Data Application Products (DAPs):

- **Tool #20 - Urban Water Cycle Observatory**, to systematise, collect and facilitate access to data at the city level and at the single users/consumers level (DAP 2).
- **Tool #24** – Reclaimed water quality in the distribution network, for modelling reclaimed water quality in the distribution network (DAP 2).
- **Tool #25** - Water-Energy-Phosphorus balance planning, a module for the quantification of the city water cycle components and assessment of water-energy-phosphorus balance for non-potable uses (DAP 2).
- **Tool #27** - Risk assessment for urban water reuse, a module for the implementation of alternative water sources (DAP 6).
- **Tool #17 - Environment for decision support and selection of alternative courses of action**, a decision support tool for WEP sustainable management based on performance-cost-risk assessment (DAP 2), which integrates the above three tools (#24, #25, #27)
- **Tool #33 – Climate readiness certification**, with climate-readiness index and the subsequent auditing/certification mechanism for Climate Readiness of households, buildings and neighbourhoods (DAP 10).

Furthermore, a protocol for food-grade water production from treated wastewater by ozone/reverse osmosis for craft beer production is being demonstrated for communicating and disseminating (C&D) safe water reuse and thus building trust in this resilient, rainfall-independent water source. The development of this **Technology Product** (TP), TP1, does not involve software production, and consequently there is no link to T3.5 in this case.

Figure 115: The LL Lisbon tools.

The links with Lisbon LL **pilots** (WP2, tasks 2.4) are the following (Figure 116):

- TP#1 / task 2.4.1: 1 ozone oxidation/reverse osmosis (O3/RO) pilot installed at Beirolas water resource recovery facility (WRRF) for demonstration of water reuse in the food industry, namely, in artisanal craft beer production (direct potable reuse, DPR).
- Tool#25, Tool#27, and Tool#17 (and at city level, Tool#20) / task 2.4.3 (and task 2.4.2): 10 green urban areas for WEP sustainable management based on performance-cost-risk assessment, comprising 2 non-potable water uses (irrigation and landscape lakes) and 4 potential water sources, two currently used (drinking water and groundwater) and two new, i.e., reclaimed water and spring water from the Águas Livres aqueduct.
- Tool#24 / task 2.4.3: 3 reclaimed water distribution systems (RWDSs) for water quality modelling (1 rooftop-garden's irrigation circuit, 1 reclaimed water distribution network in the city (near "Frente Ribeirinha"), 1 park's irrigation circuit), to support the residual chlorine management for a safe water supply;
- Tool#33 / task 2.4.4: 9 pilots for water-smart climate-readiness certification (3 households, 3 buildings, 3 neighbourhoods).

Figure 116: The LL Lisbon pilots.

7.2.2 Integrative use of tools, pilot interaction and data flows

Making Lisbon a water-smarter city implies the involvement of different stakeholders in the provision and use of water. Thus, the Lisbon LL is focused on the development of software tools to facilitate safe water reuse and improve water-energy-phosphorous efficiency in non-potable uses, improving Lisbon's climate resilience to water scarcity. The following approaches were considered for the desired transformation into a water-smarter society:

- To increase the citizens' awareness about the local context regarding the water use in the city via the provision of appellative information on water consumption, wastewater treatment, and fit-for-purpose water use, particularly, safe water reuse.
- To inform individual entities (public or private major water consumers) about their water consumption, in case of smart water metering, and increase their awareness on wastewater treatment and fit-for-purpose water use, particularly, safe water reuse.
- To support the decision-making process of water demand planners and managers in urban, municipal and water utility contexts, by delivering an overview of the current water supply and water demand in the city to enable prioritizing strategic and tactical planning options.

- To guide or assess the promotion of climate adaptation in housing via a certification process used by housing owners and planners.

The level of integration between these tools naturally depends on the purpose for which they are used, which in turn is associated with the target user. Thus, the software applications developed at the Lisbon LL were designed to work as follows:

- Use of the **tool #20** alone with two distinct objectives in mind:
 - To increase the citizens' awareness of the urban water cycle by providing yearly-based, easy-to-read information on the city's water cycle (public access, top-down approach).
 - To promote an easier, faster, and more flexible way to access the detailed water consumption data on water facilities (usually, large consumers) and to provide a repository of information (private access, bottom-up approach).
- Integrated use of **tools #17, #24, #25, and #27** with the following objective:
 - To support urban management authorities and water utilities in making smart and climate-resilient water decisions for an efficient water-energy-nutrient balance in the city including safe water reuse, by enabling direct comparison of alternatives for matching water supply and water demand to satisfy specific non-potable uses.
- Use of the **tool #33** alone with two distinct objectives in mind:
 - To guide the design and assessment of the climate readiness potential of existing households, buildings or neighbourhoods.

Although they were not designed for integrated use in a single decision-making process, there are links between tools #20 and #33 and between these and the #17_#24_#25_#27 tool group:

- From tool #20 to tool #25 - detailed information on water consumption locations, e.g., municipal green areas, when using the private access mode.
- From tool #17 to tool #20 or to tool #33 – general information on water management planning broken down by alternative water sources, as well as information on water related energy and phosphorus content.

Tools #17, #24, #25, and #27 were designed for **integrated use**, with each tool representing a step in the decision-making process (Figure 117), namely:

- Step 1 (tool #25) – Matchmaking of water sources (potential supplies) and water demands to enable the design of supply chain solutions (the shorter and more circular the better) to a set of potential users of non-potable water, namely, reclaimed water and other water sources alternative to those currently in use (e.g., groundwater). The supply/demand alternative combinations (matches) over a target period are assessed through a range of performance and cost metrics, for supporting strategic and tactical

(aligned) planning (e.g., volume availability, cost, energy content, carbon footprint, nutrient content). This step produces the alternative combinations targeted for decision-making in step 4.

- Step 2 (tool #24) – In case of reclaimed water use, it is convenient to map and quantify risk in the water distribution network. This tool is a complete hydraulic and water quality extended-period simulation model for pressure flow networks. It complements Tool #25 in assessing the additional cost, risk and performance changes that may be required for the supply/demand combinations chosen to make use of existing or new distribution networks.
- Step 3 (tool #27) – In case of reclaimed water use, it is necessary to assess human health and environmental risk considering the applicable legislation (e.g., the Portuguese Decree-Law 119/2019) and the best practice as presented, for example, in relevant ISO standards (series ISO 16075 Guidelines for treated wastewater use for irrigation projects (2020, 2021), ISO 20426:2018 Guidelines for health risk assessment and management for non-potable water reuse and ISO 20761:2018 Guidelines for water reuse safety evaluation), based on which the EU Regulation 2020/741⁸ on minimum requirements for water reuse in agricultural irrigation was developed. Tool #27 works as a risk-based gatekeeper that must be cleared for any supply/demand combination to be considered for assessment in Tool #17. Depending on the risk level targeted for completion, it will be rejected (eventually go back to tool #25 for redesign), or otherwise cleared and move on to Tool #17.
- Step 4 (tool #17) – For all matchmaking alternatives, a final prioritization between the supply/demand combinations developed in Tool #25 and qualified by Tools #24 and #27 support the decision on the course of action for a water-smarter city, for the specific case studied or others within comparable contexts. This tool is designed to enable users to select the best water source combinations to satisfy specific non-potable uses, and to align with strategic and tactical planning options on the governance of water sources and water uses in an urban setting. As previously referred, the supply/demand alternative combinations are assessed and prioritized through a subset of standardized, user-selected key performance/cost/risk metrics, extracted from those employed to qualify the initial selection in Tool #25 (e.g., volume availability, cost, energy content, carbon footprint, nutrient content) and to further qualify the risk assessment in Tool #27, as well as in Tool #24, if applicable, e.g., in case a network to distribute very-high quality reclaimed water for unrestricted urban

⁸ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32020R0741>

uses (class A, according to Decree-law 119/2019⁹ and EU reg 2020/741¹⁰) is needed, as in Lisbon city (Lisbon LL).

Figure 118 illustrates the data flows among tools #17, #24, #25, and #27 and the pilots.

Figure 117: The LL Lisbon tools for a smarter water demand management and pilot interaction (step-by-step process).

⁹ <https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/detalhe/decreto-lei/119-2019-124097549>

¹⁰ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32020R0741>

Granularity: city/ city zone/ city facility

Figure 118: The LL Lisbon tools for a smarter water demand management and pilot data flows (start from top, tool #25).

7.2.3 Pre-processing stage and input data

The necessary steps and processes that need to be fulfilled before being able to apply the Lisbon LL tools along with related technologies are presented in Table 23 to Table 28. For each tool, the related WP2 task(s) for pilot data collection is(are) presented.

The Pre-Processing Stage includes the following aspects: identification of relevant actors, definition of case extent, definition of baseline, collection and edition of input data, conduction of workshops, and installation of equipment.

The Input Data is organized in the following aspects: primary data, background data, water data, and additional data.

Table 23: Data requirements for tool #17

T3.5 tools		#17 Environment for decision support and selection of alternative courses of action
T2.4 subtasks		T2.4.3a Urban W-E-P balance T2.4.3b Risk management - health component T2.4.3c Risk management - groundwater component T2.4.3d Reclaimed water quality modelling in the distribution system
Pre-processing stage	Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water demand planners and decision-makers in urban management, municipal, and water utility contexts.
	Case extent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Link to other strategic and tactical planning options related to water management in an urban setting, e.g., feeding the infrastructure asset management planning.
	Baseline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The high-level goal of this tool is to enable users to select the best combination of water sources to satisfy specific non-potable uses, and to enable prioritisation of strategic and tactical planning options on water management ?? in an urban setting.
	Input data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Metrics from Tools #25 and #27, as well as from Tool #24, if applicable (i.e., when the possible degradation of the distributed water quality is a critical point in the reuse system, namely, when the reclaimed water is class A).
	Workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP1/T1.3 training action scheduled for April 18, 2024
Input data	Primary data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Metrics employed to qualify the initial selection in Tool #25 (e.g., volume availability, cost, energy content, carbon footprint, nutrient content, geolocation) and for further qualification through risk assessment in Tool #27 and potentially in Tool #24, if applicable, as illustrated in Figure 118 and listed in Table 25, Table 26, and Table 27, respectively.
	Background data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Municipal policy/plans, e.g., on water reuse and climate action.
	Water data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The water data relevant (i.e. the primary data above) for tools #24, #25, and #27, illustrated in Figure 118 and listed in Table 25, Table 26, and Table 27, respectively.

Table 24: Data requirements for tool #20

T3.5 tool		#20 Urban Water Cycle Observatory
T2.4 subtask		T2.4.2 Water matrix and concepts behind water observatory
Pre-processing stage	Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public access – citizens, urban management authorities, academia, NGOs, media, and other key stakeholders. Private access – municipalities (especially, Lisbon municipality in the scope of the Lisbon LL), private institutions of public interest, private entities with large water consumption.

	Case extent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This tool can function as a data repository.
	Baseline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public access – provision of information on an annual basis, related with main water flows, consumption disaggregation (by type of use and type of user), amount of treated wastewater and reclaimed water production. Private access – visualization of aggregated consumptions and costs per typology of water use, water consumption evolution, and individual consumption analysis.
	Input data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public access – collection of annual open data regarding the city’s urban water cycle (drinking water, wastewater and reclaimed water), edition privileges the use of infographics. Private access – collection of water consumption data registered through smart meters, edition via a set of analytics.
	Workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP1/T1.3 training action scheduled for November 16, 2023
	Equipment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Private access – water smart meters
Input data	Primary data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public access – open data of water consumption, wastewater treatment, and reclaimed water production in the city. Private access – smart meter data on water consumption, location of the consumption points.
	Background data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Municipal policy/plans, e.g., on water reuse and climate action.
	Water data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The same as primary data.

Table 25: Data requirements for tool #24

T3.5 tools		#24 Reclaimed water quality model in the distribution network
T2.4 subtasks		T2.4.3d Reclaimed water quality modelling in the distribution system
Pre-processing stage	Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hydraulic engineering experts in urban management, municipal, and water utility contexts.
	Case extent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assessment of the need for disinfection and residual chlorine in the design of distribution networks or, in the case of already constructed networks, to evaluate the disinfection efficiency and introduce adjustments as needed for water safety.
	Baseline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Complete hydraulic and water quality extended-period simulation model for pressure flow networks, designed to simulate the advection, mixing, and transformation of waterborne parameters and the chlorine decay (residual disinfectant management) in reclaimed water.
	Input data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This tool includes complete descriptors for network assets, demands, operational constraints and rules, and state variables describing hydraulics, travel time, and advection/transformation of water quality parameters (incl. free- or combined chlorine content).
	Workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP1/T1.3 training action scheduled for February/ 15, 2024
	Equipment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water smart meters, chlorine sensors, etc.

Input data	Primary data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water demand descriptors. Reclaimed water supply descriptors.
	Background data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Municipal policy/plans, e.g., on water reuse, water losses management.
	Water data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water quality (WQ) descriptors: WQ boundary conditions (e.g., chlorine concentration, ammonium concentration), WQ formulation(s) Water network operation descriptors: e.g., flow, velocity, pressure.
	Additional data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Network descriptors: e.g., irrigation network plant, pipe diameters, location of irrigation devices (e.g., sprinklers), irrigation schedule.

Table 26: Data requirements for tool #25

T3.5 tools		#25 Water-Energy-Phosphorus balance planning
T2.4 subtasks		T2.4.3a Urban W-E-P balance
Pre-processing stage	Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Planners and decision-makers in urban management, municipal, and water utility contexts
	Case extent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The tool is applicable to any demand-driven matchmaking problem (as it is, requiring no modification).
	Baseline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Standardized means to combine and assess water source combinations to satisfy specific demands.
	Input data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The matchmaking environment is driven by the demand(s) to be satisfied, translated as time series of required monthly volumes over a pre-specified period. The supply and demand alternative combinations are assessed through a range of user-selected metrics (e.g., volume availability, cost, energy content, carbon footprint, nutrient content).
	Workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP1/T1.3 training action scheduled for April 18, 2024.
	Equipment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water meters – supply and demand.
Input data	Primary data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water demand descriptors. Water supply descriptors.
	Background data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Municipal policy/plans, e.g., on water reuse and climate action. National regulations: e.g., Decree-Law 119/2019 on water reuse. European regulations: e.g., Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (recast) (new proposal under approval).
	Water data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water descriptors: volumes (availability/supply and consumption/demand), water price (supply). Related energy descriptors: energy content water (supply). Related phosphorus descriptors: P concentration in reclaimed water (supply).

	Additional data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alternative specific costs: CAPEX and OPEX, energy. Carbon footprint.
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Table 27: Data requirements for tool #27

T3.5 tools		#27 Risk assessment for urban water reuse
T2.4 subtasks		T2.4.3b Risk management - health component T2.4.3c Risk management - groundwater component
Pre-processing stage	Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water demand planners and decision-makers in urban management, municipal and water utility contexts.
	Case extent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human health and environmental risk assessment associated to water reuse in agriculture.
	Baseline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Standardized means for building the hazard exposure scenarios and to assess the risk associated with each scenario.
	Input data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Descriptors of the main features of the urban facility (e.g., public park) that may impact the human and environment exposure to the hazards present in the reclaimed water. Human health and environmental risk assessment requires basic knowledge of risk management and of the legislation applicable to water reuse.
	Workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP1/T1.3 training action scheduled for March 14, 2024.
Input data	Primary data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water demand descriptors relevant for risk assessment.
	Background data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Municipal policy/plans, e.g., on water reuse and climate action. National (Portuguese) regulation: Decree-Law 119/2019 on water reuse. European regulation: Reg. (EU) 741/2020 on minimum requirements for water reuse in agricultural irrigation. International standards: e.g., ISO 16075-2:2020, ISO 20426:2018, ISO 20761:2018.
	Water data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reclaimed water quality.
	Additional data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On risk treatment measures.

Table 28: Data requirements for tool #33

T3.5 tool		#33 Climate readiness certification
T2.4 subtask		T2.4.4 Water-smart for climate ready certificates
Pre-processing stage	Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Householders, urban planners, municipalities, building industry, and Climate Ready Certificates auditors.
	Case extent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Link to other housing certification system.

	Baseline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A single certificate to assess the water efficiency, the water-energy nexus performance, and the climate adaptation evaluation of households, buildings, and neighbourhoods. The evaluated projects can be in the design phase, new construction, or in use.
	Input data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The CRC methodology has closed questions that can be answered by a single option, multiple options or percentages. Each of the 96 evaluation criteria has an associated score and the answers are ordered by descending score.
	Workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP1/T1.3 training action scheduled for December 12, 2023
	Equipment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water meters, water pressure sensors.
Input data	Primary data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Households, buildings, and neighbourhoods – description of water distribution network and related equipment and devices
	Background data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Municipal policy/plans, e.g., on water reuse and climate action. European standards: e.g., EN 16941 series on on-site non-potable water systems.
	Water data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water quality descriptors: e.g., chlorine concentration (if water supplies (e.g., treated greywater) other than drinking water are used for non-potables uses). Water network descriptors: e.g., flow rates, pressure.
	Additional data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy descriptors (onsite systems): e.g., energy consumption in water distribution, energy consumption in water treatment. Climate adaptation descriptors: e.g., climate risks maps, climate adaptation measures targeted to housing.

7.2.4 Setup process and application

Table 29 to Table 34 present information about the setup process and application of the Lisbon LL tools #17, #20, #24, #25, #27, and #33, respectively. For each tool, the related WP2 task(s) for pilot data collection is (are) presented.

Table 29: Setup process and application: tool #17

T3.5 tool	#17 Environment for decision support and selection of alternative courses of action
T2.4 subtask	T2.4.3a Urban W-E-P balance
	T2.4.3b Risk management - health component
	T2.4.3c Risk management - groundwater component
	T2.4.3d Reclaimed water quality modelling in the distribution system

Data inputs and model initialisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The tool allows for the specification of the key parameters: objectives, timesteps, metrics, alternatives. There is also the ability to import or export from/to a dedicated Excel® format, which facilitates sharing of results or further manipulation of the analysis. When the tool is started, it displays the available analyses (imported from tool #25) as well as the option to create a new one. When an alternative is created here, its values are either typed in on this screen or imported using the Excel® import/export facility. An analysis contains a set of alternatives, a set of metrics to assess them, over a set of timesteps. It may include the specification of different scenarios (external contexts).
Parameters and assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Most of the metrics are imported directly from a linked Matchmaking analysis (tool #25), along with the alternatives, using the option available through the last item on the menu of tool #17. The user can also add new metrics directly on this environment filling out the Data Table, which contains the metrics' values for each alternative at each time step. This applies to water reuse risk metrics (tools #24 and #27). Other metrics can be defined by the user. The user introduces in the Metrics Editor the relationship between the metric's 'real world' values and a standardized 0-to-3 scale that is used throughout the app, effectively turning each metric into an index. Metrics may be given a relative weight from a closed list (0.5, 1, 2) – this is used later when ranking the alternatives.
Temporal or spatial scales	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monthly, annual Neighbourhood, city, region
Design of scenarios	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The baseline scenario corresponds to the “business as usual” alternative (first year of the planning timeline). The supply and demand alternative combinations are assessed over a targeted period (planning horizon). The time frame for evaluating the impact of the plan is the analysis horizon. The 3D cube of tool #17 provides an overview of the decisional problem with the 3 dimensions – alternatives (Z-axis) over time (Y-axis) and across all metrics (X-axis) – simultaneously displayed. This allows for a unique overall perception of the dynamics of decision among the alternatives.
Deployment of the tool	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This tool may be applied to any decisional problem of the same type (alternatives vs. metrics over time). In the implementation that is embodied in Tool #17, it is designed to work in tandem with Tool #25 and assess the supply/demand matchmaking alternatives developed there.

Table 30: Setup process and application: tool #20

T3.5 tool	#20 Urban Water Cycle Observatory
T2.4 subtask	T2.4.2 Water matrix and concepts behind water observatory
Data inputs and model initialisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public access – open data on water consumption, wastewater treatment, and reclaimed water production in the city. Private access – water consumption per facility, aggregation per type of use, associated costs, performance indicators, georeferencing of facilities.

Parameters and assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tool #20 allows the identification and quantification of the main water flows in the city of Lisbon, disaggregating, whenever possible, the consumption by type of user and type of use. In this sense, the information provided allows the characterization of the Lisbon's territory regarding water supply and wastewater collection and treatment.
Temporal and spatial scales	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In terms of scale application, public access has a broader implementation at the city scale, as the private access can be implemented at an entity or even at a single water meter scale.
Design of scenarios	N/A
Deployment of the tool	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public access – is in use by the Lisbon Municipality in the scope of the Lisbon Living Lab. Additionally, it is starting to be well known by citizens, resident's associations, NGOs, etc. • Private access – is in use by the Lisbon Municipality in the scope of the Lisbon Living Lab. Additionally, there are two other entities, associated to Lisboa E-Nova, that are using this private access for water, such as the public passenger transport company (buses and trams).

Table 31: Setup process and application: tool #24

T3.5 tool	#24 Reclaimed water quality model in the distribution network
T2.4 subtask	T2.4.3d Reclaimed water quality modelling in the distribution system
Data inputs and model initialisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cadastral and demand data and operational parameters to simulate the movement, mixing, and dynamics of key reclaimed water parameters throughout the network. • The primary input for the hydraulic and water quality model is an Epanet.INP file and an EPANET MSX file, respectively. The model runs based on those two files and the interface allows for querying of results as well as full visualisation in Baseform's 3D environment.
Parameters and assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parameters for water quality modelling of reclaimed water distribution networks, incorporating sensor data (e.g., flow, chlorine residuals, temperature, turbidity, pH).
Temporal and spatial scales	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minutes, days. • Urban water distribution network or bulk water network.
Design of scenarios	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This tool offers a unique standardized means to compare reclaimed water supply/demand combinations through multiple criteria, with a purposefully developed formulation for reclaimed water (for non-potable, unrestricted urban reuse in Lisbon LL), on top of advanced hydraulics simulation capabilities.
Deployment of the tool	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The tool #24's model is self-contained and as such may be used on its own to fulfil its primary purpose. However, in the context of the project, it aims at being used in conjunction with tool #25 to qualifying the supply/demand alternatives developed there, from the viewpoint of assessing the risks incurred in transport and distribution of the reclaimed water, in the Lisbon LL case, for non-potable, unrestricted urban reuse.

Table 32: Setup process and application: tool #25

T3.5 tool	#25 Water-Energy-Phosphorus balance planning
T2.4 subtask	T2.4.3a Urban W-E-P balance
Data inputs and model initialisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The tool allows for the specification of the key parameters: geo location of water demands and water supplies, metrics (e.g., costs, energy content, carbon footprint, nutrient content), alternative descriptors. The tool allows the import of time series from a dedicated Excel® format for the following data: water volumes (availability/supply and consumption/demand), water price (supply), phosphorus content in water (supply), phosphorus fertilization (demand). These data series consist of the user's forecast for the evolution of the values of these variables over the planning period. When the tool is started, the user is asked to register potential sources, with corresponding time series of available volumes taking place in the same time window, though not necessarily spanning its entirety. The user is then asked to combine the available sources to make up the required monthly volumes, while complying with the energy and nutrients contents as desired. Such combinations are called 'alternatives' and are characterized by the degree to which they satisfy the required volumes over time, as well as by their energy consumption, nutrients contents, and cost. One or more alternatives will be designed to solve the demand problem at stake.
Parameters and assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The supply and demand alternative combinations are assessed and matched through a range of user-selected metrics (e.g., volume availability, cost, energy content, carbon footprint, nutrient content) over a targeted period.
Temporal and spatial scales	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monthly, annual. Urban facility (e.g., public park), neighbourhood, city, region (the software allows for full geographic representation of the sources and demands).
Design of scenarios	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> When the tool #25 is started, it displays the available analyses as well as the option to create a new one (top right). An analysis contains one or more matchmaking alternatives for a given supply/demand application case, as well as a set of metrics and a range of analysis timesteps.
Deployment of the tool	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The tool #25 is autonomous and may be deployed on its own or in conjunction with tools #17 and #27. The tool is applicable to any demand-driven matchmaking problem without requiring modification.

Table 33: Setup process and application: tool #27

T3.5 tool	#27 Risk assessment for urban water reuse
T2.4 subtasks	T2.4.3b Risk management - health component T2.4.3c Risk management - groundwater component

<p>Data inputs and model initialisation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In each alternative, each urban facility (e.g., public park) with water demand satisfied with reclaimed water is tested for human health and for environmental risks. • Tool #27 provides a structured analysis of the water reuse system. In the menu “Configuration”, the user is asked to describe the following groups of information: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ “Components” organized in 5 subgroups: “Hazards”, “Exposure routes”, “Exposure sites”, “Activities”, and “Population or environment at risk”. The user must fill in the fields “Category” and “Name” of every component. ○ “Barriers”, including the indication of “Name”, “Expected Log removal value”, “Number of barriers”, and “Reference” of this information. ○ “Preventive measures”. For each one, the user must fill in the field “Name” of every measure. ○ “Hazardous events”. The user must fill in the field “Name” of every hazardous event. • The data input in the configuration menu provides the necessary information for the risk assessment process, which is organised in the following steps: risk identification, risk analysis and risk treatment. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The risk analysis is carried out in the “Analysis” menu, scenario by scenario. After selecting the demand (i.e., a green area irrigated with reclaimed water), the user describes the scenarios together with the respective risk assessment using the menu “Create scenario”. This menu sequentially presents a set of fields that are filled in with information provided in the "configuration" menu or require rating of the likelihood of exposure to hazards or the potential damage to the population or environment at risk.
<p>Parameters and assumptions</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The risk analysis is done for every defined exposure scenario, assigning to each scenario a rating for the likelihood of exposure to the hazards, as well as a rating of the harm that might result to the recipient (persons and environment). The levels used for the classification of likelihood and harm are predefined (i.e., not available for configuration by the user). • The risk assessment ends with the comparison of the results of the risk analysis with the established criteria to determine whether the residual risk is tolerable, using a risk matrix.
<p>Temporal and spatial scales</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Annual. • Urban facility (e.g., public park).

Design of scenarios	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tool #27 is a standardized means for building hazard exposure scenarios and assessing the risk related to each scenario. • Exposure scenarios set out how and under what circumstances people and the environment may be exposed to hazards. To facilitate the construction of exposure scenarios to hazards, a structured methodology was developed based on three questions: "what?", "why?", and "how?" (Ribeiro and Rosa, 2022). In the first moment ("what"), an analysis of the water reuse system is made to identify the constituent elements, those that may be at the basis of the risk. Next ("why"), the link between the elements of the system is identified. Finally ("how"), credible combinations between system elements are described that correspond to normal situations of system use that may, through the influence of hazardous events, result in a risk to the recipients. This methodology is embedded in tool #27.
Deployment of the tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The tool #27 is autonomous and may be deployed on its own or in conjunction with tools #17 and #25. The tool is applicable to human health and environmental risk assessment related with water reuse in irrigation and other non-potable urban uses, aligning with principles established in European and Portuguese legislation (Reg. (EU) 741/202 and Decree-Law 119/2019, respectively), as well as with relevant ISO standards (e.g., ISO 16075-2:2020 and ISO 20426:2018).

Table 34: Setup process and application: tool #33

T3.5 tool	#33 Climate readiness certification
T2.4 subtask	T2.4.4 Water-smart for climate ready certificates
Data inputs and model initialisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The methodology has closed questions that can be answered by a single option, multiple options or percentages. Each criterion has an associated score and the answers are ordered by descending score. The answer with the most points is always the first option. In the case of a criteria that does not apply and as such is not evaluated, the auditor can exclude it and its score is proportionally distributed to the other methodology criteria.
Parameters and assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The CRC methodology encompasses three dimensions: water efficiency, water-energy nexus and climate adaptation. Overall, it has 96 evaluation criteria: 53 criteria in the water efficiency dimension, 23 criteria in the water energy nexus, and 20 in the climate adaptation. • All these criteria are evaluated on three different scales of applicability: household, building and neighbourhood, though some of the criteria are not applicable to the household and outdoor space analysis.
Temporal and spatial scales	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N/A • Household, building and neighbourhood.
Design of scenarios	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N/A
Deployment of the tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Once the web tool is operational (October 2023), the auditors will be able to select the building typology to be certified, fill out the CRC methodology directly in the web tool and the platform will calculate the class of each dimension, the overall class and issue the CRC certificate.

7.2.5 Results

Having in mind the **Lisbon LL ambition** (section 7.1), the following results can be drawn at this moment for tools #25, #24, #27, and #17 (coherently with the outputs illustrated in Figure 118) and for tools #20 and #33:

1. Improving water supply-demand management

- **Tool #25 W-E-P balance planning** was successfully developed and, as planned, is a matchmaking environment that enables the design of supply solutions driven by the demand(s) to be satisfied and translated as time series of required monthly volumes over a pre-specified period – “alternatives”. An “alternative” consists of the combination of the available water sources to make up the required monthly volumes in a predefined group of water demand points (e.g., green areas), while complying with the energy and nutrients contents as desired. Such combinations are characterized by the degree to which they satisfy the required volumes over time, as well as by their energy consumption, nutrient content, and cost. By facilitating the linking of water consumption locations (geographic representation) with various information related to those water demand points, tool #25 can function as a design planning tool since it allows the testing of different water management solutions, which are easily translated by the alternatives.
- **Tool #25** was designed to function both as an information repository and as a communication channel between different stakeholders – critical issues during planning and developing water-smart projects. The information to be provided to the software consists of a time series of required monthly values of water volumes, water price or P consumption over a pre-specified period, and unit values with the estimation of some variables. The full geographic representation of the sources and demands helps planners and decision-makers in urban management, municipal, and water utility contexts define water supply solutions. Finally, the software allows the introduction of text to justify the information as well as the design of alternatives. It is considered that this aspect (i.e., introduction of text) is of great use, both in a revisitation of the planning exercise, and in its consultation and discussion by different decision makers.
- The energy consumption associated with each alternative results from two factors: the energy consumption associated with water production (which naturally depends on the origin of the water) and the energy consumption associated with water distribution, i.e. placing the water at that point of consumption. This information, which results from the planner’s concrete knowledge of the locations of water consumption and available sources, is introduced in **Tool #25** through the description menu of each alternative. Tool #25 also includes information on water losses and carbon footprint related to each water sources. In this way, it is possible to identify the contribution of the improved water supply-demand management to strategies implemented at the municipal level, through a water losses management plan or a climate action plan.

- **Tool #17 Environment for decision support and selection of alternative courses of action** is completed and enables users to select the best water source combinations to satisfy specific non-potable uses, and enables prioritizing strategic and tactical planning options on the management of water sources and water uses in an urban setting. The supply/demand alternative combinations are assessed through a range of standardized, user-selected performance, risk, and cost metrics, complementing those employed to qualify the initial selection in Tool #25 (e.g., volume availability, cost, energy content, carbon footprint, nutrient content). To ensure the alignment of decisions for improving water supply/demand management with the Lisbon LL Strategic Agenda, the metrics correspond as much as possible to metrics integrated in the BWS Evaluation Framework (Tool #34) or else contribute to their calculation.
- **Tool #20 Urban Water Cycle Observatory** was upgraded as foreseen. Its public access component provides visually appealing information on the urban water cycle (including the consumption of drinking water, the treatment of wastewater and the production and use of reclaimed water) as a means of increasing citizens' water literacy, hoping to make them more willing to be active agents in managing water demand in the city. In 2022, there were 8500 visits to the website and until 22/06/2022, 7200 visits were registered. Its private access component can help those responsible for large water consumption (municipalities and private institutions of public interest) to be more efficient in managing water use in those facilities. Processing raw data from smart meters by type of use provides useful information.

2. Testing the use of alternative water sources – the case of water reuse

- **Tool #27 Risk assessment for urban water reuse** was successfully developed. It provides a user-friendly solution for carrying out human health and environmental risk assessments, requiring a basic knowledge of risk management and of the legislation applicable to water reuse. For this purpose, a methodology for hazard exposure scenario building was developed from scratch and a process for human health and environmental risk assessment based on ISO standards and the EU Regulation 2020/741 on minimum requirements for water reuse was defined (Ribeiro and Rosa, 2022).
- **Tool #24 Reclaimed water quality model in the distribution network** is completed and tested in three pilots (distribution networks). It simulates the advection, mixing, and transformation of waterborne parameters in reclaimed water (Costa et al., 2021). It aims primarily at mapping and quantifying risk in reclaimed water distribution networks. In the case of Lisbon, where the strategy for water reuse is being decided, Tool #24 has significant potential for supporting the design and monitoring of a public reclaimed water distribution network.
- **Tool #25 W-E-P balance planning** allows the integration of phosphorus circularity in a more comprehensive decision-making process regarding the management of water

supply/demand in municipal (and other) green areas. It conducts a phosphorus balance in water consumption sites (gardens and other green areas) by comparing the P fertilisation needs throughout the year with what can be supplied through reclaimed water. The assessment of the fertilisation potential from the reclaimed water use is aligned with the need to improve resource efficiency and support the circularity of phosphorus – phosphate rock and specific form of P4 are currently on the EU Critical Raw Material List.

3. Promoting climate adaptation in buildings

- “3” is the number to consider for the promotion of climate ready housing, as there are three aspects to consider: the evaluated dimensions (water efficiency, water-energy nexus and climate adaptation), the scale of analysis (household, building and neighbourhood) and the moment of certification (design phase, in construction and in use). This was the basis for the development of the **Tool #33 Climate readiness certification**, which has been tested at the abovementioned scales of analysis.

This section will be completed with final results and reported through Milestone 32 at month 45.

7.3 Lessons extracted

Having in mind the **Lisbon LL ambition**, the following lessons can be drawn at this moment:

1. Improving water supply-demand management

Pros

- Since the goal is to optimise the use of water in the city for non-potable uses, the decision-making process should be demand driven, i.e. with a fit-for-purpose quality to satisfy an efficient water use, as developed (tools #25 and #17). The decision-making process must also ensure alignment between strategic and tactical planning (namely aligning T1.4 and T2.4 outputs).
- The integration of the energy component associated with water allows the management of the water supply/demand to contribute to other city objectives, such as energy neutrality and climate action (tools #25, #17, #33).

Challenges

- Compiling information about water demand for non-potable uses in the city and available water sources can be difficult. Applying tools that function as data repository (e.g., tools #25, #20) catalyses proper data management.
- Exploiting the full potential of a smart-water allocation in Lisbon requires the existence of a public reclaimed water distribution network (nowadays available only in some areas), with a sound asset management.

2. Testing the use of alternative water sources – the case of water reuse

Pros

- Decision-making tools must provide structured, user-friendly methodologies for human health and environmental risk assessment, making expert-knowledge available for risk managers and stakeholders responsible for non-potable water uses in the city, as in tool #27.
- It is important to predict the evolution of water quality along the reclaimed water distribution network and, when necessary, the irrigation network, as developed in tool #24. This simulation allows one to assess the need for disinfection and chlorine residual supply in the design of distribution networks or, in the case of already constructed networks, to evaluate the efficiency of the disinfection process to introduce adjustments if necessary.

Challenges

- The simulation of the evolution of reclaimed water quality in distribution networks, namely in irrigation networks, requires a temporal and spatial granularity of the base data that may be difficult to achieve. The state of conservation of the water distribution network can affect its hydraulic performance. These two aspects constrain the calibration of mathematical models, thus affecting the quality of simulation results.
- The results naturally depend on the quantity and quality of the information available for the calibration and use of the hydraulic and water quality models (as in tool #24). The effort required to obtain this information is largely compensated by the benefits that the control of the disinfection process of reclaimed water has on the risk management associated to water reuse, as well as on the investment and operational cost of the reuse system.
- The decision on at what point of a WWTP the treated wastewater should be subject to further treatment depends on the evolution of European regulations, particularly, the Directive 91/271/EEC concerning urban waste-water treatment, and it is important to recognise this uncertainty when planning on a strategic level. For example, for phosphorus, the likely more stringent limit values in effluent discharge to receiving waters may be avoided by promoting phosphorus circularity via water reuse for irrigation. This challenge on water discharge can turn into an opportunity for water reuse.

3. Promoting climate adaptation in buildings

Pros

- There is interest in the housing market in providing information on environmental aspects of buildings.

Challenges

- The major bottleneck found so far was the lack of technical documentation from the projects (household, building and neighbourhood) to be certified.

7.4 Summary table of the LL

Table 35: Summary table for LL Lisbon

Title	Methods, algorithms and software for a smart allocation of the water quality (fit-for-purpose) and quantity (water efficiency) in Lisbon. The ambition is to (i) improve the water supply / demand management and ultimately the city's water-energy-phosphorus (WEP) footprint while increasing the green areas, (ii) promote the safe use of alternative sources (e.g., reclaimed water), and (iii) promote climate-ready (water-energy efficient, climate-change proof) housing.
Description	<p>Making Lisbon a water-smarter city implies the involvement of different stakeholders in the provision and use of water. The following approaches were considered for the desired transformation into a water-smarter society:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ To increase the citizens' awareness about the local context regarding the water use in the city via the provision of appellative information and to inform individual entities about their water consumption, in case of smart water metering (Tool #20). ▪ To support the decision-making process of water demand planners and managers in urban, municipal and water utility contexts, by delivering an overview on the current water supply and water demand in the city to enable prioritizing strategic and tactical planning options (Tools #17, #24, #25, and #27). ▪ To guide or assess the promotion of climate adaptation in housing via a certification process used by housing owners and planners (Tool #33).
Reference point	https://earth.google.com/web/@38.73328057,-9.14002902,76.18325293a,14074.25418275d,35y,0h,0t,0r
Location	Lisboa, Portugal
Country (-ies)	Portugal
URL	N/A
Project	B-WaterSmart
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Water Scarcity ▪ High drinking water demand due to dense or growing resident population and economy ▪ Dependent on distant freshwater resources ▪ Untapped efficiency potential of water resources ▪ Need for safe water reuse schemes, including building and managing a dedicated reclaimed water distribution system
Tools/Product/Services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Environment for decision support and selection of alternative courses of action (#17) ▪ UWC observatory (#20) ▪ Reclaimed water quality model in the distribution network (#24) ▪ Water-energy-phosphorous balance planning (#25) ▪ Risk assessment for urban water reuse (#27) ▪ Climate-readiness certification tool (#33)
Technologies	1 ozone oxidation/reverse osmosis (O3/RO) pilot installed at Beirolas water resource recovery facility (WRRF) for demonstration of water reuse in the food industry, namely, in artisanal craft beer production (direct potable reuse, DPR)

Scales	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Tool #20: city level ▪ Tools #17, #24, #25, and #27: urban facility (e.g., public park), neighbourhood, city, region ▪ Tool #33: household, building and neighbourhood
Legislation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ National (Portuguese) legislation: Decree-Law 119/2019 on water reuse. ▪ European regulations: Reg. (EU) 741/2020 on minimum requirements for water reuse in agricultural irrigation and Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (recast) (new proposal under approval).
Synergistic benefits	To be reported in MS32.
Facts of the applied technologies	To be reported in MS32.
Key Performance Indicators	To be reported in MS32.
Requirements and conditions	To be reported in MS32.
Key lessons	<p>A selection of key lessons</p> <p>Pros:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Since the goal is to optimise the use of water in the city for non-potable uses, the decision-making process should be demand driven, i.e. with a fit-for-purpose quality to satisfy an efficient water use. ▪ Decision-making tools must provide structured, user-friendly methodologies for human health and environmental risk assessment, making expert-knowledge available for risk managers and stakeholders responsible for non-potable water uses in the city. ▪ There is interest in the housing market in providing information on environmental aspects of buildings. <p>Challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Compiling information about water demand for non-potable uses in the city and available water sources can be difficult. Applying tools that function as data repository catalyses a proper data management. ▪ The results naturally depend on the quantity and quality of the information available for the calibration and use of the hydraulic and water quality models. The effort required to obtain this information is largely compensated by the benefits that the control of the disinfection process of reclaimed water has on the risk management associated to water reuse, as well as on the investment and operational cost of the reuse system. ▪ Exploiting the full potential of a smart-water allocation in Lisbon requires the existence of a public reclaimed water distribution network (nowadays available only in some areas), with sound asset management.
Lessons learned from technology operation	To be reported in MS32.
Technology performance and best practices	To be reported in MS32.
Outcome of assessments	To be reported in MS32.
Organisations	<p>The Lisbon LL gathers six partners:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ CML (Lisbon Municipality), with a linked third-party – LEN (Lisboa E-Nova). ▪ LNEC (Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil) ▪ ADTA (Águas do Tejo Atlântico) ▪ ADENE (Agência para a Energia) ▪ ICS-UL (Instituto de Ciências Sociais da Universidade de Lisboa)

Contact persons	Maria João Rosa, mjrosa@lnec.pt , LNEC (LL mentor) Rita Ribeiro, ribeiro@lnec.pt , LNEC (LL deputy-mentor) Pedro Teixeira, pedro.teixeira@cm-lisboa.pt , CML (LL owner)
Data Manager	Not available at this stage.
Costs	Not available at this stage.
Tags	#reuse #water #multicriteria #supply #demand
Publications/Reference	Costa, J., Mesquita, E., Ferreira, F., Rosa, M. J., and Viegas, R. M. (2021). Identification and modelling of chlorine decay mechanisms in reclaimed water containing ammonia. <i>Sustainability</i> , 13(24), 13548. Ribeiro, R., Rosa, M.J. (2022). Avaliação do risco para a saúde humana associado à reutilização de água: construção de cenários de exposição. 20.º ENASB, Cascais, 24-26 November 2022, 5 p. (communication in a conference)
Images	
Caption/Source	Lisbon LL aims (i) to demonstrate the potential for safe potable water reuse in the beverage industry in the mid to long run, and (ii) in the short term, to promote water (and related energy and phosphorus) efficiency, water smart allocation (fit-for-purpose quality), circular economy, and safe non-potable urban water reuse.

8 Tools and Methods for LL Alicante

8.1 Key WS challenges, ambition and case study description

Key water-smart challenges in Alicante are water scarcity, limitations to water reuse due to high salinity, and limitations to water reuse due to lack of storage infrastructure to cover the time decoupling between production and demand. Although water scarcity in Alicante is not a problem for direct human consumption yet, it is a foreseeable problem since the inland supply of freshwater from the Tagus-Segura transfer (33% of total share in the past) may come to an end due to the decreasing availability of water in the high course of the Tagus river. Scarcity is already a problem for the sustainability of agriculture irrigation. Water reuse may be one opportunity to secure a constant water supply of the region. However, the application of water reuse is not without challenges. A technical challenge is the high level of salinity of part of the wastewater, which led to the construction of a desalination plant ten years ago, in order to carry out an additional treatment stage after the conventional tertiary phase. Nevertheless, wastewater with very high conductivity cannot be used in the existing reverse osmosis (RO) plant; in any case, the treatment capacity of the desalination plant poses a limit for the amount of water that can be regenerated.

The ambitions of Alicante LL are to boost water reuse and circular economy (CE) in the region. This is in line with the bio-factories initiative fostered by AGBAR-Veolia (former SUEZ Spain). Through the B-WaterSmart project, Alicante wants to recover and reuse energy (#10, #13), nutrients (#9) and salts and water from RO brine (#7, #8).

The diversity of water resources in the region and the complexity and interlinkages when evaluating the implementation of new investments related to water-smartness makes it difficult to quantify environmental impacts and benefits or to analyse alternative solutions quickly.

The RE-ACTOR Tool (#18) helps to solve these challenges by evaluating alternative scenarios that can be implemented in the region in a user-friendly interface. The web-based digital solution allows the quantification of the impacts and benefits related to a full-scale implementation of the technical solutions evaluated within the B-WaterSmart as well as other solutions that could promote water-smartness in the region. These results allow prioritising most promising scenarios as well as to demonstrate and communicate to relevant stakeholders the impacts and benefits for a water-smart region.

Figure 119 The LL Alicante ambition

8.2 Application of tools and methods

8.2.1 Selected tools and technologies of pilots

The Alicante Living Lab demonstrates technologies to recover energy (#10, #13), nutrients (#9), valorize brine and increase reclaimed water production (#7, #8) from urban water infrastructures. The results obtained from the monetization and evaluation of the different technologies assessed in WP2 (co-digestion, turbines for own electricity production, selective electro dialysis + electrochlorination for sodium hypochlorite production or nutrients valorisation technologies) are used to feed part of the database of tool #18. Technical results, as well as environmental impacts and operation and capital costs of the technologies are obtained from pilot plants operation. When necessary, these values will be scaled up based on literature data or data from full-scale operations to ensure the highest representability of the tool estimations.

The tool integrates an API that allows the administrator to modify costs, impacts and other technical parameters relevant for each technology. Thus, whenever new information or results are ready, their integration within the tool can be easily made.

As depicted in Figure 5, the RE-ACTOR Tool mostly helps boosting the strategic objective (SO) of promotion of adaptive change towards resilient infrastructure, by allowing the analysis of investments on new resilient infrastructure in the territory, and the SO of citizens and actors engagement by helping the demonstration of the co-benefits from the proposed water-smart solutions. The selected approach focuses in the easiness of use through an intuitive user interface, but mainly by way of reducing the input data required for the simulation of investments. This strategy allows the user to compare multiple scenarios in a short time, at the assumed cost of sacrificing the highest level of accuracy in the results.

Figure 120 Relationship between Alicante LL Strategic Objectives and Technologies and Tools

8.2.2 Integrative use of tools, pilot interaction and data flows

As presented in Figure 121 The LL Alicante tool, the solution includes the necessary connections (via API) so that the administrator can modify costs, environmental impacts, and other technical parameters relevant for each technology or set of actions. These functionalities are included in the Parameter's Editor section. On the other hand, on the Project's Editor, the user is able to create or edit projects that will be composed of a baseline scenario and alternative modified scenarios.

USER INPUTS

- New user or action on reclaimed water:
- Increase of capacity of existing plants
 - Additional treatment / brine valorization in existing plants
 - Energetic improvement / installation renewal energies
 - Fit-for-use advanced treatment
 - Green infrastructures

Inputs introduced by the user in the web-app

Environmental impact model
Costs models of technologies (CAPEX / OPEX) models for different scales
Network models- METRESA - (renewal needs , excavation costs, materials...)

RE-ACTOR Tool

Tables, databases and models treated constitute the API and is regularly updated with new real data from operations, literature, own-produces, etc.

Outputs obtained in the web-app and/or report extracted via PDF

TOOL OUTPUTS

- Estimations of:
- Cost of the action (CAPEX, OPEX)
 - Environmental impacts and benefits as compared to current scenarios or other alternatives (seawater desalination, water transfer)
 - Other economic indicators: ROI, avoided costs by reusing
 - Quantification of benefits
 - Social impacts (ecosystemic services monetization)
 - Others

Figure 121 The LL Alicante tool

A Baseline Scenario is defined by a group of Assets from a territory (e.g., WWTPs, DWTP, water users, water infrastructure...) with specific parameters and characteristics. The user will then create Modified Scenarios by adding new assets or deleting assets from the baseline scenario or by applying actions to the existing assets (e.g., installation of renewable energies or modification of the treatment train of a WWTP).

As mentioned in the previous section, a functionality is added so that the administrator can modify costs, impacts and other technical parameters relevant for each technology. In this sense, whenever new information or results are ready, their integration within the tool will be easily made. This new information may originate from results obtained within the pilot plants operation in WP2 or also from new literature or market data availability. The more reliable the information fed into the database, the more accurate the results obtained in RE-ACTOR will be.

Figure 122 The Alicante LL tool and pilot interaction

The core back-end of the tool is formed by a database that contains a high volume of values related to the parameters regarded in the platform and from which calculations are carried out to estimate the impact on economic and environmental parameters. These values have been obtained from an exhaustive bibliographic search as well as other resources available. It needs to be highlighted that such values may be dependent on specific plants and conditions not applicable to all water treatment plants. Moreover, data related to most recent and innovative technologies (i.e. not conventional) could not be found or was found for small pilot scale plants or even lab-scale studies, which is far from a full scale scenario. The interpretation and extrapolation of these values to other case studies may lead to reducing the accuracy of the results but can give a general overview and even magnitude of order of the impacts.

Since in Alicante LL we are validating innovative technologies and treatment trains (at pilot scale) for different purposes within water treatment in WWTPs, the results obtained from the operation of these technologies will be also used to feed RE-ACTOR’s database with new values of economic and operational parameters that will improve its quality and help in obtaining more accurate results.

8.2.3 Pre-processing stage and input data

In order to apply RE-ACTOR tool, the user will need input data belonging to the case-study plants that need upgrading or is being evaluated. Input data can be either mandatory or optional fields consisting of data related to the facility identified including basic characteristics (design flow, population equivalent), treatment trains involved (primary, secondary, tertiary, others), process efficiency and quality parameters of water discharge (COD, TSS, N and P) as well as energy parameters related to both consumption and production if applicable.

A database with all the different processes has been generated in order to organise the inputs in its different parameters, in order to filter the input values in different ranges to finally obtain the unitary outputs that the tool will use to calculate the final results. The tool does not calculate the outputs applying mathematical formulas, it uses the database organised in ranges to obtain the different output results from the unitary ratios instead, so that the internal parameters can be changed just by modifying the database without the need to alter the application code. In this way, the updating of the system's calculation logic is enabled without the need for resources with advanced programming knowledge.

Figure 9 shows a part of the tool's database. As can be seen in the figure, the inputs are organised in columns, and the different ranges are organised in rows, so the tool can filter the input selected and the value introduced in the front end. Once the input is filtered in the different ranges depending on the technology selected, the tool multiplies the different parameters obtained from the filter (H, I, J columns) by the input value to obtain the final result/output. In case the calculations need to be updated, it will only be necessary to replace the database file with the new version. The system will automatically apply this new version without service interruption or further configuration changes.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L
1	TRATAMIENTO	INPUT1	INPUT1	INPUT2	INPUT2	INPUT3	INPUT3	PARAM1	PARAM2	PARAM3	OUTPUT5	OUTPUT7
2	Terciarios_Fisicoquimico_decantación	Cap_min_m3dia	Cap_max_m3dia	Fe_Turb_min_NTU	Fe_Turb_max_NTU	Al_Turb_min_NTU	Al_Turb_max_NTU	Cons_E_mean_kWhm3	FeCl3_gm3	NaOH_gm3	Sup_ocupada_m2m3d	CAPEX_em3dia
3	Terciarios_Fisicoquimico_decantación	0	2000	0	2	0	2	0,02	56,5	5,3	0,019	11,75
4	Terciarios_Fisicoquimico_decantación	0	2000	2,1	5	2,1	5	0,02	56,5	5,3	0,019	11,75
5	Terciarios_Fisicoquimico_decantación	0	2000	5,1	10	5,1	10	0,02	56,5	5,3	0,019	11,75
6	Terciarios_Fisicoquimico_decantación	0	2000	10,1	100	10,1	100	0,02	56,5	5,3	0,019	11,75
7	Terciarios_Fisicoquimico_decantación	2001	10000	0	2	0	2	0,02	56,5	5,3	0,017	10,55
8	Terciarios_Fisicoquimico_decantación	2001	10000	2,1	5	2,1	5	0,02	56,5	5,3	0,017	10,55
9	Terciarios_Fisicoquimico_decantación	2001	10000	5,1	10	5,1	10	0,02	56,5	5,3	0,017	10,55
10	Terciarios_Fisicoquimico_decantación	2001	10000	10,1	100	10,1	100	0,02	56,5	5,3	0,017	10,55
11	Terciarios_Fisicoquimico_decantación	10001	50000	0	2	0	2	0,02	56,5	5,3	0,014	6,3
12	Terciarios_Fisicoquimico_decantación	10001	50000	2,1	5	2,1	5	0,02	56,5	5,3	0,014	6,3
13	Terciarios_Fisicoquimico_decantación	10001	50000	5,1	10	5,1	10	0,02	56,5	5,3	0,014	6,3
14	Terciarios_Fisicoquimico_decantación	10001	50000	10,1	100	10,1	100	0,02	56,5	5,3	0,014	6,3
15	Terciarios_Fisicoquimico_decantación	50001	1000000	0	2	0	2	0,02	56,5	5,3	0,012	5
16	Terciarios_Fisicoquimico_decantación	50001	1000000	2,1	5	2,1	5	0,02	56,5	5,3	0,012	5
17	Terciarios_Fisicoquimico_decantación	50001	1000000	5,1	10	5,1	10	0,02	56,5	5,3	0,012	5
18	Terciarios_Fisicoquimico_decantación	50001	1000000	10,1	100	10,1	100	0,02	56,5	5,3	0,012	5

Figure 123 RE-ACTOR tool upgrade database

8.2.4 Setup process and application

The application of the Decision Support System RE-ACTOR consists of a simple process based on 4 steps, shown in Figure 124

Figure 124 Step-by-step process of RE-ACTOR tool

Firstly, a project needs to be created that can either consist of a single asset which will be later upgraded, or multiple assets to create scenarios for its upgrading.

Figure 125 View of initial step in RE-ACTOR

The assets that can be explored with RE-ACTOR are (1) Wastewater Treatment Plant, (2) Drinking Water Treatment Plant and (3) Seawater Desalination Plant. Future versions could be expanded to include new categories. This project can be saved, and it is possible to later modify parameters or scenarios explored. Once the project has been created, the second step focuses on the definition of parameters related to the asset(s) that represent the baseline scenario. In this step several inputs are required at different levels (appearance can be observed in Figure 125):

- Type of asset – it is possible to select 3 different kinds of assets: Wastewater Treatment Plant (WWTP), Drinking Water Treatment Plant (DWTP) and Seawater Desalination Plant (SWDP).
- Basic characteristics – parameters related to the identification of the asset
- Treatment train – type of processes involved in the asset to remove different type of pollutants from water. The parameters to be entered are dependent on the type of asset selected given their different purposes and objectives. Depending on the processes selected more levels are required in defining the baseline to better approach the scenario conditions.
- Asset information – related to the creation date and modification dates of the assets.

Figure 126 Baseline definition step in RE-ACTOR

After entering and saving this information to the DSS platform, a new section still within Baseline Definition is accessible in order to provide more detailed information related to the Basic characteristics and Treatment train. This implies introducing specific values regarding water quality, energy consumption and design parameters of the asset that is being analysed. The last step in the definition of the baseline consists in locating the asset in a map, which is especially interesting when defining a baseline with multiple assets in a single project that are distributed geographically.

After the Baseline has been created, the next step is the Application of Upgrades. The RE-ACTOR DSS aims at evaluating alternative scenarios that could be implemented on an asset, in order to quantify the impacts and benefits related to a full-scale implementation of the technical solutions evaluated within the B-WaterSmart, as well as other changes that could promote water-smartness and economy circularity. Figure 127 displays several of the technologies and solutions that can be applied within this step.

Figure 127 Application of upgrades to asset for assessment

Each of the solutions/technologies requires further details related to its operation and target objectives, once its option is selected. An example of the information required can be observed in Figure 128; this case is associated with the potential upgrade of implementing solar panels in the asset.

Figure 128 Example of operational details required for upgrades

Finally, the last step consists in the analysis of the results, so that the upgrades applied in the asset in terms of economic and environmental criteria can be evaluated. RE-Actor has an option to display the overall results obtained within the platform and a report can be downloaded in PDF format, with both the global results and the breakdown for each upgrade applied as well. In any case, the platform provides quantitative results for both the baseline scenario and the upgraded case study. Figure 129 shows an example of the results as shown within RE-Actor and Figure 130 a results report that can be downloaded.

Figure 129 Comparison of results for baseline and upgraded case study

Figure 130 Results report downloaded from RE-ACTOR in pdf format.

8.2.5 Results

The current case study has focused on two WWTPs in Alicante region: 1) Rincón de León and 2) Monte Orgegia WWTPs. Both plants are expected to receive upgrades even though at pilot plant during B-WaterSmart execution.

Baseline definition for WWTPs in Alicante LL

The second step of the RE-ACTOR methodology is to define the baseline for the project. The baseline was created for each of the WWTPs of the LL Alicante separately (Monte Orgegia and Rincón de León). The results are internal information that can be shared with reviewers appointed by the EC upon request.

Application of upgrades within B-WaterSmart in Monte Orgegia WWTP

In the frame of WP2 in B-WaterSmart, microturbines are currently being installed in Monte Orgegia WWTP for energy recovery from wastewater effluents. The demo pilot microturbine that is being implemented at this plant has an output power of 2 kW, even though this parameter has been increased to study its impact.

For some of the parameters in Table 2, microturbines did not have any impact in terms of reducing its value in comparison to the baseline scenario. This is the case in marine eutrophication, freshwater eutrophication and occupied area given the fact that these microturbines have no chemical interaction with water so they should not be neither increasing nor reducing the content of nutrients in water.

On the other hand, microturbines had a positive effect on carbon and water footprint as well as in the OPEX (Figure 131), by reducing the values for each parameter compared to the baseline cases. If we consider the installed power that is being installed in Monte Orgegia at pilot scale in the frame of WP2, which is 2 kWh, carbon and water footprint would be reduced by 2% and 0.1%, respectively, and regarding the OPEX it would be decreased up to almost a 10%, given that this renewable energy would reduce the plant energy consumption from fossil fuels.

Figure 131 RE-ACTOR results of applying microturbines in Monte Orgegia WWTP

The potential impact on these parameters achieved by increasing the installed power with microturbines up to 10 kW has also been evaluated and the results point out reductions in carbon and water footprint up to almost 10% and 0,3% respectively, and up to a 35% reduction in the OPEX of Monte Orgegia WWTP.

Application of upgrades within B-WaterSmart in Rincón de León WWTP

The application of co-digestion in Rincón de León WWTP has been assessed taking into account three main parameters: volume of waste treated (Tn/year), solid content in waste (kg of TS/Tn) and the biodegradability of the waste (in %). Given that several types of waste are being investigated in the co-digestion pilot plant in WP2, a preliminary study modifying these parameters (Table 36) has been carried out.

Table 36 Scenarios set for co-digestion assessment

Scenario Sn	Volume of waste treated [Tn/year]	Solid content in waste [kg TS/Tn]	Biodegradability [%]
S1	10	50	70
S2	30	50	80
S3	100	50	80
S4	100	80	80
S5	300	240	80

S6	500	250	80
----	-----	-----	----

In most scenarios evaluated, the biodegradability has been maintained high, due to the fact that waste from the agrifood sector will be used for co-digestion and they typically have high biological degradability. The volume of waste treated has been increased from 10 up to 500 Tn/year, which will actually depend on the activity of the industries giving away their waste for this matter, and also the solid content has been raised from 50 up to 250 kg, which will also be a crucial parameter indicating the solid-liquid content in the waste.

The results obtained for each scenario are displayed in Figure 132 where the % reduction is calculated taking the results obtained from applying the upgrades to RE-ACTOR and comparing them to those in the baseline. As it can be seen in Figure 131, increasing both the volume of waste treated and the solid content results in significantly reducing the OPEX up to 30%, given that biogas is being generated that will be converted into energy for self-consumption, which will contribute to decreasing the overall energy consumption of the plant.

On the other hand, the use of biogas as an energy source can reduce the carbon footprint of a wastewater treatment plant in several ways:

- Energy generation: Biogas can be used to generate heat and electricity, which can offset the energy demand of the Rincón de León WWTP. This reduces the need for energy from external sources, which are often derived from fossil fuels, resulting in a lower carbon footprint.
- Reduced methane emissions: The anaerobic digestion process that produces biogas also reduces the amount of methane emissions from the WWTP. Methane is a potent greenhouse gas, with a global warming potential much greater than that of carbon dioxide. Therefore, by capturing methane in biogas, the plant can reduce its overall greenhouse gas emissions.
- Waste reduction: The use of biogas systems in wastewater treatment plants can also help to reduce the amount of waste material that would otherwise need to be transported and disposed of elsewhere. This further reduces the carbon footprint associated with waste management.

In this sense, increasing the volume of waste used in anaerobic digestion would reduce the carbon footprint of Rincón de León since more biogas would be produced; therefore more energy for the self-consumption of the WWTP, which is why it can be seen in Figure 132 how carbon footprint tends to an increased reduction in the different scenarios. Moreover, the use of external waste from other industries would also contribute to reducing the carbon footprint of not only Rincón de León, but also the industries providing the waste.

On the contrary, a negative impact would be observed in the CAPEX derived from increasing the volume of waste, where it would not be reduced but increased given that the digester

volume would also increase and this would require bigger reactors and higher space requirements.

Figure 132 Impact of applying co-digestion in Rincón de León WWTP

The application of electro dialysis (ED) in Rincón de León WWTP as a strategy of minimising the liquid discharge of the WWTP has been assessed including four main parameters in the equation: design capacity of the technology (in m³/day), average flow to be treated (m³/day), recovery (m³/day) as well as the efficiency to separate ions and water and conductivity of water (mS/cm). These parameters have been modified according to Table 37 below to generate different scenarios and compare the results to the baseline.

Table 37 Scenarios set for electro dialysis assessment

Scenario Sn	Design capacity [m ³ /day]	Average flow [m ³ /day]	Recovery [%]	Conductivity [mS/cm]
S1	10	8	65	7,5
S2	100	80	65	10
S3	500	400	75	10
S4	1000	1000	75	15
S5	1000	1000	94	15

As similarly observed in the results obtained for the application of the co-digestion unit, the parameters Water footprint, Marine eutrophication and Freshwater eutrophication have not been affected at all due to the implementation of ED. Ideally, if all the brine produced in the plant was valorised into valuable products (such as NaClO) there would not be any discharge into the sea, and therefore nutrients discharge within the brine would be decreased. This should imply a reduction in the marine eutrophication parameter, which has not been noticed in RE-ACTOR calculations. This seems to be an incoherence that may come from the backend of the tool, which will be further regarded in future versions of the tool.

The carbon footprint as well as the OPEX have been slightly affected as it can be seen in Figure 19. These parameters have smoothly increased up to 0,15% and 0,38% respectively compared to the baseline scenario in Table 2, given the fact that there has been included an additional technology to the current scheme and this technology implies an energy consumption that eventually contributes to incrementing the costs of its operation (i.e. OPEX) and also to the overall carbon footprint of Rincón de León WWTP.

Increasing both the design capacity and average flow to be treated has depicted an increase in the CAPEX of the plant, even though it did not even reach a 7%. The reason behind this is in accordance with what was discussed above; applying an additional technology to the treatment train implies higher costs.

Figure 133 Impact of applying electrodialysis in Rincón de León WWTP

The application of electrodialysis in WWTPs is not commonly found in WWTPs but its application in such plants includes:

- Desalination: ED can be used to remove salts and other dissolved minerals from wastewater, particularly in areas where freshwater resources are scarce.
- Acid and alkali recovery: ED can also be used to recover acid and alkali from wastewater, which can be reused in other industrial processes.
- Heavy metal removal: ED can also remove heavy metals from wastewater, which can be harmful to the environment and human health if left untreated.
- Nutrient recovery: ED can be used to recover nutrients, such as nitrogen and phosphorus, from wastewater, which can be reused as fertilisers.

In B-WaterSmart selective ED is being applied for a three-fold purpose: 1) Maximise reclaimed water production, 2) Valorization of monovalent ions for hypochlorite sodium production and 3) Valorization of divalent ions for water reuse in crops irrigation. The approach being pursued in the project is highly innovative. In this sense, data related to ED operational efficiency parameters is scarce. In addition, when Zero or Minimum Liquid Discharge (ZLD/MLD) strategies are being implemented, complementary technologies need to be included in the overall treatment train, thus capital expenditures will always increase, as observed in Figure 18. For this reason, the benefits of applying this kind of technologies need to be regarded to the mid/long-term, and in the context of B-WaterSmart we also need to take into account that valuable by-products that are being generated are not being considered in RE-ACTOR due to the complexity of the whole picture and its initial scope. Nevertheless, this point has been identified as a shortcoming of the current version of the tool that should be improved in future developments.

8.3 Lessons extracted

The decision process for implementing water reuse technologies can be time consuming and require loads of effort only for assessing the implementation of one technology. Alicante LL is implementing several technologies (at pilot scale) at the same time under WP2; thus, the assessment of both economic and environmental benefits of such actions would need an extensive amount of work and time before even considering their implementation or scalation. RE-ACTOR aims to support this task in a less accurate but faster way so as to help decision-makers to carry out a first agile approach that allows rejecting most scenarios and focusing efforts on those initiatives that are really worthwhile. The real ultimate goal is to make it easier for stakeholders involved in such a process to keep investing in water reuse technologies.

In this sense, RE-ACTOR has been designed as a user-friendly and manageable web-based digital tool that can estimate quantitatively several economic and environmental parameters without the necessity of providing extensive amounts of process data and inputs. Therefore, RE-ACTOR allows to assess the application of upgrades in a straightforward and fast manner. It needs to be highlighted that the results have a certain degree of uncertainty; as mentioned, this characteristic is intentionally assumed in order to avoid the model of “data-hungry” applications that need extensive analysis just for providing a preliminary depiction of the investment scenarios. On the other hand, further efforts will need to be dedicated to

refining the back-end database, since this component is fed with available data related to the technologies, and in several situations (those associated with some of the most innovative solutions) this data does not yet exist.

Experimental results obtained in the frame of WP2, under the operation of the pilot plants, will be used to nourish and improve the backend database that estimates the impacts, both economic and environmental, of applying upgrades to assets.

8.4 Summary table of the LL

Table 38 Summary table for LL Alicante

Title	Boosting water reuse in Alicante LL
Description	DSS for the evaluation of new investments and actions related to water reuse and circular economy solutions within the urban water cycle. Scope of application: regional level.
Reference point	WWTP Rincón de León (https://goo.gl/maps/Ry2j7Fy5tC4qpabU7) and WWTP Monte Orgegia (https://goo.gl/maps/PMHZaRUAN7Uq4B9S9)
Location	Alicante, Spain
Country (-ies)	Spain
URL	https://reactor.fidesol.org/resultScenario
Project	B-WaterSmart
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water Scarcity, • Limitations to water reuse due to high salinity/nitrates,
Tools/Product/Services	Re-Actor (#18)
Technologies	Water recovery > Wastewater treatment technologies > Membrane systems > Electrodialysis Energy recovery > Biomass production > Biogas production via anaerobic (co)digestion
Scales	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local (e.g., single treatment plant, industrial site or city quarter), • City (whole city level), • Metropolitan (extending beyond the city e.g., into neighbouring cities or peri-urban fringe area),
Legislation	European regulation on minimum requirements for water reuse (EU 2020/741) Spanish Royal Decree 1620/2007 for water reuse

Synergistic benefits	The tool allowed users to assess environmental and economic impacts of upgrading scenarios with different technologies and prioritize them.
Facts of the applied technologies	Eutrophication, Carbon footprint, CAPEX, OPEX
Key Performance Indicators	Performance of technologies evaluated in WP2 (at pilot level) does not depend on the RE-ACTOR tool but the other way around. RE-ACTOR database is being fed with performance data of technologies in WP2.
Requirements and conditions	Internet and minimum requirements to access to the web app Reliable and updated data on economic and environmental parameters for the WP2 technologies. Especially economic data on fluctuant costs needs to be updated on a regular basis if accurate results are pursued. Basic information to define baseline
Key lessons	The application of circular economy solutions in WWTPs usually implies including supplementary technologies. For this reason, CAPEX is frequently a challenge, despite the advantages of recovering resources or valorizing wastes. The cost of doing nothing is often apparently lower.
Lessons learned from technology operation	RE-ACTOR allows to assess the application of upgrades in a straightforward and fast manner. It needs to be highlighted that the results have a certain degree of uncertainty; as mentioned, this characteristic is intentionally assumed in order to avoid the model of “data-hungry” applications that need extensive analysis
Technology performance and best practices	Pre-screening general assessment on different scenarios for a later deeper assessment.
Outcome of assessments	N/A
Organisations	CETAQUA; Aguas de Alicante; AGBAR, Veolia
Contact persons	Eric Santos, eric.santos@cetaqua.com, CETAQUA Ignacio Casals, ignacio.casals@aguasdealicante.es, Aguas de Alicante
Data Manager	Miquel Sarrias Miquel.sarrias@cetaqua.com / Eric Santos, eric.santos@cetaqua.com Ignacio Casals, Ignacio.casals@aguasdealicante.es /
Costs	OPEX – Domain and server maintenance (approx.. 400€/month), + staff costs of using it (dependent on time dedicated)
Tags	DSS, environmental impact, economic impact, investment assessment, water reuse
Publications/Reference	N/A

Images

Caption/Source

RE-ACTOR tool scope and objectives

9 Tools and Methods for LL Bodø

9.1 Key WS challenges, ambition, and case study description

Bodø has the ambition of becoming a low-emission society and to adapt to climate change. Re-location of the airport enables new sustainable city development with research-based solutions. Key challenges for LL Bodø that impact water includes a growing resident population and economy, increased pollution, and untapped efficiency potential.

There are three challenges characteristic for many small to medium size cities in northern regions: i) improve resource recovery from wastewater in an efficient way given the small scale, especially concerning biogas production from sludge; ii) improve wastewater quality by improved infiltration detection technologies coupled with leak detection technologies in an integrated system, to reduce energy consumption and improve the quality of the wastewater stream; iii) minimize strain upon existing pipe infrastructure from heavy rainfall events.

Figure 134: The LL Bodø ambition

9.2 Application of tools and methods

9.2.1 Selected tools and technologies of pilots

The aim of applying the Nessie system (#29) and the Environmental dashboard (#30) is to easier access information on Bodø's drinking water systems through various user interfaces and assist LL Bodø in meeting the case study challenges. Both solutions (#29 and #30) are

developed to complement each other and have different implementation scales for the LL Bodo. The Nessie system (#29) focuses on a household level to notify the end users i.e., households of water consumption and service disruptions based on the smart metering data of collected as part of T2.2.1. The Environmental Dashboard (#30), on the other hand, collects the data of T2.2.1 and other sources on a utilities level regarding measurements in the water distribution and urban drainage system to enable management of the overall system performance. The Environmental Dashboard can help to detect leakages in the network for drinking water in reducing water usage by raising awareness. This is enabled by connecting information from the technologies in WP2 and various detectors (#14) and smart water meters (#15) to the Environmental Dashboard. Nessie system, on the other hand, targets in better information at a household level (e.g., flow, pressure, temperature) enabling better monitoring and management of water consumption.

9.2.2 Integrative use of tools, pilot interaction and data flows

Smart water meters (#15) developed by Techni (Figure 135) are being installed in the homes of inhabitants of a pilot area in Bodø which logs real-time water consumption data. Various detectors (#14) include data from municipal water meters and sewer flow meters within the pilot area. This data is sent to NORD who will forward data to NTNU and ICCS.

Figure 135: Water smart meter installed.

NTNU uses this information to develop leakage detection algorithms. These algorithms will be linked to the Environmental dashboard (#30) being developed by NORD. The professional interface of the tool assists us in detecting leakage in the network for drinking water and gives a better overview of municipal water use. NORD has integrated the Techni smart-meters and are successfully delivering their data to ICCS. NORD also automates the calculation to estimate the average consumption per household in a zone. This data is integrated within the environmental dashboard per now (beta version not released).

ICCS will use the smart water meter data to further align Nessie system (#29) to end user's needs. In Bodo case, the web application has been redesigned and enhanced to enable householders to monitor water consumption at the household level, using real-time data from smart meters. The application can support seamless integration with third-party algorithms and analytics, which continuously fed with data from smart meters, for the detection of leakages and bursts. The monitoring of water consumption at the household level will help end-users to reduce water use by raising awareness.

Bodø's main water source is located 26 km from the city centre, but most of the distribution is automatic due to height difference. However, within the city water is distributed via pumps. To save energy our objective is to minimize production by minimizing water usage and leakages. The water meters can give users intensification in reducing the use of water. At the same time, users do not have to pay for more than they use. Water supply is costly for the municipality and its inhabitants. With better monitoring, the municipality reduces its costs and therefore its services are cheaper for the users.

Figure 136: The Bodø tool and pilot data flows

Figure 137: Smart water meter (#15) personal data flow chart

9.2.3 Pre-processing stage and input data

The pre-processing stage started with the selection of a pilot area to test the smart water meters (Technology #15) as well as detection of I/I by installing flow measurements in the sewer network (Technology #14). These technologies are linked directly to the tools #29 and 30 as they will provide input data to both. A short overlook of the steps in this process:

- Selecting pilot area
- Sending requests to homeowners for pilot project volunteers.
- Developing smart water meters (#15) (delays due to covid and supply chains)
- Meetings regarding installation of various detectors (#14)
 - Meeting regarding installation of sewer flow meters
 - Installing sewer flow meters
 - Meetings regarding municipal water meter data transfer
 - Creating contracts between Bodø kommune, NORD, NTNU and Sintef
 - Delays due to availability restraints between Bodø kommune's IT department, ATEA (Bodø kommune's outsourced IT), ABB (Company that currently manages municipal water services) and/or NORD for opening a port for NORD to receive municipal water meter data.
- Sending of first 5 water meters.

- Collaboration between Bodø kommune and NORD on the development of the Environmental Dashboard (#30)
- Creating data flow chart
- Creating GDPR data processor agreements and risk assessments between Bodø kommune & NORD, Bodø kommune & NTNU and Bodø kommune & ICCS.
 - Delays due to communication regarding the required technical detail needed within the contract.
- Finalizing homeowner contracts.
- Hosting a Workshop by ICCS regarding Nessie (#29).
- Installing first 5 smart water meters.
- Monitoring data for errors.
- Installing remaining 25 smart water meters, to be done in August 2023.
- Data delivery to the tools starting with July 2023 experimental testing of NTNU algorithms.

Regarding input data, NORD had to integrate data inputs of multiple standards. The goal was to make the data sets as standardized as possible. To achieve this, an Azure based integration system has been developed. This provides better flexibility for potential new sensors. The data model in use is the standard defined in NGSI-V2 (FIWARE approved). The main properties within the data set includes properties such as flow, pressure and temperature. For each sensor NORD provides 10 min/1-hour averages on a daily/weekly basis. The platform also provides the same averages/reports for a few selected water-meter zones. More zones will be continuously added and a weekly report of leakages per zone is available.

The algorithms linked to tool #30 were developed by NTNU within the above-mentioned limitations in mind using either available open-source data sets (Vrachimis et al. 2022) or Norwegian datasets of comparable quality for training and testing of algorithms. Data is collected, goes through quality control, and runs in the available algorithms.

Similarly, data from smart water meters will be inserted into Nessie through its Restful API, known as NaaS. Prior to data insertion, a setup procedure must be followed to create the smart water meters and other household sensors in Nessie's data model. The entire setup procedure is also carried out through the NaaS API via HTTP requests. After the setup and with the proper authentication credential, sensor measurement data can be inserted into Nessie by HTTP Post requests.

9.2.4 Setup process and application

Three families of algorithms have been developed and tested at NTNU to be linked in future with the Environmental Dashboard (#30). The differentiation is mainly about the main goals of the algorithms into Leakage detection algorithms, I/I algorithms, and possible combinations.

A first methodology (Vimme 2021) was developed to prioritize DMAs for water loss intervention based on different leakage indicators and data quality. Also, a proposal for new and improved DMAs was suggested. The zones were made based on several criteria, where the most important criterion was that creating a zone requires low-cost intervention. Then several leak detection methods were evaluated, either model based (Nordahl, 2022) or purely data driven ones (Mohan Doss et al., 2022 and Totland, 2022). Once data from Bodø is available it will be decided, which level of detail is possible and which of the methods can be applied.

For infiltration and inflow into the sewer system, measurements are available and basic data analysis allowed the application of the minimum night flow method to assess the current I/I water volume and other assessment methods based on Bentes et al. (2022). To enable more measurements cheap flow measurements devices (low-cost cameras) were tested in a laboratory setting and showed promising results (Meier et al., 2022). To use the minimal available data to the fullest three Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) models were re developed to predict the water flow based on the available variables. The models' suitability for detecting and locating new inflow and infiltration sources were assessed (Søvik, 2021).

A combination of the two problems is used as an approach based on Zhang et al. (2021) creating a proof of concept describing the system interfaces and modelling environment in Python.

With regard to Nessie system, the tool is a group of intertwined open source and in most of its entirety long term supported applications. The main tools, which have been deployed in Nessie's set up process and application, are the following.

Python /Django Web Application Framework

Python is a popular programming language that is widely used for web development because of its simplicity and ease of use. Django is a high-level Python web framework that enables developers to build web applications quickly and efficiently. Its built-in features and libraries allow developers to build web applications quickly and efficiently. Its modular design allows for scaling applications easily as needs grow. Django provides built-in security features such as cross-site scripting (XSS) protection, SQL injection protection, and clickjacking protection. It can be used for a wide range of web applications, including content management systems (CMS), social networks, e-commerce sites, and more. Its large and active community of developers contributes to the development and provide support. Finally, it supports Object-relational mapping (ORM) which makes it easy for developers to work with databases by providing an abstraction layer that allows them to work with databases using Python objects.

PostgreSQL Database System

PostgreSQL is an open-source relational database management system that has been designed to reliably store any type of data, including geolocational. PostgreSQL's source code is freely available under an open-source license, which allows for the freedom to use,

modify, and implement it as per business needs. It can handle large amounts of data and can scale up or down as per user or business needs. Its many advanced features make it unique in the ecosystem of relational databases. Taking advantage of these unique features and collaborating with others is the foundation of building powerful applications.

PostGIS Database Extender for Geolocation queries

PostGIS is an open-source software program that adds support for geographic objects to the PostgreSQL object-relational database. It follows the Simple Features for SQL specification from the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC). PostGIS was implemented as a PostgreSQL external extension. It adds support for geographic objects allowing location queries to be run in SQL. In addition to basic location awareness, PostGIS offers many features rarely found in other competing spatial databases such as Oracle Locator/Spatial and SQL Server.

NginX Reverse Proxy Server

Nginx is a high-performance web server and reverse proxy server that can handle different protocols such as HTTP, HTTPS, TCP, UDP, SMTP, IMAP, and POP. A reverse proxy server is a type of proxy server that typically sits behind the firewall in a private network and directs client requests to the appropriate backend server. Using Nginx as a reverse proxy provides various benefits such as improving performance, security, and caching for the applications. It can also navigate through firewalls that protect backend resources and act as a cache or buffer to reduce latency.

Gunicorn Web Server

Gunicorn is a Python Web Server Gateway Interface (WSGI) HTTP server. It is a pre-fork worker model ported from Ruby's Unicorn project. Gunicorn server is broadly compatible with various web frameworks, and it allows you to run any Python application concurrently by running multiple Python processes within a single dyno. It provides a perfect balance of performance, flexibility, and configuration simplicity.

Redis Cache and Message Broker Server

Redis is an open-source, in-memory data structure store used as a database, cache, and message broker. It is a key-value store which is often called a NoSQL database. Redis is widely used as a cache because it stores data in memory, making it extremely fast and efficient. It can be used to store and manage data structures such as strings, hashes, lists, sets, and more. Redis can also be used as a message broker, a distributed cache, and a task queue. A message broker is software that enables applications, systems, and services to communicate with each other and exchange information. The message broker can translate messages between different languages, platforms, and protocols. It can also validate, transform, route, and deliver messages to the appropriate destinations. A message broker can reduce the mutual awareness and dependency of the communicating parties. It also

helps in regard to real-time data broadcasting to 3rd party application developers or consumers.

All these tools and applications are installed in a UBUNTU Long Term Supported installation (in our case it is 22,04) but will be upgraded accordingly to the next LTS version.

The configuration steps included:

1. Creating and configuring the Python/Django Application
2. Creating and configuring service files and Gunicorn
3. Creating and activating a linux socket for the communication between NginX and Gunicorn
4. Installing and configuring NginX reverse proxy and static file server
5. Installing and configuring Redis server as a cache mechanism and a message broker

9.2.5 Results

The current situation is that NORD has successfully integrated approximately 250 sensors from the communal water supply network, and a few household-sensors (Techni). Approximately 1+ Months of data has been accumulated from the communal water supply network and a few weeks of household water consumption data. The Environment dashboard (#30) currently displaying data from a selected zone, and additional zones are in the work. Further work with developing the dashboard is needed to enhance the user experience.

NORD has also established a working API for other third parties to collect data. This is done on a request basis. Nessie system (#29) will be provided with their own unique access.

SINTEF & NTNU have received API access and begun retrieving data from the TECHNI sensors through NORD. SINTEF use case has been developed with the *Streamlit* library which allows to create simple interactive tools in Python. The Bodø's meters data can be retrieved by the user for a specified period. The weekly water balance can be automatically calculated based on the average flow recorded at the different relevant locations at the boundaries of the considered DMA or system. In fact, relevant sensors data, stored within the Environmental Dashboard, are linked in the back end with the different components of the water balance according to the IWA methodology. As a demonstration, the user interface to import weekly data is illustrated in the following figure.

Figure 138: Import data page developed for the use case of the Environmental Dashboard.

The inputs for the calculation of a water balance can be overwritten by the user, displaying in real time the results provided with the given variations. For illustration purposes, an image with an example of a water balance displayed in the front-end of the developed web-application is shown in the following Figure.

Figure 139: Water balance calculator page developed for the use case of the Environmental Dashboard.

From the *Water Balance Calculator* page, the web-application allows the user to save multiple water balances related to different periods to allow the comparison of the water balance components over time in the *Historical Water Balances* page, as shown in the following figure.

Figure 140: Historical water balances page developed for the use case of the Environmental Dashboard.

9.3 Lessons extracted

9.3.1 GDPR Documentation

Creating GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) documentation is a timely process that requires a high level of collaboration between partners. These documents are critical to the installation process of smart water meters. It's recommended to begin the process as early as possible and having experienced legal and technical advisors assist in the process of creating the documentation.

Personal data used in the LL Bodø's smart water meter case study include real-time logging of water flow data, water pressure data, battery voltage, water temperature data, ambient temperature, as well as homeowner users interface's usernames and passwords, number of residents per address, house size, locational data, and water meter unit ID. GDPR law denotes that if personal data is being processed, data controllers and data processors must

create a DPA (data processor agreement), a risk analysis, and homeowner's informed written consent contracts ready before any data can be transferred or installation can occur.

9.3.1.1 Data flow chart

Creating a data flow chart and updating throughout the processes of DPAs' creation is extremely beneficial. As seen in the Figure 137, transferring data between LL partners is a complex process. It must be first clarified what data each LL partner will be receiving and the purpose for obtaining this information. Afterwards the discussion of how data will be transferred must be described in detail. Each process must be closely analysed and scrutinized to ensure that data is securely transferred, processed, and stored.

It is worth noting that in the case of installing smart water meters outside of research proposes, the transferring and storing of data will be simpler as it should involve a lesser number of parties.

9.3.1.2 Data Processor Agreements

DPA agreements denote the purpose of processing the data and the security measures implemented to ensure the protection of personal data. Data minimization is a high priority of DPAs as it is the best measure to lowering the consequences in the case of a data breach. The purpose of processing data must be deemed sufficient to receive the data. The security measures are highly technical and requires IT knowledge to describe the planned security measures such as storage details, encryption, pseudonymisation, confidentiality, programs, identification, authorization, logging, restoration plans, data transfer details, testing, audits, evaluations and/or other technical information regarding security. The security measures listed in the DPA are implemented in a risk analysis and lower the risk of worst-case scenarios.

The highest risk through the installation of smart water meters is unauthorized personnel accessing real time water flow data and locational data. This would grant unauthorized personnel awareness to occupancy patterns of homeowners. Thus, it's critical that a high level of data minimization and security measures details listed to lower risk and consequences to the lowest amount possible while still obtaining enough data to complete the objectives of research. The process of DPA creation can take time and requires close collaboration between data controllers and data processors.

In the case of LL Bodø's smart water meter case study, BODO was the data controller and three separate agreements were created with NORD, NTNU and ICCS. Another degree of complexity added was the collaboration with members outside of Norway, as the existing DPA template used by Bodø kommune was only in Norwegian. Due to the technicalities of legal documents, we could not directly translate the existing Norwegian document. The EU's English DPA template was used for the research partner outside of Norway.

9.3.1.3 Risk Analysis

A risk analysis consists of worst-case scenarios of data breaches and listed measures to minimize the probability and consequence of an event occurring. Security measures taken must be included in the DPA. If the risk cannot be lowered to an acceptable level, further documentation will be needed. Thankfully, this was not the case for the smart water meter pilot case study.

9.3.1.4 Homeowner consent contracts

Homeowners must give explicit consent before installation takes place. The contract must use clear easily readable language that allows homeowners to fully understand what they are consenting to.

In the case of dwellings with multiple addresses or one address sharing multiple water meters, all homeowners must consent to installation. In Bodø it is not mandatory for inhabitants to have water meters installed. The majority of inhabitants pay for water by the meters squared area of the residence. Thus, it may be possible that older houses originally built as a single dwelling and were later split into split dwellings do not have the pipe infrastructure to install multiple smart water meters. In this case, multiple addresses under a single residence would share a water meter. This complicates giving data to homeowners through the homeowner's interface, as neighbors would then be able to see each other's water usage. They could then deduct neighbors' occupancy which poses safety and ethical issues.

A possible solution is only providing daily water usage data without hourly information or denying use of the homeowner's interface entirely. Before installation of water meters, it's important to be prepared for all scenarios and use best judgement. These details regarding data shown in the homeowner's interface would need to be detailed and would entail creating a separate homeowner's contract of consent for this case scenario.

The area of installation has a mixture of older and newer houses. LL Bodø has decided to not install the smart water meters in the case of multiple addresses sharing one water meter until further consultation and preparation is completed.

9.4 Summary table of the LL

Table 39: Summary table for LL Bodø

Title	Bodø, Norway
Description	B-WaterSmart Living Lab Bodø has been launched a pilot study to improve the identification of infiltration and leaks in municipal water systems. Smart water meters have been paired with sewer flow meters in a selected area to gather high-quality temporal data. The data will be analysed using advanced algorithms and visualized on dashboards to provide insights into water usage patterns, potential leaks, and other anomalies. This approach is expected to enhance the efficiency of water management

	and conservation efforts and pave the way for more sustainable water systems. Bodø kommune has high ambitions of increasing awareness of water infrastructure and water usage by hosting local events and supporting the development of water-smart technologies.
Reference point	https://goo.gl/maps/gt2tKpBcoMxrCj1T8
Location	Bodø, Norway
Country (-ies)	Norway
URL	https://b-watersmart.eu/living-lab/bodo-norway/
Project	B-WaterSmart Project
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High drinking water demand due to dense or growing resident population and economy, • Untapped efficiency potential of water resources
Tools/Product/Services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nessie System (#29) • Environmental Dashboard (#30)
Technologies	Data collection and aggregations, Smart metering
Scales	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local (e.g., single treatment plant, industrial site or city quarter), • City (whole city level).
Legislation	General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) requires a high degree of detailed security measures and details regarding purpose for use of data before municipalities can share personal data regarding flow consumption measured in homeowners' homes.
Synergistic benefits	Not applicable yet.
Facts of the applied technologies	Not applicable yet.
Key Performance Indicators	<p>Improved water use efficiency is an expected impact of the project by increasing awareness of water usage from homeowners. No data is produced yet.</p> $\text{Improved water efficiency} = \frac{\text{Average water consumption in pilot area}}{\text{Municipal average water consumption}}$
Requirements and conditions	At the moment data availability is the governing constraint.
Key lessons	Not applicable yet.
Lessons learned from technology operation	Installation of Smart water meters is unable to take place until the data processor agreements are completed. This should be done as early as possible to speed up the installation process.
Technology performance and best practices	To be seen in the demonstration phase of the technologies.
Outcome of assessments	Not applicable yet.

Organisations	Bodø kommune, NTNU, NORD, ICCS, Techni															
Contact persons	Rachelle Collette, rachelle.collette@bodo.kommune.no , Bodø kommune, Living lab Bodø project leader															
Data Manager	Rachelle Collette, rachelle.collette@bodo.kommune.no Bodø kommune, Living lab Bodø project leader															
Costs	Not applicable yet.															
Tags	Water usage, leakage, I/I, user information, dashboards, households, smart meters															
Publications/Reference	Not yet applicable.															
Images	<p style="font-size: small;">Display the ratio between sensor values and an atomic variable Customize</p> </div> </div>	#	Sensor	Value	Timestamp	Flag	1	Water Flow	435	2022-02-01 13:45	Error	2	Water Turbidity	5.2	2022-02-01 11:24	OK
#	Sensor	Value	Timestamp	Flag												
1	Water Flow	435	2022-02-01 13:45	Error												
2	Water Turbidity	5.2	2022-02-01 11:24	OK												

10 Conclusions

The aim of B-WaterSmart is to accelerate the transformation to water-smart economies and societies in coastal Europe and beyond. Among other results that the project delivers to achieve this objective, different smart data applications have been released to support more efficient and safe allocation and use of resources.

D3.4 reports the early release of 10 such applications (developed in tasks T3.2 – T3.7 in collaboration with the Living Labs) as parts of the monitoring, negotiation and decision support solutions toolkit. The 10 tools have been applied and tested in 4 LLs. Those are Venice, Alicante, Flanders and Lisbon. Summary and concluding remarks on the 10 tools of D3.4 are provided below. These are considered to be preliminary conclusions, as the tools will continuously be applied (and optimised where necessary) throughout the project duration:

The **Water reuse strategic platform (tool #16)** and **Sludge management platform (tool #19)**, developed by leveraging components from the **Digital Enabler (tool #32)**, have the overall objective of identifying different valorisation pathways for both resources (water and sludge) based on the most sustainable option (from both environmental and economic perspectives), to support the users in the decision-making process with an objective and standardized evaluation also contextualized on the territory of interest. The overall aim of the water reuse strategic platform is to enable freshwater saving and wastewater reuse (WWR). It is an evaluation support system for identifying the optimum reuse opportunities of the treated municipal wastewater based on context and territorial data. In a complementary manner, the aim of the sludge management platform is to support the identification of the optimum sewage sludge (from municipal wastewater treatment) valorisation strategy to foster resource reuse/recovery either towards agricultural application or energy production. The platform allows evaluation and ranking of treatment options and valorisations, considering information from different contexts. With regard to the Venice case, tool #16 allows freshwater saving and general purified wastewater reuse, by analysing potential water reuse opportunities and supporting the users in the decision-making process with a standardized scheme of evaluation, contextualized on the territory of interest, whereas tool #19 fosters sewage sludge valorisation, by analysing in a standardized manner the state of the art of sludge and by considering/weighing the best related treatment and valorisation solutions, to support the decision-making processes, also in relation to the territorial context. As to some preliminary lesson extracted in developing the two platforms, continuous involvement of territorial stakeholders is a key enabling factor for customizing the tools with respect to the specific characteristics of the case study. This is particularly important for what concerns data collection and preparation. Moreover, the sharing of relevant data/information can have political, role and risk implications which are delicate (and could be critical) which require a lot of communication and mediation skills and are time consuming. Making an IT tool of this magnitude requires objective attention and adequate time both in the preliminary phase and in the development phase.

The **RE-ACTOR Tool (tool #18)** is a DSS for the evaluation of new investments and actions related to water reuse and water treatment. The tool allows simulating alternative scenarios in a territory to explore potential impacts related to different actuations, such as new processes in a WWTP, installation of renewable technologies or new reclaimed water distribution infrastructure to supply new users with reclaimed water. The web-based digital solution allows the quantification of the impacts and benefits related to a full-scale implementation of the technical solutions evaluated within the B-WaterSmart as well as other solutions that could promote water-smartness in the region. These results allow the prioritisation of most promising scenarios as well as the demonstration and communication to relevant stakeholders, of the impacts and benefits for a water-smart region. The case study has focused on two wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) in the Alicante region: 1) Rincón de León and 2) Monte Orgegia WWTPs. Both plants are expected to receive upgrades even though at pilot plant during the implementation of B-WaterSmart. It needs to be highlighted that the results have a certain degree of uncertainty; this characteristic is intentionally assumed in order to avoid the model of “data-hungry” applications that need extensive analysis just for providing a preliminary depiction of the investment scenarios. On the other hand, further efforts will need to be dedicated to refining the back-end database, since this component is fed with available data related to the technologies, and in several situations (those associated with some of the most innovative solutions) this data is not yet made available.

The **Nessie System (tool #29)** is a complete digital solution for the collection, harmonization, processing, storing and visualisation of big amounts of high-resolution data from any IoT agents and 3rd party client applications, such as web applications, sensors, or smart meters. Nessie currently provides a series of built-in analytics to support, among others, forecasts, anomaly detection and alerting, optimization of urban systems, advice provision, as well as some more case-specific functionalities, e.g., hydraulic simulation of open-channel systems, modelling of wastewater treatment processes. In the framework of BWS, Nessie system is being expanded to meet the requirements and needs of Bodø case, focusing on the development of a digital platform that allows householders to monitor and manage the water consumption of their household. Also, at the Bodø case, the **Environmental dashboard (#30)** has been developed with a view to present data sources in maps and graphs. Data has been aggregated and gives a picture of water consumption in the different districts, thus representing a complementary tool with respect to #29. The professional interface of the Environmental Dashboard can help to detect leakages in the network for drinking water. The public interface of the tool supports LL Bodø in reducing water usage by raising awareness. As a general lesson extracted from the development of both tools, installation of smart water meters is unable to take place until the data processor agreements are completed. This should be done as early as possible to speed up the installation process.

The **Environment for decision support and alternative course selection (tool #17)** is a multi-criteria decision framework designed to enable direct assessment, comparison and prioritization of decisional alternatives. In the context of the project, it is applied to the final prioritization between the supply/ demand matchmaking alternatives developed in Tool #25 and qualified by Tools #24 and #27, reported in D3.5. It enables users to select the best water source combinations to satisfy specific non-potable uses, and enables prioritizing strategic and tactical planning options on the management of water sources and water uses in an urban setting. The supply/demand alternative combinations are assessed through a range of standardized, user-selected performance, risk, and cost metrics, complementing those employed to qualify the initial selection in Tool #25 (e.g., volume availability, cost, energy content, carbon footprint, nutrient content). To ensure the alignment of decisions for improving water supply/demand management with the Lisbon LL Strategic Agenda, the metrics correspond as much as possible to metrics integrated in the B-WaterSmart Evaluation Framework (Tool #34) or else contribute to their calculation.

The **Urban Water Cycle Observatory of Lisbon (tool #20)** is another tool applied in the Lisbon LL. It is a data visualization instrument to systematise, collect and facilitate access to data on the city water cycle. It allows to monitor and communicate performance, support urban planning and decision making. Following the motto “to know so to reduce”, the Observatory is integrated in the scope of Lisbon city's sustainability policies, covering water and wastewater dimensions, as well also other environmental dimensions of the city, namely energy consumption, urban waste management, greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions and mobility. This Observatory includes two complementary tools: i) a public access tool, with open data information of the water and wastewater city dimensions (top-down approach); ii) a private access tool, for individual entities to integrate and analyse, via a set of analytics, the water consumption data of their facilities (bottom-up approach). Its public access component provides visually appealing information on the urban water cycle (including the consumption of drinking water, the treatment of wastewater and the production and use of reclaimed water) as a means of increasing citizens' water literacy, hoping to make them more willing to be active agents in managing water demand in the city. In 2022, there were 8500 visits to the website and until 22/06/2022, 7200 visits were registered. Its private access component can help those responsible for large water consumption (municipality and private institutions of public interest) to be more efficient in managing water use in those facilities. Processing raw data from smart meters by typology of use provides useful information.

One last tool applied in the Lisbon LL is the **Climate-readiness certification tool (tool #33)**, is an online assessment platform that calculates and issues the Climate-ready certificate (CRC), combining three dimensions: water efficiency, water-energy nexus and climate adaptation in one certificate. The CRC can be applied to residential and small service/commercial buildings, as well as to “neighbourhoods” considering both the buildings

and outdoor areas within the frontier established for the neighbourhood. The evaluated projects can be in different stages: design, new construction, or in-use. The underpinning methodology has been tested in one neighbourhood (Praça de Entrecampos), three buildings (in Praça de Entrecampos, Bairro da Boavista and ADENE's), four detached houses (three in Bairro da Boavista and one in Seixal) and thirteen households/dwellings in multi-family apartments (nine in Praça de Entrecampos, two in Bairro da Boavista, one in Peniche and one in Carcavelos). The detailed results of this exercise will be presented in the report for MS32 (due in month 45).

The storm-water management tool (tool #21), is a management tool to control water level in the basin and optimal distribution to the irrigation system based on water level, water demand, and weather prediction of precipitation/storm events (for flood protection too). The tool is used in the Flanders case to control the outflow from the basin and the water distribution for irrigation, so as to optimize the functioning of the basin for flood prevention and availability of water for irrigation during dry periods. The tool is intended to be used to control the basin inlet and outlet and distribute irrigation water to fields based on water availability and demand. Tool #21 is based on the specific design parameters and local situation of the stormwater management system and has a local scale. Nevertheless, the interplay of these two objectives (flood volume retention vis-à-vis coverage of agriculture needs) can be explored using water systems modelling.

Further to the above tools documented in detail in D3.4, 10 more software solutions are reported in D3.5, as part of the final release of the water cycle modelling and assessment solutions toolkit. The two deliverables have been prepared in parallel to ensure alignment and consistency among the approaches and contents and in order to highlight the toolkits' complementarity. Such complementarity is defined by a high-level process, described in detail in Chapter 4 and summarized in Table 40 which is a reference procedural framework for using the toolkits through the fundamental steps that have to be followed by people who aim at improving the water smartness smartness of their systems. In particular, while the monitoring, negotiation and decision support solutions toolkit aims at improving water smartness by supporting the steps of context awareness, decision making, management and monitoring and certification, the toolkit presented in D3.5 is focused on advanced analytics for providing detailed evidence in support of the decision-making step. This is achieved by providing the tools to conduct simulations, predictions, demand/supply match-making and other analyses (Table 40). Additionally, the two toolkits aim at providing solutions to assist in coping with the water related challenges (Figure 142) and to support each step of the urban water cycle while complementing each other, as depicted in Figure 142 and Figure 143.

Table 40: Overview of toolkits' solutions and apps used in the LLs

	Alicante (Spain)	Bodø (Norway)	East Frisia (Germany)	Flanders (Belgium)	Lisbon (Portugal)	Venice (Italy)
Context awareness		(#30) Environmental Dashboard ¹			(#20) UWC observatory ¹	(#16) Water reuse strategic platform, enabled by Digital Enabler (#32) ¹ (#19) Sludge management platform, enabled by Digital Enabler (#32) ¹
Advanced analysis			(#22) UWOT ²	(#22) UWOT ²	(#25) Water-energy-phosphorous balance planning module ²	
			(#23) Regional demand supply matching GIS tool ²	(#26) QMRA+ for water reuse and agriculture ²	(#24) Reclaimed water distribution network water quality model ²	
			(#28) Short-term demand forecasting tool ²	(#31) SuTRa ²	(#27) Risk assessment for urban water reuse module ²	
Decision making	(#18) Re-Actor ¹				(#17) Environment for decision support and alternative course selection ¹	
Management/monitoring		(#29) Nessie system ¹		(# 21) Stormwater reuse management system ¹		
Certification					(#33) Climate-readiness certification toolkit ¹	

¹The monitoring, negotiation and decision support solutions toolkit

²The water cycle modelling and assessment solutions toolkit

Figure 141: 18 solutions of the 2 toolkits related to the urban water challenges.

Figure 142: Tools of the water cycle modelling and assessment solutions toolkit supporting each step of the urban water cycle

Figure 143: 18 solutions of the 2 toolkits related to the urban water cycle steps

Beyond complementarity of the two toolkits, replicability of the digital tools in other cities/regions is ensured by different actions and results that T3.8 is pursuing, by interacting with the rest of the project. In particular, D3.1 has delivered at M20 the BWS FIWARE approach with its interoperability guidelines (implementation guidelines, FIWARE and interoperability maturity levels) that aim to help developers conceive and realize tools that are easily integrated with third party systems through the use of open and standard APIs, thus boosting replicability. T3.8 and the corresponding deliverables D3.4 / D3.5 make reference to the results of D3.1 and in particular to the “interoperability maturity levels” to document the readiness of each tool to be integrated with other systems and its (potential for) FIWARE compatibility.

More than 1/3 of WP3 applications are or will be FIWARE compatible. More in detail, WP3 delivers 19 applications (18 from T3.2-T3.7 - reported in the toolkits’ deliverables D3.2/D3.3 and 1 from T3.9 - based on information from D3.1) out of which 7 are FIWARE compliant. The tools that have been developed in T3.2-T3.7 and are FIWARE compatible are the following: water-reuse strategic platform (#16), sludge management platform (#19), short-term demand forecasting tool (#28), Nessie System (#29), Environmental Dashboard (#30) and Digital Enabler (#32). Most of them are described in detail in D3.4, whereas the short-term demand forecasting tool (#28) can be found under section 5.7 of D3.5.

Moreover, beyond investigating the need for conducting tactical joint meetings between WP3/WP2/WP1/WP7 to better align efforts, replicability is supported by several synergies with such WPs that have been activated and will be further enhanced by:

- Intensifying discussion and exchange among the technology/tool developers in joint WP2/WP3 meetings and conducting additional ones upon demand;
- Allocating efforts for continuous collaboration with WP1 in developing training material and conducting training activities (possibly inviting also CoP members and not only project’s colleagues). Most of the training activities are planned for the last year of the project when developments of tools are mature.
- Using recordings of training actions on tools and disseminating them through the colleagues’ networks and WP7 (website, social media and Marketplace). Training activities have already taken place and the produced material is available in the WE Marketplace (under the detailed page of each tool - - <https://mp.watereurope.eu/l/Product/>) and on the project’s website (<https://b-watersmart.eu/>).
- Highlighting replicability aspects and opportunities in the LLs work, and communicating reports to a broader audience via WP7 (website, social media and Marketplace, e.g., information available in the case study section documenting lessons learned from tools’ applications, etc.)

As next steps, contents related to results and lessons extracted for each LL after an extended application of the BWS digital tools will be updated through the new MS32 which is suggested to be added at month 45.

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13 Annex A: Technology Readiness Level

Where a topic description refers to a TRL, the following definitions apply, unless otherwise specified:

Level	Description
Level 1 - Basic Research: basic principles are observed and reported	Lowest level of technology readiness. Scientific research begins to be translated into applied research and development. Examples might include fundamental investigations and paper studies.
Level 2 – Applied Research: technology concept and/or application formulated	Once basic principles are observed, practical applications can be formulated. Examples are limited to analytic studies and experimentation.
Level 3 – Critical function, proof of concept established	Active research and development is initiated. Laboratory studies aim to validate analytical predictions of separate components of the technology. Examples include components that are not yet integrated or representative.
Level 4 – Laboratory testing of prototype component or process	Design, development and lab testing of technological components are performed. Here, basic technological components are integrated to establish that they will work together. This is a relatively “low fidelity” prototype in comparison with the eventual system.
Level 5 – Laboratory testing of integrated system	The basic technological components are integrated together with realistic supporting elements to be tested in a simulated environment. This is a “high fidelity” prototype compared to the eventual system.
Level 6 – Prototype system verified	The prototype, which is well beyond that of level 5, is tested in a relevant environment. The system or process demonstration is carried out in an operational environment.
Level 7 – Integrated pilot system demonstrated	Prototype is near, or at, planned operational system level. The final design is virtually complete. The goal of this stage is to remove engineering and manufacturing risk.
Level 8 – System incorporated in commercial design	Technology has been proven to work in its final form under the expected conditions. In most of the cases, this level represents the end of true system development.
Level 9 – System ready for full scale deployment	Here, the technology in its final form is ready for commercial deployment.

Level beyond 9 - Market introduction

The product, process or service is launched commercially, marketed to and adopted by a group of customers (including public authorities).

14 Annex B: Template tables

Below there are the template tables that have been used in previous sections for the description of tools and their application to the different cases studies. Instructions of anticipated information are included in each field. It is noted that the definition of those tables and their fields has been done in collaboration with WP7. The collected information will be used to populate the Water Europe Marketplace (aka. the Knowledge Portal of WP7, Task 7.1).

Table XY: Template table for tool's attributes and description

Tool's attribute	Description
Type of product	Select which of the following statements describe best your product. You may choose more than one statement. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A software supporting the Circular Economy A hardware product or a technological device around the Circular Economy A service, offered as part of a Circular Economy enabling portfolio A methodology or a process related with the Circular Economy
Name	Name of the tool/product.
Description	General information on the product, its components and the scope of application
Abbreviation	The acronym/abbreviation of the tool/product (if available)
URL	Related URL, providing further information on the product/tool, if available
Costs	If applicable, describe the costs and conditions for purchasing the product, obtaining a license or providing the service
Target audience	Profile of users who would find the tool/product useful or/and are qualified to use it.
Actors, roles and interactions	Actors involved (e.g., water utilities, industries, technology providers, end-users), their roles and their interactions.
Unique selling points /Added Value/Innovation	Description of the unique selling points, added value and innovation elements of the tool, product or service
TRL	The Technology Readiness Level (TRL) giving an estimate of the technology maturity of the related tool, product or service.
Technical requirements	Technical requirements to obtain, install or run the tool, product or service
Environment	Operating environment in which the tool/application runs e.g., Microsoft Windows (if applicable)
Version	Current stable version number or version code of the tool, product or service (if applicable)
Initial release	Year of the initial release of the tool (if applicable)
License type	General license type (free or commercial) (if applicable)

Programming language/technologies used		<i>The programming languages or/and major technologies which are used to implement the tool/application (if applicable).</i>
Open interface		<i>Describe the different integrations options, if any, which are supported by the tool/product e.g., web service, libraries, etc. (if applicable)</i>
Graphical Interface / Headless software	User	<i>Describe if the tool can be executed in headless mode, batch mode, if it is command line executed and/or if it has GUI, etc. (if applicable)</i>
Supported scales	spatial	<i>Different spatial scales that can be supported by the tool and applied e.g., household, neighbourhood, city, region, etc. (if applicable)</i>
Supported scales	temporal	<i>Different temporal scales that can be supported by the tool and applied e.g., daily, annual, etc. (if applicable)</i>
Water Use Types		<i>Indicate the water use types with which the tool is related e.g., urban, industrial, rural and agriculture</i>
Compatibility FIWARE	with	<i>Indicate whether the tool is compatible with FIWARE or not.</i>
Organisations		<i>Organisation(-s) that own the tool, product or service.</i>
Contact details		<i>Contact details of the person related to the tool, product or service. Needs to include at least first name, last name and email.</i>
Data Manager		<i>Indicate the persons who will be responsible to monitor and update the information about the tool/product/service in the Water Europe Marketplace (https://mp.watereurope.eu/l/Product/). Include the contact details by providing at least first name, last name and email.</i>
Technologies		<i>Circular economy technologies related with the tool, product or service. You may examine the Overview of Technologies available in the Water Europe Marketplace (https://mp.watereurope.eu/technologies/) and select among them or add new technologies in order to be included.</i>
Tags		<i>Tags related with the tool, product or service.</i>
Images		<i>Characteristic images or schematic representations of the tool. In case where the file is provided as a separate file, all known formats up to a certain size which are supported by web browsers are accepted (e.g., jpeg, png). The file must not exceed the size of 5MB.</i>
Caption/Source		<i>Caption needs to be provided for each illustration in textual format, as well as its reference/source that should be included.</i>
Publications		<i>Publications related with the tool, product or service</i>

Table XX: Template table for the application of tools/technologies to case studies and LL

Indicative application of the tool	
Title	<i>Title of the case study where the tool/product/service is applied.</i>
Description	<i>Brief description of the application of the tool/product/service to the case study/Living Lab.</i>
Reference point	<i>Indicate a point location that best represents the application of the tool to the Case Study/Living Lab by sharing a Google's maps location link.</i>
Location	<i>The name of the city /area/geographical location which best represents the application of the tool to the Case Study/Living Lab.</i>
Country (-ies)	<i>Countries hosting the case study/Living Lab where the tool has been applied.</i>

URL	Related URL, providing further information on the application of product/tool to the Case Study/Living Lab, if available
Project	Related project where the application of tools to the Case Study/Living Lab has been applied (if applicable)
Challenges	Select the challenges that are addressed through the application of tools and/or technologies. Multiple selection can be made: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water Scarcity, • Limitations to water reuse due to high salinity/nitrates, • Limitations to water reuse and recovery due to low acceptance, • High drinking water demand due to dense or growing resident population and economy, • Untapped efficiency potential of water resources, • High or increasing irrigation water demand for agriculture, • Groundwater overexploitation, • Water quality deterioration, • Dependent on distant freshwater resources, • Increasing water demand by growing industrial sectors, • Need for reuse and recovery schemes for wastewater & sludge, • Other
Tools/Product/Services	Tools/Product/Services that have been applied in the case study/Living Lab.
Technologies	Circular economy technologies related with the tool, product or service. You may examine the Overview of Technologies available in the Water Europe Marketplace (https://mp.watereurope.eu/technologies/) and select among them or add new technologies in order to be included.
Scales	Typical operational scales of this case study/Living Lab related to the application of tool(-s)/technology(-ies), i.e., the scales at which the solutions/technologies are implemented and have an impact.: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local (e.g., single treatment plant, industrial site or city quarter), • City (whole city level), • Metropolitan (extending beyond the city e.g., into neighbouring cities or peri-urban fringe area), • Regional (across several municipalities and/or administrative borders, incl. rural areas), • National (relating to a whole country), • Other
Legislation	EU/National/Regional/Local regulations that are related to the application of tools/technologies to the LLs e.g., limits of quality parameters of reused water, etc (if applicable).
Synergistic benefits	Description of the synergistic benefits that came along from the application of the tool/product/services to the case study and its combination with other tool(s) and/or related technologies.
Facts of the applied technologies	Capacity, production rate or yield, energy consumption, CAPEX, OPEX. (If applicable, related to the technologies and the WP2 work).
Key Performance Indicators	KPIs for every technology and comparison to the situation before its implementation (if applicable, related to the technologies and the WP2 work).
Requirements and conditions	Requirements, conditions or constraints that might have been encountered for the application of the tool/product/service in the case study.
Key lessons	Brief textual description of the key lessons learned from the application of tools to the case study and the potential combined used of technologies/tools.
Lessons learned from technology operation	Required competence, maintenance, technological risk (downtimes and its avoidance). If applicable, related to the technologies and the WP2 work.

Best practices	<i>Best practice guidelines to construct and operate the applied technologies (if applicable, related to the technologies and the WP2 work).</i>
Outcome assessments	<i>of LCA, LCC, QMRA, QCRA, Technical RA, etc. (if applicable, related to the technologies and the WP2 work)</i>
Organisations	<i>Entities which are involved in the case study/Living Lab.</i>
Contact persons	<i>Contact persons for this case study where the tool/product has been applied. Needs to include at least first name, last name, email and organisation.</i>
Data Manager	<i>Indicate the persons who will be responsible to monitor and update the information about the application of the tool/product/service to the specific case study/LL in the Water Europe Marketplace (https://mp.watereurope.eu/l/CaseStudy). Include the contact details by providing at least first name, last name and email.</i>
Costs	<i>Approximate costs for tool/technology implementation including e.g., purchase, setup, etc.</i>
Tags	<i>Keywords that capture knowledge about the specific case study/Living Lab and the application of the tool.</i>
Publications/Reference	<i>Issued publications that refer to the application of tool/technology to the case study/Living Lab.</i>
Images	<i>Characteristic images or schematic representations of the tools' applications to the Case Study/Living Lab. In case provided as a separate file, all known formats up to a certain size which are supported by web browsers are accepted (e.g., jpeg, png). The file must not exceed 5MB in size.</i>
Caption/Source	<i>Caption needs to be provided for each illustration in textual format, as well as its reference.</i>

15 Annex C: Summary table of the tools documented in D3.4/D3.5

#No.	Tool name (leading partners)	Living Lab using the tool	Deliverable
16	Water reuse strategic platform (VERI/ENG)	Venice	D3.4
17	Environment for decision support and alternative course selection (BASE)	Lisbon	D3.4
18	Re-Actor (CET, AMA)	Alicante	D3.4
19	Sludge management platform (VERI/ENG)	Venice	D3.4
20	UWC observatory (Lisboa E-Nova, third party linked to CML)	Lisbon	D3.4
21	Stormwater reuse management system (AQUAFIN/VITO)	Flanders	D3.4
22	UWOT (ICCS/KWR)	Flanders/East Frisia	D3.5
23	Regional Demand-Supply Matching GIS tool (IWW)	East Frisia	D3.5
24	Reclaimed water distribution network water quality model (BASEFORM)	Lisbon	D3.5
25	Water-energy-P balance planning module (BASEFORM)	Lisbon	D3.5
26	QMRA+ (KWR)	Flanders	D3.5
27	RA-Reuse (BASEFORM)	Lisbon	D3.5
28	Short-Term Demand Forecasting Tool (IWW)	East Frisia	D3.5
29	Nessie System (ICCS/NTUA)	Bodø	D3.4
30	Environmental Dashboard (Nordkontakt AS)	Bodø	D3.4
31	SuTRa (KWR) (former ASR-pro tool)	Flanders	D3.5
32	Digital Enabler (ENG)	Venice	D3.4
33	Climate-readiness certification tool (ADENE)	Lisbon	D3.4

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